

Developing metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts on the environment and society

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Executive summary

Citizen science involves members of the public in the generation and application of scientific knowledge. (A full definition of *citizen science* is provided later.) The MICS project developed methods and tools to help citizen-science projects reflect on and measure their impacts. These reflections and measurements should help projects to achieve more positive-impact. MICS included several case studies which brought together community groups and local authorities to co-design new citizen-science initiatives around nature-based solutions. In Italy, school children and other locals monitored wetlands’ impacts on the Marzenego River’s water quality. They also developed their own method for measuring levels of bacteria. In Romania, citizen scientists investigated the impact of Danube-wetland restoration on water quality and bank stability. The project, in Hungary, surveyed water quality and biodiversity to promote the restoration of Creek Rákos. In the UK, MICS worked with two established citizen-science projects, Outfall Safari and Riverfly, to evaluate their impacts. The MICS project also developed a platform to help all citizen-science projects assess their impacts. MICS considers the impact of citizen science in several areas (or domains): society, the environment, the economy, governance, and science and technology. MICS found that citizen-science projects improve engagement and promote a scientific mentality, contributing to achieving the UN’s sustainable development goals and discussing about a sustainable future. Before MICS, it was not easy to accurately measure the impact of citizen science. The MICS project has developed a web-based platform to do that. With the platform’s help, users can assess whether a project has had an impact

on several domains. The MICS platform is free to use, and any citizen-science project can register on the platform to assess its impact. All results are available to the public. The impact-assessment process on the MICS platform includes over 200 questions, each with a pre-defined set of answers that users can choose from. These questions capture so-called input features and are based on current impact-assessment methods and other frameworks such as the ECSA characteristics of citizen science. (More details about the relation between MICS and the *ECSA characteristics of citizen science* are provided later.) Each project's answers are analysed by an artificial-intelligence algorithm, Alquimics, which generates impact scores. The MICS platform also provides projects with recommendations on improving impact across several domains and an assessment of their impact on the UN's sustainable development goals. Finally, the MICS platform can analyse a project at any stage of development and can be used to inform ongoing activities to improve impact.

Definitions

citizen science, *n.* Work undertaken by civic educators together with citizen communities to advance science, foster a broad scientific mentality, or encourage democratic engagement, which allows society to deal rationally with complex modern problems (Ceccaroni et al., 2017)

ECSA characteristics of citizen science, *n.* Features set out to address the questions “what is citizen science?” and “what is not citizen science?” They consider five areas: core concepts; disciplinary aspects; leadership and participation; financial aspects; and data and knowledge. They can be found here: [<https://zenodo.org/communities/citscicharacteristics>].

impact, *n.* In MICS, impact is a marked change, effect or influence. For example, suppose a project collects scientific observations, and these observations represent a significant change in the number of observations in a particular context. In that case, the project is considered to have an impact on science. Even if impact represents change, in MICS, it is not generally relatable to a so-called *theory of change*.

indicator, *n.* A combination of a set of input features. For example, the “Interdisciplinary science” indicator combines the following two input features: “Which disciplines are the focus of the project’s research?” and “Does the project explicitly promote interdisciplinary ways of working?”.

input feature, *n.* Input features are variables used by the MICS platform. MICS uses some variables as *targets*, or *labels*: these are the impact scores in the five domains. For example, the *impact on Environment* is a target. The remaining variables, about 200, are used as features. The MICS’s machine-learning algorithm’s job is to find how the set of input features can successfully predict the target. Then, for new projects, the platform uses the model (i.e., the machine-learning algorithm) to predict impact based on its input features (input variables). The input features are represented by questions (and answers), such as “Which disciplines are the focus of the project’s research?”.

sustainable development goals (SDGs), *n.* The SDGs are a collection of 17 interlinked global goals designed to be a blueprint for achieving a better and more sustainable future for all [<https://sdgs.un.org/>]. The SDGs were set up in 2015 by the United Nations General Assembly (UN-GA) and are intended to be achieved by 2030. They are included in a UN-GA Resolution called the *2030 Agenda* (or *Agenda 2030*). The SDGs were developed in the Post-2015 Development Agenda as the future global development framework to succeed the Millennium Development Goals, which ended in 2015.

1 Introduction

To evaluate citizen-science impact, what counts as impact must be clarified, and so must the analysis method. In section 2, the analytical approach and framework that have been used throughout the MICS project are presented. The analytical approach is built on previous articles and methodologies published on the subject. While these articles and methods could not demonstrate the potential of a citizen-science impact assessment framework in action, MICS provides an opportunity to do just that, which is documented in this deliverable.

First, the analytical approach for comprehensive and systemic impact analysis in citizen science is presented. This approach has been developed within WP2 and has already been introduced in other deliverables, so this document will mainly provide pointers to those deliverables.

Second, the framework for presenting the results arrived at with such an approach is presented, as developed in the form of a software platform [mics.tools]. The technical aspects of the platform are presented in a WP3 deliverable, while in this document the focus will be on the knowledge management, the input features used for measuring impact, the comprehensiveness of the approach, the role of *artificial intelligence* (AI), and the limitations of the framework. The impact-assessment process on the MICS platform includes over 200 questions, each with a pre-defined set of answers that users can choose from. These questions capture so-called input features and are based on current impact-assessment methods and other frameworks such as the ECSA characteristics of citizen science. Each project's answers are analysed by an artificial-intelligence algorithm, which generates impact scores. The MICS platform also provides projects with recommendations on improving the impact and an assessment of their impact on the *United Nations' sustainable development goals* (SDGs).

Third, the MICS platform is complemented by comprehensive online guidance, which provides insights into the various impacts of citizen science, why it is important to measure them, how citizen-science initiatives can be co-designed for impact, and how to measure their impacts. At [about.mics.tools], the users are guided through available resources such as tools, scientific papers, training materials, and networks and are helped to improve impact assessment.

Finally, the relation between the impact assessment framework and the case-study sites of the project will be presented. Most of this has already been introduced in WP4 deliverables, so this document will mainly provide pointers to those deliverables and explain some of the latest developments.

All the deliverables of the project are described in "Appendix A - MICS deliverables (and descriptions)".

2 A methodology for impact assessment

The impact assessment methods developed by the MICS project have been developed over three phases (depicted in Figure 1). Firstly, in the scoping phase, the existing state of the art with regard to impact assessment in citizen science was considered. This included a literature review and user-requirement interviews with citizen-science project coordinators. In the second phase, the results from the scoping exercises were combined and consolidated in an initial framework for impact assessment. In the third phase, this initial framework was enhanced and further developed in two ways. On the one hand, the details of the impact indicators in the framework were strengthened with insights from impact assessment in disciplines from outside of citizen science. At the same time, the indicators collected in the initial framework were converted into a set of closed questions and corresponding answers and tested with citizen-science project coordinators to ensure they were accessible. The results from these three phases of development have been delivered in the MICS platform [mics.tools] and accompanying website [about.mics.tools], which are described in sections 4 and 5 of this deliverable, respectively.

Figure 1. Visual description of impact assessment methodological development in the MICS project

The details of each of the three phases of methodology development have previously been described in other MICS deliverables and papers and are summarised below.

2.1 Scoping phase

The methodologies for impact assessment developed in the MICS project are firmly based on current best-practice and the state-of-the-art in the field of citizen science. During the scoping phase, the aim was, therefore, to identify current methods for impact assessment. This included selecting reference projects, carrying out an in-depth literature review, and completing user-requirement interviews with citizen-science project coordinators.

To start, 503 projects were screened from the Joint Research Centre’s and the European Commission’s ‘inventory of citizen science activities for environmental policies’ (European Commission, 2018) and 130 projects were shortlisted for further investigation based on their relation to citizen science, nature-based solutions, or impact assessment. Altogether, 24 projects were selected as reference projects to give insights into citizen-science impact assessment and to inform further activities of the MICS project. The screening process and review of the 24 reference projects are described in greater detail in [Deliverable D2.1: Report about identified research results ready for review](#).

To complement the selection of reference projects, an in-depth literature review was carried out. The process of selecting relevant literature for this systematic review was iterative, starting with an initial list of 21 publications identified in [Deliverable D2.2: Report detailing impact-assessment methods adapted to citizen science](#) and adding further publications from searches on Web of Science and Wiley. After screening, a total of 77 publications were included for in-depth review. The results from this review are described in [Deliverable D2.3: Impact-assessment methods adapted to citizen science](#) and a peer-reviewed publication: “[Impact assessment of citizen science: state of the art and guiding principles for a consolidated approach](#)”.

Finally, empirical research was carried out via dedicated, semi-structured interviews with 11 citizen-science project coordinators. The purpose of the interviews was to collect examples of current impact assessment approaches in citizen science as well as to elicit project needs regarding an impact assessment tool. The results from the interviews were used to create a customer profile and value proposition canvas to help shape the design of the MICS platform. The user-requirement interviews are described in both [Deliverable D2.2: Report detailing impact-assessment methods adapted to citizen science](#) and a peer-reviewed publication “[Coordinator Perceptions When Assessing the Impact of Citizen Science towards Sustainable Development Goals](#)”.

2.2 Initial framework creation

Following the scoping phase, a large volume of material had been collected on existing methods for impact assessment in citizen science. The review of these methods revealed strengths to the approaches as well as gaps which the current methods did not cover. On the basis of this review, six guiding principles for an impact assessment framework were written:

1. accommodate a variety of purposes of citizen-science impact assessment;
2. conceptualise non-linear impact journeys rather than impact silos;
3. adopt comprehensive impact-assessment data collection methods and information sources;
4. move beyond absolute impact;
5. foster comparison of impact assessment results across citizen-science projects;
6. enhance the framework over time.

These recommendations are presented in the form of a science brief in [Deliverable D5.3: Recommendations about the assessment of the impact of citizen science](#). The six principles were used to shape the impact indicators identified in the scoping phase into an initial MICS impact assessment framework. The framework consisted of 83 indicators arranged in 19 thematic clusters and associated to the five MICS domains (society, the economy, science and technology, the environment, and governance). The framework is fully described in [Deliverable D2.7: Finalised version of the conceptual framework](#).

2.3 Development phase

Whilst this initial framework provides a comprehensive overview of the current best practice with regard to impact assessment in citizen science, the MICS project aims to go beyond the state of the art in developing a new methodology for impact assessment and to increase the accessibility of impact assessment methods by overcoming the barriers to projects carrying out impact assessment identified in the scoping phase.

To progress impact assessment in the field of citizen science, targeted literature reviews of impact assessment approaches in other disciplines were carried out to enhance the methods available to citizen-science practitioners. A review of best practice in the field of environmental psychology for measuring environmental attitudes, behaviour and knowledge was undertaken and is described in this peer-reviewed publication "[How to measure the impact of citizen science on environmental attitudes, behaviour and knowledge? A review of state-of-the-art approaches](#)". The indicators extracted from this targeted literature review were added to the MICS framework (reported in [Deliverable D2.7: Finalised version of the conceptual framework](#)).

To increase the accessibility of the impact assessment methods identified in the MICS framework, the indicators were converted into closed questions with a corresponding set of answers that citizen-science projects could choose from. The aim was to create a standardised approach to impact assessment which would allow any citizen-science project coordinator to assess impact and characterise their project simply by answering all of these questions. The questions were tested thoroughly through a combination of workshops and interviews, which, over three rounds of testing, resulted in changes to the wording of the questions, the addition of answer options for some questions, and the creation of help and information text to assist users in fully understanding the questions. The process of creating, testing and refining the questions and answers is described in [Deliverable D2.8: Citizen-science model for impact-evaluation research](#) and in this peer-reviewed publication "[A Practical Approach to Assessing the Impact of Citizen Science towards the Sustainable Development Goals](#)". An updated list of questions, answers, help and information text, and sources for each of these questions is provided in section 4 of this deliverable.

2.4 Platform and website

The methodological development described in these three phases has resulted in a comprehensive impact assessment framework along with a new standardised approach for citizen science impact assessment in the form of questions and corresponding answers. These methods have now been applied in a platform for impact assessment, [mics.tools] (described in section 4 of this deliverable) and been made available as detailed guidance in the accompanying website, [about.mics.tools] (described in section 5 of this deliverable).

3 The challenge of evaluating citizen-science impact

3.1 Analytical approach

The MICS project developed a new framework for systematising the analysis of citizen science's impacts by examining the impacts through five domains or dimensions, and in relation to the SDGs. By doing so, the project will be able to measure how citizen science affects the **economy, society, the environment, governance, and science and technology**. From these broad categories, it can delve deeper into a nuanced understanding of citizen-science impact. This framework will allow for more effective public communication and more awareness regarding the impacts of citizen science. The five domains cover a wide range of issues. Still, the project acknowledges that specific issues remain unexplored by considering those domains, and these issues will also be taken into account.

The project will not be able to distinguish different forms of direct citizen-science impacts from indirect ones, and to distinguish among different levels of analysis, like micro, meso, and macro. Nevertheless, these various forms and levels and their roles are acknowledged in the following sections.

3.1.1 Different forms of direct and indirect impacts

In this section, the expressions "direct impacts" and "indirect impacts" are used. This is an important distinction, as citizen science will, in some instances, be used in ways that directly impact the five domains, but it is also characterised by a range of *indirect* impacts. For example, citizen science can directly engender societal benefits, which will, in turn, potentially have significant impacts on efforts to combat poverty (economy domain and SDG 1). The difference between how an impact on one domain leads to impacts on other domains, and direct impacts is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Direct and indirect impacts

There are, however, other forms of indirect impacts, and the impacts just discussed (and in Figure 2) will thus be referred to as *ripple impacts*, as they are characterised by the spread of impacts from original direct impact areas.

Especially in the *Environment* domain, the notion of *scopes* of impacts is also relevant for illustrating how citizen-science impacts can be more or less direct. And it is helpful to consider how one project's actions have an impact both upstream and downstream.

Scope 1 impacts are the direct impacts caused by the project's own development and application of citizen science. This might, for example, entail how a project can use citizen science to clean a river or plant a forest, but also how the travel involved and the use of offices and equipment generate emissions or the generation of waste.

Scope 2 impacts entail considerations regarding the power and electricity, heat, and cooling used to provide those citizen-science solutions. The project might use services external to the organisations involved in the project, and while the emissions resulting from those services are in a sense external to the project, they are directly related to the project's activities and have to be considered an indirect impact from the project. While the project does not produce the emissions directly, the emissions would not exist without the project's activities. (There might be nuances to this point. When considering, for example, the emissions of participants driving or flying to the location of the activities, one can argue that, if they were not driving or flying to participate in the project, they would drive or fly somewhere else to do something else. Even if this is true, it does not completely remove the project's responsibility for those emissions.) Therefore, the additional use of power and the associated emissions must be considered against the positive contributions captured by scope 1.

Scope 3 impacts involve all other impacts caused by the project's upstream and downstream activities. For example, corporate sponsorship of the project or the activities might be considered here. When, for instance, corporations linked to the fossil-fuel industry associate their brand with a citizen-science project, they reinforce their brands and their lobbying power with governments, undermining, delaying and blocking those environmental regulations that are the only way to achieve significant, sustained changes about environmental challenges and health protection. Another aspect to include in the scope-3 impact assessment will be how others use any system developed by a project and the sustainability-related impacts of such usage. Does a model of the ocean developed by a project to improve the management of marine protected areas help others to, for example, extend the exploration for fossil fuel? Is an algorithm developed for species monitoring used for participants' tracking? Do cookies for user management lead to the invasion of participants' privacy? Scope-3 impacts can, of course, also be positive, in that the indirect use of the project's solutions can reinforce the branding of like-minded organisations or, in the specific case of MICS, improve the positive impact of other projects which use the platform.

3.1.2 A systemic and layered approach

With the notion of scopes and impacts external to the project in question, MICS adopted a systemic approach to citizen-science impact. Impacts beyond its direct context will always characterise citizen science's deployment. Seeing citizen science as part of a more extensive socioeconomic system means that citizen science will be assumed to have an impact on the governance and economic systems. At the same time, these systems will also be considered to constrain and guide the evolution of both the design and use of citizen science. To understand the impacts of citizen science, then, its role in and relation to the socioeconomic system must be considered. Doing the opposite entails performing what Barley (2020), in a different context, refers to as *isolationist* analyses. While such analyses might be of some importance, as they provide case studies and use cases that can be considered input to a more

comprehensive analysis, how citizen science is used in “closed” projects (as in closed systems) here is considered to be of minor importance in and of itself, if the broader strategy is not taken into account.

As part of this framework, MICS tried to distinguish between impacts on the micro, meso, and macro levels. Citizen science might, for example, be used to allow individuals to improve their health and nutrition, and such impacts on *individuals* and *small groups* are considered micro-level impacts. Meso-level impacts relate to how citizen science impacts *groups of more significant size*, and it involves considerations of how *large organisations, classes, nations, and even regions* are impacted by citizen science. The macro level is the level of *political, economic, and production systems*, and the impact at this level is the *long-term* impact of citizen science on the economies and societies in the broadest sense. Moving from the micro level to the macro level, we also tend to move from *short-term* to *long-term* considerations of impacts. Similar considerations are also typical of so-called theories of change, which include additional terms such as *outputs* and *outcomes*.

MICS acknowledges that the limitations related to the fuzziness of approaches such as the micro, meso, and macro levels or the theory of change make them currently unusable in a framework that tries to quantify the impact of citizen science. For example, the impact on 300 individuals is not similar to the impact on 300 million individuals. What are small groups? 30 people? 300 people? What are groups of more significant size? 300 people? 300 million people? Regarding nations and regions, the impact on Belgium is not similar to the impact on Africa. What are long-term and short-term? Is “3 years” long or short term?

The framework developed by MICS is very ambitious but realistic enough to be used in the form of a software platform. The introduction (into the platform) of the elements of fuzziness presented in this section would have generated concerns that the project did not have the resources to provide solutions to. We then want to emphasise that this section mainly intends to highlight and force considerations of the wide range of indirect sustainability-related impacts citizen science has. MICS does not use these considerations to provide a final answer that summarises all the impacts of citizen science but provides practitioners with the necessary scope to know where to look to find all critical impacts. A too ambitious framework would, by necessity, entail that it is not possible to go deep into all the details and nuances. MICS chose an ambitious framework; a framework that is vastly more comprehensive than any previously existing one but, at the same time, simple enough to allow all the details of its 200 input features to be considered, to finally provide a realistic and valuable account of the impact of citizen science.

3.2 A framework for systematising citizen-science impacts on the economy, society, the environments, governance, and science and technology

Considering the analytical approach just described, MICS has developed a framework for presenting the results of an impact analysis of a citizen-science project. In previous deliverables, how this framework could be used to evaluate and report on citizen-science—related efforts for organisations has been examined, and there a preliminary version has been presented of the framework that is fully developed in this document. For those interested in using MICS for impact reporting, the recommendation is to use the platform and refer to this document for more detail.

The main feature of the framework for summarising and presenting the results of the analysis is the production of reports such as the one shown in Figure 3. In the following sections, the questions related to how citizen science impacts each domain are presented, along with an overview of the sources that form the basis and support for them.

Figure 3. Summary of citizen-science impacts on five domains

4 A new approach and a platform for impact assessment

In this section, the learnings and analysis of existing impact-assessment frameworks and methodologies discussed so far in this document are reimagined into a new approach for impact assessment. A process of operationalisation is explained, where input features are transformed through an iterative, user-centred process into answerable questions for citizen-science coordinators when considering impact. In parallel, guidance and resources have been created to help practitioners collect the information required to answer these questions when it is not apparent how to do so. The MICS platform is the culmination of this process and the access point to ensure this new approach to impact assessment is accessible and widely exploited.

The platform represents the gateway through which end-users, be they citizen-science practitioners, participants, reviewers, policy makers or other stakeholders, can access the MICS impact-assessment approach, and better understand the strengths and weaknesses of citizen-science projects in terms of impact. It provides a space to discover different citizen-science activities and their attributes, understand and utilise the MICS approach when assessing impact, and review standardised impact scores and outputs to help realise potential impact in the future. Figure 4 shows the home page of the MICS platform [mics.tools].

Figure 4: MICS platform home-page

Whilst the methodologies behind the MICS platform, its functionality and its approach to impact assessment are described in the following, a complete technical description is provided through D3.5: “Participatory adaptive, personalised information-delivery web platform, period-2 prototype (P2P)”. The platform, in July 2022, is considered an initial instance. This is because although it represents the end of a thorough design process, and has been tested to ensure it is suitable for release, it has been designed to be adapted and updated in the future. Important content, including the input features and questions presented to the user, and the recommendations and output produced, have been designed to be fully editable beyond the timeline of the funded project. This allows the MICS platform to evolve with the changing themes and associated priorities of both the citizen-science and impact-assessment fields, ensuring its sustainability and relevance for future citizen-science activities and methodologies.

The MICS platform measures the impact of citizen science on the economy, society, the environment, governance, and science and technology. These domains are related to challenges and threats to societies, and, in terms of challenges and threats to societies, few frameworks communicate their broad and fundamental character better than the idea of *sustainable development*, which is today often related to the SDGs. These goals were launched in 2015 as part of Agenda 2030, and they encompass 17 domains focused on the environment, social justice, economic growth, health, work, and politics.

The basic idea of sustainable development, that we have to satisfy our needs today without jeopardising the needs of future generations, has garnered increasing attention since the Brundtland Commission developed it in 1987. Particularly so since new reports show how humans are incontrovertibly changing and affecting the environments in problematic ways. Particular attention should be devoted to the loss of species (decreasing biodiversity) and various forms of pollution, for example, the vast amounts of plastic in the environments. This is the environmental dimension of sustainability. However, sustainable development as a concept also encompasses the social and economic dimensions, which detail how issues of justice, distribution, and the way economic growth is created are intimately linked to how we affect the potential of future generations.

Citizen science is increasingly heralded as one of the enablers of a better future, and MICS analysed how citizen science can enable and measure the achievement of the SDGs across five domains.

The positive potential of citizen science to help the achievement of the SDGs cannot be neglected. However, it is easy to be dazzled by the stories of citizen-science success, while being blinded to the fact that citizen science might simultaneously be an inhibitor, a distraction, or simply an insignificant factor. The characterisation of citizen science and the challenge of getting to grips with citizen-science impacts have been the focus of MICS. For example, most citizen-science projects use smart devices, such as a smartphone. This enables citizens to keep track of a vast array of aspects related to, for example, the environments, and the more they use these devices, the more helpful they become as data are gathered and citizen science is used to analyse them and provide better monitoring, for example, of water quality, and suggestions for activities that will benefit the aquatic environment. This has to positively impact the SDGs, as SDG 6 is about clean water and sanitation. Superficially, yes, but the real impact might not be particularly large or positive. First of all, the impact might not be that strong. In addition, when it is added that such use of citizen science entails producing (and shipping, and disposing) new sorts of kits or equipment, using energy and computing infrastructure to process data (and produce emissions), and how such technologies can increase the gap between those with the resources to acquire them and those who do not, the positive impact could easily be argued to be marginal at best. SDG 6, when one looks deeper into it, describes things such as “achieving universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all” or “achieving access to adequate

and equitable sanitation and hygiene for all and end open defecation” or “improving water quality by reducing pollution, eliminating dumping and minimising release of hazardous chemicals and materials”. Helping to observe bank vegetation in European rivers through smartphones and the generation of additional emissions does not seem to be the primary focus of the goal.

Impact assessment is complicated, and the purpose of MICS was to present a method for evaluating and making sense of the various impacts of citizen science, and, in particular, how to grasp the interdependence among the economic, social, environmental, governance, scientific and technological dimensions of sustainability. These dimensions are discussed in the following sections.

4.1 Impact on the economy

One of the least-often—discussed ways in which citizen science is argued to impact the SDGs is through its impacts on the economy. Indirectly, citizen science enables various beneficial innovations and scientific advances, which can make existing modes of economic activity more effective. This would indicate that citizen science potentially positively impacts the economy-related SDGs.

The goals detailed in this section are the following:

- SDG 8 (decent work and economic growth)
- SDG 10 (reduced inequalities)
- SDG 12 (responsible consumption and production)

However, the positive sustainability potential of citizen science needs to be explicitly related to the actual content and nuances of the goals about, for example, economic growth and responsible consumption and production.

SDG 8: Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.

SDG 10: Reduce inequality within and among countries.

As already mentioned, citizen science’s impact on the world of business is not often discussed. Citizen science is not, generally, a catalyst for economic growth and the creation of economic value, and this entails that citizen-science impacts on the economic SDGs are, generally, not significant.

A key point to consider when dealing with economic growth is the common assumption that economic growth in and of itself is a good thing. Economic growth might, after all, allow to solve problems related to the scarcity of resources, and thus reduce poverty, fight starvation, and allocate more resources to protect the environment. Trickle-down economics, and the notion that a rising tide will lift all boats, have been a staple of many varieties of growth schools, but modern history has not always been kind to these theories. Economic growth has also led to increased inequality and exponential use of resources. So much so that new schools are now calling for economic degrowth (Latouche, 2009). As clearly stated in SDG 8, the kind of growth imagined is *sustained, inclusive, and sustainable*. This necessitates going much deeper into the *nature* of economic growth, while growth for growth’s sake is of little interest.

Few question the fact that inequality is a challenge for modern societies, as also indicated by SDG 10. Chancel (2019) provides an account of current inequalities and suggests that both between-country and in-country inequality are high and increasing. While inequality has traditionally often been discussed as the problematic difference between rich and developing countries, in-country inequality is increasingly essential, and, together with nationality, class is seen to be a critical factor in describing current inequalities.

MICS argues that identifying whether citizen science enables SDG 8 requires looking at the interplay between SDG 8 and SDG 10 in particular (reduced inequalities), but also the social and environmental goals, as positive impacts on these will have indirect impacts on SDG 8 and will allow seeing what kind of growth citizen science promotes. MICS also acknowledges the limitations associated with using the SDG framework (a framework premised on the notion of growth and not of degrowth) to assess the economic impact of citizen science.

Understanding the nature of growth engendered by citizen science and the causes that determine how citizen science influences development the way it does is a crucial area for future research.

Concerning direct impacts on SDG 8, citizen science has been shown to promote growth. Still, it is highly uncertain whether this growth can be sustained, inclusive, and sustainable. The MICS platform will help to characterise these cases better.

The indirect impacts of citizen-science—enabled economic growth are numerous and essential, and these will mainly be mentioned in the context of other SDGs. It suffices to state here that these impacts will be both negative and positive, as economic growth might, for example, promote health and education, but it could also increase inequality, increase consumption, and, in turn, lead to adverse environmental impacts. The key in MICS’s analysis of citizen science and economic growth was to adopt a broad enough perspective to ensure that the nature and the distribution of growth are factored in.

SDG 12: Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns.

Sustainability is a simple concept at its core, as it states that what is used cannot exceed what is replenished. Earth Overshoot Day [<https://www.overshootday.org/>] marks the date each year in which more resources have been used than what is generated in a year, in which the Earth’s biocapacity is exceeded by humankind’s ecological footprint, and is primarily used to show that this occurs quite early each year and, what is worse, it happens earlier each year. In 2022 it was 28 July, down from 4 August in 2012, 23 September in 2000, and 11 October in 1990. To improve this situation, both consumption and production patterns have to be changed, and citizen science can play a role in this change.

For example, in designing and regulating policies and incentives related to plastic-waste generation and pollution, citizen science can be used to prioritise resource challenges and collect data.

The following table presents the input features (in the form of questions and answers) used in MICS to measure how citizen science enables (or inhibits) the achievement of sustainable economic development.

4.1.1 Table explanation

In the table, the first column contains the question number, visible on the platform interface; this number is relative to the domain in question; so, 1 means “question 1” of the Economy domain. The first column, in brackets, also contains the internal code of the question, which is only interesting for the system administrators. The second column is self-explanatory. The third column refers to the text of the Help and Information pop-ups that can be associated with a question. The fourth column contains the source of the question and the original, corresponding wording that the input feature had in that source. This explanation of the content of the following table is also valid for the tables of all the other domains.

Table 4.a Economy-domain input features

#	Question text and answer options	Help and Information	Source of question and original wording
1 (301)	<p>How has the project been funded?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal funding of the coordinating organisation(s) • Micro funding • Crowdfunding • Private foundations or non-governmental organisations • Corporate sponsors / funders • Government funding or appropriation • Other national sponsors/funders • European Union (for example, via Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe) • Other international sponsors/funders • The project does not require funding • None of the above • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Not sure about the difference between micro funding and crowdfunding? There is a general connection between all forms of alternative funding: they all provide access to capital for a segment of the population that cannot access it through traditional means. However, there are significant differences between micro funding and crowdfunding.</p> <p>Micro funding includes microfinance and social (peer-to-peer) lending, and is not commonly used in citizen science. Microfinance provides loans and other basic financial services to the poor. Social lending gives ordinary people the ability to lend around the world.</p> <p>Crowdfunding is the practice of funding a project or venture by raising money from a large number of people, typically via the Internet.</p>	<p>Bonney et al. 2009: # of grants received</p> <p>Wiggins et al. 2018: Existence (or total monetary value) of competitive funding awards from private or public funders</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: revenue stream</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Funding source: Public, Philanthropic, Combination</p>
2 (302)	<p>Did the project generate related new projects?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • It's in progress (for example, a project proposal has been written) • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> For example, a related new project might include the project's methods being applied in other locations or a new iteration of the project's methods or technology.</p> <p>"Not yet, but it might one day?" Don't worry; you can always come back and update your answers on the MICS platform when it does.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Did the project generate new research questions, new projects or proposals?</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: How many CO-related research projects is your organization currently involved in?</p>
3 (303)	<p>In total, how much external funding has been received for these new projects? (in €, £ GBP, or \$ USD)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 - 3000 • 3001 - 30 000 • 30 001 - 300 000 • 300 001 - 3 000 000 • More than 3 000 000 • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> External funding is money that comes from outside the organisation(s) managing the project.</p> <p>In this question, we use €, £ GBP, or \$ USD interchangeably because the answers are given as orders of magnitude which make the difference in the exchange rate between the three currencies largely irrelevant. Here's a currency converter in case it's helpful: https://www1.oanda.com/currency/converter/</p>	<p>Wehn et al. 2017: In total, what is your organization's budget (income & own investment) in these CO-related research projects?</p>
4 (304)	<p>Does the project create any competitive advantage for the organisations involved with the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Here "competitive advantage" refers to factors that allow an organisation to produce outputs or services better or more cheaply than its rivals. For example, incorporating citizen science might provide a competitive advantage for the ecotourism providers in the tourism market; healthcare data might provide a competitive advantage for pharmaceutical companies.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project include any competitive advantage?</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: What value proposition(s) related to COs and enabling technologies does your organization have? How many different revenue streams does your organization have for CO-related value propositions?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and Information	Source of question and original wording
5 (305)	<p>Does the project generate new jobs among the organisations running the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know • No, the nature of the project would not allow for the generation of new jobs (e.g. it is entirely community-run). 	<p><i>Help:</i> Some projects are run by paid staff at organisations. The growth of these projects can therefore create new jobs. However, some citizen science projects are run entirely by volunteers without any jobs related to the project. These types of project are sometimes referred to as collegial projects (as explained in this model of participation by Shirk et al.).</p>	<p>Wehn et al. 2017: How many jobs are directly related to the CO topic and enabling technologies? What is the nature of these jobs? (junior, middle, senior positions) [nominal]</p>
6 (306)	<p>Does the project involve commercial activities related to industry or academia?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes (for example, commercialisation of tools or technology developed within the project) • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Information:</i> While a level of scepticism exists towards business involvement in citizen science, some observe that the sector has made positive and impactful contributions towards advancing the tools and application of citizen science as well as in providing participants through campaigns that engage employees.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Commercial activities. If a direct commercial benefit is the main aim of an activity, and results from the use of data, for example via paid data services for the sole personal benefit of the person who shares the data and further commercial use beyond services for the data provider, it is generally not considered as citizen science. This also applies if motives for activities are perceived solely to support a marketing or business strategy, rather than supporting a unique research goal and a justified involvement of citizens. However, commercial activities that are in line with the <i>ten principles</i> and are transparent could still be considered as citizen science.</p>
7 (307)	<p>Does the project explicitly promote the formation and growth of micro-, small- or medium-sized enterprises / businesses?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Ways in which a project could promote the formation and growth of SMEs include new start-ups forming based on technology developed by the project or growth of a business due to the project creating increased awareness in the business's target market.</p>	<p>SDG 8.3 Promote development-oriented policies that support productive activities, decent job creation, entrepreneurship, creativity and innovation, and encourage the formalization and growth of micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises, including through access to financial services</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project generate any economic impact, e.g. cost reduction, new job creation, new business model, etc.?</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: See above.</p>
8 (308)	<p>Does the project generate new jobs in organisations external to those running the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Wehn et al. 2017: See above.</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project generate any economic impact, e.g. cost reduction, new job creation, new business model, etc.?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and Information	Source of question and original wording
9 (309)	<p>Does the project increase demand for the sustainable services of any organisation, internal or external to the project (for example, by promoting sustainable tourism or by promoting clean energy)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Information:</i> The platform doesn't assign a positive economic impact to unsustainable services given the externalities associated with them.</p>	<p>SDG 8.9 By 2030, devise and implement policies to promote sustainable tourism that creates jobs and promotes local culture and products</p>
10 (310)	<p>Does the project have a positive impact on the livelihoods of participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Pocock et al. 2019: Improved wellbeing and livelihoods through connection to (and consequent ownership of) nature and sense of belonging</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Enhancing natural and socio-cultural capital to create a sustainable environment. Livelihood assets enhanced.</p> <p>SDG 8.5 By 2030, achieve full and productive employment and decent work for all women and men, including for young people and persons with disabilities, and equal pay for work of equal value</p> <p>Chase and Levine 2016: Reliance on a resource for economic benefit or livelihood motivates some citizen science programs and may foster a more diverse and dedicated group of collaborating partners. Industries or communities may be highly motivated to participate in monitoring a resource upon which they are heavily dependent (e.g., cooperative fisheries research partnerships [Hartley & Robertson 2006]).</p> <p>Those who rely heavily on a resource for livelihood purposes are also more likely to self-organize and to have greater knowledge about the resource, which relates to awareness and knowledge characteristics.</p>
11 (311)	<p>Does the project have any economic potential to be exploited in the future (for example, new intellectual property with economic value, or new sensors with a clear market)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Exploitation is defined as the use of results for commercial purposes or in public policymaking.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project have any economic potential to be exploited in the future?</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: How many IPRs related to COs and enabling technologies (patents, trademarks, copyright, other know-how rights) does your organization hold? What value proposition(s) related to COs and enabling technologies does your organization have?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and Information	Source of question and original wording
12 (312)	Does the project have an explicit exploitation plan? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<i>Help:</i> Exploitation is defined as the use of results for commercial purposes or in public policymaking. Exploitation plans often include generating new business models.	Kieslinger et al. 2017 : Does the project have a sustainability plan?
13 (313)	Does the project have any concrete cooperation in place for the exploitation of results? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<i>Help:</i> Exploitation is defined as the use of results for commercial purposes or in public policymaking.	Kieslinger et al. 2017 : Does the project have any cooperation for exploitation, e.g. with social entrepreneurs?
14 (314)	Does the project have an intellectual property rights (IPR) strategy? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<i>Help:</i> Intellectual property involves the creations of the human mind including patents, copyrights and industrial design. An Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) strategy helps organisations and projects to manage these assets. Here is a resource which might help the project to develop an IPR strategy.	Wehn et al. 2017 : How many IPRs related to COs and enabling technologies (patents, trademarks, copyright, other know-how rights) does your organization hold?
15 (315)	Does the project have explicit plans to sustain its activities after the current funding received has ended? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		Woods et al. 2020 : How likely are you going to carry on recording measurements and associated data after the project ends? How likely are you going to stay in contact with your citizen science community?
16 (316)	Does the project explicitly improve economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading or innovation? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes; the project doubled the GDP of a country • Yes; but it wasn't as successful as that! • No • I don't know 		SDG 8.2 Achieve higher levels of economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading and innovation, including through a focus on high-value added and labour-intensive sectors Woods et al. 2020 : To what extent has participating in this project fostered innovative and entrepreneurial approaches? Have you identified any new areas where the data can be used innovatively?

#	Question text and answer options	Help and Information	Source of question and original wording
17 (317)	<p>Is the citizen science used in the project more cost-efficient than using experts and traditional scientific methods?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It has not been estimated • It has been estimated and there is no clear winner from the economic point of view. • Citizen science clearly produces savings in comparison with using experts or traditional scientific methods. • We know that it can be awkward to admit that citizen science is more expensive or less efficient than traditional methods, but here is the option to do so • I don't know 		<p>Palmer et al. 2017: Economic cost Our first point of comparison is cost. Mosquito Alert operated during 2014–2015 with a total budget of 300,000 Euros, covering 487,775 km² in Spain for an average cost of about 1.23 Euros per km² per month. In contrast, we estimate that the much more labour-intensive ovitraps, which must be set and checked by experts in the field and lab, cost about 9.36 Euros per km² per month (see Methods for detailed calculation)—nearly eight times the cost of Mosquito Alert.</p> <p>Pocock et al. 2019: Increased ability to leverage funds and enhance sustainability through cost-effectiveness</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: For your organization, what is the value added of the citizen observatory focused on [CO topic] for your capital expenditure? (Cost avoidance due to CO - CAPEX) For your organization, what is the value added of the citizen observatory focused on [CO topic] for your operating expenditure? (Cost avoidance due to CO (OPEX))</p>
18 (318)	<p>By engaging citizen scientists, is the project able to cover a larger sample size (i.e., to collect or analyse a larger amount of data) than a project with equivalent resources involving only professional scientists?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Not relevant for the project • Too difficult to say • I don't know 		<p>Palmer et al. 2017: With its relatively low cost centred on non-recurring investments, citizen science is inherently more scalable than traditional tools. This makes it possible for citizen science to greatly expand surveillance areas even in the face of shrinking budgets.</p> <p>Pocock et al. 2019: Enhanced data collection, including coverage, resolution (spatial, temporal and taxonomic), accuracy and inter-disciplinarity</p>
19 (319)	<p>Does the project explicitly contribute to the reduction of government expenditure?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: “Not yet, but it might one day?” Don't worry; you can always come back and update your answers on the MICS platform when it does.</p>	<p>MacKenchie et al. 2011: Recent UK Government policy speeches have described the use of Big Society as a way to compensate for reduced funding. In particular, the Secretary of State for the UK's Department for the Environment and Rural Affairs (Defra) when launching the consultation on the Natural Environment White Paper, described the 'new opportunity to hand over control to local people'.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and Information	Source of question and original wording
20 (320)	<p>Does the project explicitly contribute to the reduction of costs for other external organisations?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> An example of contributing to the reduction of costs for an external organisation would be a project increasing the availability of data required by another organisation.</p>	<p>Wehn et al. 2017: Overall, what are the current costs of external inputs (e.g. data, public opinions, expert knowledge) that your organisation needs in order to perform its function in relation to [CO topic]? How easily available are these external inputs (e.g. data, public opinions, expert knowledge)? (example of efforts)</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project generate any economic impact, e.g. cost reduction, new job creation, new business model, etc.?</p>
21 (321)	<p>What are the estimated, typical, annual project staff costs (in £, € or \$)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 3000 • 3000-30,000 • 30,000-300,000 • More than 300,000 • I don't know 		<p>Ferri et al. 2020: to estimate the costs as data-related costs, staff costs and other costs and the benefits in terms of scientific benefits, public engagement benefits and the benefits of the strengthened capacity of participants.</p>
22 (322)	<p>What are the estimated, typical, annual costs of IT systems for data collection and management (in £, € or \$) (for example for the use of cloud-computing services or software licenses)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 300 • 300-3000 • 3000-30,000 • More than 30,000 • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> This would not usually include initial investments in IT to develop an app or a platform.</p>	<p>Ferri et al. 2020: See above.</p>
23 (323)	<p>What are the estimated, typical, annual equipment costs (in £, € or \$)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 300 • 300-3000 • 3000-30,000 • More than 30,000 • I don't know 		<p>Ferri et al. 2020: See above.</p>
24 (324)	<p>Does the project require recurring investments in technology (for example, software licences or app/platform maintenance) that affect its long-term sustainability?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Palmer et al. 2017: Overall, the results suggest the potential for citizen science to outperform traditional methods in many respects. With its relatively low cost centred on non-recurring investments, citizen science is inherently more scalable than traditional tools.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and Information	Source of question and original wording
25 (325)	<p>What is the estimated, approximate cost per observation (in £, € or \$) (observations as defined by the project)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observations are not a significant element of the project and quantifying their cost is not important. • Less than 2 (Just for comparison, this is the income per day of one seventh of the world population.) • 2-8 (Just for comparison, this is the income per day of three sevenths of the world population.) • 9-32 (Just for curiosity, this is the income per day of two sevenths of the world population.) • More than 32 (Just for curiosity, this is the income per day of one seventh of the world population.) • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> It can be hard to define the number of observations for projects which involve continuous, real-time measurement (for example, collected by a sonde). To make the calculations easier consider the number of observations to be the number of minutes of active measurement. A single sonde collecting data for a full calendar year would therefore be considered to have collected about 500,000 observations (the number of minutes in a year).</p>	<p>Alfonso et al. 2022: An important variable, albeit almost never explicitly reported in projects involving Citizen Science, to evaluate the value of Citizen Science for data generation is related to the costs invested to produce these observations. As mentioned before, the statement that Citizen Science is a cost-effective approach to data collection frequently found in literature, needs to be based on evidence.</p>
26 (326)	<p>How much time is invested by the project in training citizens in a typical recent year?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project does not train participants • Not much (hours) • Some (days) • A lot (there are one or more people, or a work package, explicitly dedicated to training citizens) • Too difficult to quantify • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Training might involve identifying different species or planets, using equipment or sensors, or analysing data, and can include the production of training materials.</p> <p>This is not the time invested by the participant to be trained. It is the total time invested by the project in training all participants.</p>	<p>Thornhill et al. 2017: to explore the relationship between the costs and benefits of a citizen science program, we compared the time invested in training and engagement by individual researchers with the equivalent time saved in sampling and measurement.</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Costs of (increased organisational) capacity: As these engagement activities are intended to be sustainable after the end of the project, information about the actual costs of developing and maintaining these is an important consideration. One way to explore this is by looking at budget allocation; another is by enquiring how much participants are willing to pay for such events - the difference between these can shed light on the needed cost to be covered by other means. This is useful information for funders and decision-makers.</p>
27 (327)	<p>On average, how many hours does a participant dedicate to the project in a typical recent year?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 3 • 3-30 • More than 30 • The project has no participants • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> We acknowledge that this can vary hugely from participant to participant; go with an average participant.</p>	<p>Chandler et al. 2017: # of people and # of person-hours dedicated to collecting scientific data</p> <p>Cox et al. 2015: Median time interval (in weeks) between a registered user's first and last recorded classification</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Time (hours/month) required for participation</p> <p>Butterfoss 2006: [measures of community participation] amount of time spent in and outside of coalition activities,</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and Information	Source of question and original wording
28 (328)	<p>On average, how long do participants have to travel to take part in the citizen science activities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants do not have to travel • Less than 10 minutes • 10 - 30 minutes • 30 minutes - 1 hour • More than 1 hour • I don't know 		<p>Wehn et al. 2017: Geographic scope of the issue in focus and location of stakeholders (inside/outside the geographic boundaries)</p>
29 (329)	<p>Do participants have to pay to take part in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, at least in some cases • No • I don't know 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: Payment to take part in a project. For example, requesting financial contributions from citizens to finance data-measurement kits can be consistent with citizen science. But consideration should be made regarding how this may affect social inclusion (e.g. excluding poorer participants) and bias participation.</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Investment required for participation; capital (€) and long term (€/month)</p>
30 (330)	<p>What is this payment used for?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General support to an organisation • Equipment or services given to the participants • Training given to the participants • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: See above.</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Investment required for participation; capital (€) and long term (€/month)</p>
31 (331)	<p>Can participants make a voluntary financial contribution to the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: An example of a voluntary financial contribution could be a participant becoming a Patreon supporter.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Financial support for scientific research. Pure financial support to a project, such as crowdfunding, subscription fees and donations, is not considered citizen science, as no participation in any phase of the scientific research takes place. Careful consideration of the consistency with citizen science should be made if the financial contribution is a prerequisite to a form of participation in the scientific research phase of the project.</p>

4.2 Impact on society

While the term sustainability tends to lead the mind towards forests and gas emissions, *people* are heavily emphasised in the SDGs. Nine goals are categorised as social goals, and they relate to a broad set of issues. The goals detailed in this section are the following:

- SDG 1 (no poverty)
- SDG 2 (zero hunger)
- SDG 3 (good health and well-being)
- SDG 4 (quality education)
- SDG 5 (gender equality)
- SDG 6 (clean water and sanitation)
- SDG 7 (affordable and clean energy)
- SDG 11 (sustainable cities and communities)
- SDG 16 (peace, justice, and strong institutions)

SDG 1: End poverty in all its forms everywhere.

MICS considers the indirect impact of promoting inclusive growth (SDG 8) as citizen science's main potential positive impact on eliminating poverty. Nevertheless, it is worth remembering that economic growth in itself does not necessarily contribute to reduced inequality and a reduction of poverty, as discussed in the section about the economy.

SDG 2: End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture.

Examples of citizen science used to disseminate ecosystem-enhancing and environmental-action—driven expertise to all rural actors, or to engage farmers in monitoring the health of the soils demonstrate how citizen science can make agriculture both more resource-effective and more effective in general. The potential inhibitor related to citizen science and the food system is the risk that such solutions will mainly be used by those who already have access to food and resources. Such a development could negatively influence, for example, SDG 10 (increased inequalities).

SDG 3: Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages.

Citizen science is highly implicated in micro-level health and citizens' lives. A wide range of apps and technologies are today used to track an individual's health, activity, and nutrition, for example. One example is citizen-science projects using the health-tracking functionality built into smartphones, or the increasingly ubiquitous fitness and health trackers of various kinds, which can track most aspects of citizens' lives.

SDG 4: Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.

Citizen science can provide student and school activities to promote education on sustainability. It can be used to raise awareness about societal challenges in students and can potentially improve the quality of education, but as the description of SDG 4 clearly shows, quality is not all, as this education has to be inclusive and equitable. While citizen science might improve quality, it might also increase the risk that education for those best off will be enhanced, while others will not benefit from this. If so, increased inequality is a potential result.

SDG 5: Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.

Inclusivity and equality are central to the SDGs, but gender equality is one topic perceived as so important that it has gotten a goal of its own. While one might want to argue that equality related to ethnicity, functional diversity, and LGBTQ+ status is equally essential, SDG 5 limits its focus to women and girls. Nevertheless, MICS uses the Society domain as an opening for a broader discussion of how citizen science enables or inhibits discrimination of various types. One example is question 152: *Has the project been designed to give access, where possible, to all participants, including those with “functional diversity”?*

SDG 6: Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all.

Water systems can be more effectively monitored through the addition of citizen science, and many examples exist in this sense [mics.tools/citizen-science-and-water-quality]. This goal is also clearly related to SDG 14, which entails the conservation and sustainable use of oceans, seas, and marine resources. The relationship might, however, be both positive and negative. For example, increasing people’s access to water and sanitation might entail solutions that negatively impact non-human access to and use of various types of water.

SDG 7: Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all.

SDG 9 (see section 4.5), both in terms of science and technology, will be vitally important for reaching SDG 7, and the key impacts of citizen science are assumed to be the indirect impacts of contributing to SDG 9. Another potential benefit of citizen science concerning energy is that it might promote the environmental benefits associated with clean energy sources. However, SDG 7 mainly mentions *sustainable* energy, without thoroughly defining what sort of energy qualifies as sustainable. Depending on the energy sources, there will be different impacts on SDG 15 (life on land). SDG 14 (life in water) is also related to energy sources, as marine windmills proliferate.

SDG 11: Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable.

One fundamental way citizen science promises to impact human settlements is in the context of the development of *smart cities*: technology-intensive cities in which sensor data are analysed and used to improve and optimise existing services, as well as prepare the grounds for new ones. In terms of resilience, citizen science shows positive potential. For example, generating and analysing environmental data enables a more effective identification and forecasting of threats to settlements. This relates both to the threats and the weaknesses that arise in, for example, a settlement’s infrastructure, and to the potential external threats posed by polluted environments. Insights generated by citizen science might be used to respond more effectively in a crisis, but, even more importantly, citizen science might also be used for planning and adapting to potential threats before they occur.

SDG 16: Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels.

Concerning the notions of justice and inclusive governance, citizen science combined sometimes with AI can enable more effective nudging of individuals. Nudges are policies and incentives to encourage behaviour change via interventions leading people, for example, to choose products with less virgin plastic. But, in general, such nudging can be argued to constitute a form of liberty reducing manipulation, and this realisation has made regulators in the European Union propose the limitation of manipulative use of AI in general. The following table presents the input features used in MICS to measure how citizen science enables (or inhibits) the achievement of sustainable social development.

Table 4.b Society-domain input features

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
1 (101)	<p>In which phases of the project do participants play a role?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Background research • Identifying a research question • Grant proposal writing • Project initiation • Definition of project activities • Design and development of technology and equipment for the project • Collecting data • Analysing data • Monitoring in ways other than collecting data • Passive participation (for example, contributing computer resources or social media information which is harvested by the project) • Recruiting or engaging other participants • Training other participants • Sharing of outputs (including publications and arranging project events) • Assessment of project impacts • Acting on the results of the project • Closure or handover of the project • None of the above • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Projects use many words to describe the people who take part in their activities: citizen scientists, volunteers, stakeholders, amateurs, community members, human sensors.</p> <p>In MICS we just use the word participants.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: In which project phases are citizens involved? [Are citizen scientists recognized in publications and if so,] can they participate in the dissemination of results?</p> <p>ECSCA Characteristics: The roles of the participants can include, for example: identifying a research question, collecting or analysing data to support or refute a hypothesis; monitoring environmental or health conditions for management or policy outcomes; and creating generic data within a domain to support a wide range of research questions (e.g. digitising art collections, observations or mapping).</p> <p>Degree of engagement. Active engagement that requires citizens' cognitive attention during participation in the research process is favoured over limited interaction. It is also preferable to engage citizens in several phases of the research process. Minimal participation, for example volunteers sharing computing resources or social media habits without actively engaging in the research itself, or downloading an app that automatically collects data for scientific purposes, could still be considered as citizen science under certain conditions. Examples include when a project actively aligns with the <i>ten principles</i>, or supports the production of scientific results that would not have been possible without the informed decision of volunteers to contribute.</p> <p>Haywood and Besley 2014: How early are citizen participants consulted in the process and what stage/s of the research process are citizen participants included in? What roles do citizen participants have in the process compared to project leaders? (e.g. is there a division of labour?, are citizens included in the analysis and interpretation of results?)</p> <p>Butterfoss 2006: [measures of community participation] role in the coalition or its activities</p> <p>Khodyakov et al. (2013): Question: Please think about the extent to which the community partners participated in the research component of this partnered project and check all the research activities that they have been involved with either as "consultants" or "active participants." Grant proposal writing, Background research, choosing research methods, developing sampling procedures, recruiting study participants, Implementing the intervention, designing interview and/or survey questions, collecting primary data, Analyzing collected data, interpreting study findings, writing reports and journal articles, Giving presentations at meetings and conferences.</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Mechanisms for stakeholder interactions in decision-making processes (e.g. data provision, expressing preferences, deliberation and negotiation)</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
2 (102)	<p>Are participants offered multiple project activities which they can take part in?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No; participants only have one activity they can take part in • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Are the options for participation and the degree of involvement diversified? How much involvement and responsibility is offered to the participants?</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Perception of the users about the flexibility of the participation methods</p>
3 (103)	<p>Are participants offered different levels of involvement in each project activity depending on their interest, availability and knowledge?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Are the options for participation and the degree of involvement diversified?</p>
4 (104)	<p>How much responsibility is offered to the participants? (with options depending on interests, availability and knowledge).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not much, no single participant is relied on to carry out a specific task. • A lot, the project depends on specific individuals to carry out certain tasks. • Something in the middle • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: A lot of responsibility might involve collecting repeated observations, maintaining equipment or running workshops, whilst not much responsibility might be analysing data as part of a group or collecting data as part of a BioBlitz.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: How much involvement and responsibility is offered to the participants?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
5 (105)	<p>What type of citizen science is the project according to the following categories?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contractual projects, where communities ask professional researchers to conduct a specific scientific investigation and report on the results Contributory projects, which are generally designed by scientists and for which members of the public primarily contribute data Collaborative projects, which are generally designed by scientists and for which members of the public contribute data but also help to refine project design, analyse data, or disseminate findings Co-created projects, which are designed by scientists and members of the public working together and for which at least some of the public participants are actively involved in most aspects of the research process Collegial projects, where non-credentialed individuals conduct research independently with varying degrees of expected recognition by institutionalised science or professionals The project doesn't fit any of these categories. I don't know 	<p><i>Information:</i> These categories come from a paper by Jennifer Shirk et al., "Public Participation in Scientific Research: a Framework for Deliberate Design" which has become a reference in citizen science. And if your project doesn't fit into any of these categories, Jennifer won't be happy...</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Roles and responsibilities. In citizen science, there are contexts in which it is appropriate for citizens, scientists, and other project stakeholders to be considered as equal partners in the research process, and cases where the appropriate contribution is limited to data collection or providing resources. Contributors need to be aware of the act of participation, with the deliberate intention of being involved in the project. Transparency regarding the different roles and expectations in the process is recommended, and participants should be made aware that they are contributing to research. This is especially important if participants are only taking over small or micro-tasks that require little engagement, but the overall contribution to a clearly defined scientific process or research is important.</p> <p>Individual project, community-led project and researcher-led project. Citizen science projects can be led by researchers or scientists, or can be led collaboratively by a community to address a particular issue. Projects can also be run by an individual, who will carry out the whole project alone. All are potentially consistent with citizen science, and the decision on each project can be made by examining its context and practices.</p> <p>Shirk et al. 2012: We divide PPSR projects into five models based on degree of participation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contractual projects, where communities ask professional researchers to conduct a specific scientific investigation and report on the results; Contributory projects, which are generally designed by scientists and for which members of the public primarily contribute data; Collaborative projects, which are generally designed by scientists and for which members of the public contribute data but also help to refine project design, analyse data, and/or disseminate findings; Co-Created projects, which are designed by scientists and members of the public working together and for which at least some of the public participants are actively involved in most or all aspects of the research process; and Collegial contributions, where non-credentialed individuals conduct research independently with varying degrees of expected recognition by institutionalized science and/or professionals.
6 (106)	<p>Are participants equal partners in the knowledge generation with the project organizers?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No; participants lead the knowledge generation. (This is very unlikely. Please, double check before selecting this answer) No; the project organisers lead the knowledge generation I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Knowledge generation can be understood as the conclusions drawn from the research.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Are citizens and scientists equal partners in the knowledge generation process?</p> <p>Butterfoss 2006: [measures of community participation] balance of power and leadership.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
7 (107)	<p>Does the project explicitly foster co-ownership of the project among participants and other stakeholders?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Individual development: Behaviour and ownership "Does the project foster ownership amongst participants?"</p> <p>Pocock et al. 2019: Enhanced capacity and empowerment of all stakeholders in conservation, leading to action. Greater ownership through involvement at every stage, including motivations for monitoring and action, increased trust, tolerance and attitudes to nature</p>
8 (108)	<p>Are the participants satisfied with the process of participation in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Butterfoss 2006: [measures of community participation] satisfaction with the work or process of participation,</p> <p>Gresle et al. 2019: Participatory Dynamics - Satisfaction with the participatory dynamics</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Public expectations of engagement in decision-making processes; Perceived 'level' of participation/contribution; Attitude toward facilitator & organisation.</p>
9 (109)	<p>Do the goals of the project align to the demands of the participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Guldberg et al. 2019: to the extent that changes in practice make a difference to what really matters, social learning produces realised value</p> <p>Gresle et al. 2019: community alignment (alignment of project goals to the community demands and efficacy of engagement techniques) and responsiveness to community alignment.</p>
10 (110)	<p>Are participants satisfied with the results of the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Woods et al. 2020: To what extent is the value created worth the time and effort you put into this project?</p> <p>Butterfoss 2006: [measures of community participation] satisfaction with the work or process of participation,</p>
11 (111)	<p>Is participation in the project voluntary or non-voluntary?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voluntary • Non-voluntary (for example, pupils who have to participate as part of school activities) • Both • I don't know 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: Professionalism vs volunteerism. When citizen science is understood as a collaboration between professional and volunteer scientists, the question arises: what is 'professional' and what is 'voluntary'? The interpretation of these terms varies widely and depends on context, culture and the field of enquiry. It includes aspects like professional skill sets, remuneration and timescales of involvement. For example, volunteers with a scientific background or professional scientific role in other capacities can still be volunteers when they apply their skills in their free time. They can engage in scientific activities full time and still be understood as volunteers under certain conditions (e.g. when the effort is beyond their roles).</p>
12 (112)	<p>Are participants aware they are contributing to a citizen science project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: Contributors need to be aware of the act of participation, with the deliberate intention of being involved in the project. Transparency regarding the different roles and expectations in the process is recommended, and participants</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No I don't know 		<p>should be made aware that they are contributing to research. This is especially important if participants are only taking over small or micro-tasks that require little engagement, but the overall contribution to a clearly defined scientific process or research is important.</p>
13 (113)	<p>Are participants the focus of the research?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> They are the focus of the citizen-science research (This might be the case, for example, in health and medical research). They are the focus of the broader project research (This might be the case, for example, if the project lead is investigating motivation in citizen science projects) They are not the focus of the research. I don't know 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: Intention and framing. In many fields, but particularly the medical and health sciences and the social sciences, there is a subtle difference between citizen science activities and traditional practices that view participants as subjects of research, or as participants in a survey or workshop. Therefore, the decision to call an activity citizen science should include an articulation of which aspects justify this, for example, by referencing the <i>ten principles</i>.</p> <p>Subject or participant? In some disciplines, such as the medical and the social sciences, the shift from being a research subject to becoming an active researcher should be made clear. The nature of such studies means it is common that citizens themselves, their behaviours, challenges and health issues are under examination. But citizens can also take an active role in, and even initiate, the above activities. It is possible that the people who take part in such projects can be subjects and participants at the same time, depending on the intentions and framing of the research.</p> <p>The use of digital data-collection tools in the medical and the social sciences can be seen as a social survey or as participatory data collection, and therefore part of citizen science. The intention and framing of the project, as well as adherence to the <i>ten principles</i>, can help in deciding if such use is a citizen science activity.</p>
14 (114)	<p>Do changes in participants' values, perspectives, opinions and attitudes occur as a consequence of actions carried out in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes, and it has been measured Yes, but it has not been measured No I don't know 		<p>Haywood and Besley 2014: Are participants encouraged to reflect on and discuss current VPOA [Values, Perspectives, Opinions and Attitudes] relating to general science concepts and the research project? Do changes in these VPOA occur?</p> <p>Zwickle and Jones 2018: Sustainability attitudes scale</p> <p>Smajgl et al. 2015: The learning-focused ChaRL framework measured and facilitated changes in existing beliefs, by tracing the fate of new knowledge introduced by a specific research process and capturing attendant changes in value and belief orientations.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
15 (115)	<p>Does the project contribute to personal change in behaviour?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> For example, behaviour change could include "switching from plastic bags to reusable shopping bags" or "changing an omnivorous diet to a vegan one and losing all friends in the process".</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project contribute to personal change in behaviour?</p> <p>Haywood and Besley 2014: Do participants or project leaders exhibit changes in behaviour or lifestyle choices?</p> <p>Braun and Dierkes 2019: Environmental knowledge incorporates at least three different subtypes: system, action-related and effectiveness knowledge. To enable a person to act in an environmentally friendly manner, they must primarily understand the basic structural and functional characteristics of an ecosystem (system knowledge). Furthermore, knowledge about solutions for environmental issues (action-related knowledge) and the benefit of sustainable actions (effectiveness knowledge) are deemed crucial for an individual to choose a set of behaviours.</p> <p>Phillips et al. 2018: Our new framework is thus based on both empirical data and contributions from the literature and includes the following learning outcomes: Interest in Science and the Environment; Self-efficacy for Science and the Environment; Motivation for Science and the Environment; Knowledge of the Nature of Science; Skills of Science Inquiry; and Behaviour and Stewardship.</p> <p>Kaiser 2020: [General Ecological Behaviour Scale]</p>
16 (116)	<p>Do participants self-organize to carry out additional activities beyond the original scope of the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Chase and Levine 2016: Self-organization of a community or group around resource</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Number and type of participant-initiated/led activities: While these might vary in type and extent, they should be acknowledged and celebrated. Within their contexts, partner organisations should follow the cases of participant initiated/led activities to encourage them by e.g. understanding their sources and needs (this can lead to further capacity development on the part of the participant, the facilitator, and the organisation). This input feature also aims to capture over time how these initiatives develop (are they temporary, goal-oriented, intended to be longer-term, etc.).</p>
17 (117)	<p>Are participants involved in similar activities outside of the project as a consequence of being involved in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Are participants motivated to continue the project or get involved in similar activities?</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: People who volunteered time to an organisation in the past month.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
18 (118)	<p>What is the balance between engagement and research in the project? (We know that many of you would be tempted to say they are equal in the project but we want to force you to choose one!)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mostly engagement • More engagement, but balanced • More research, but balanced • Mostly research • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Research investigates a topic within sciences, social sciences, humanities or the arts to reach new conclusions. This may be done by following protocols to investigate a hypothesis, collecting and analysing data or creating generic data to answer questions.</p> <p>Engagement requires participants' attention during one or more stages of the project. This may be in the form of using apps or social media to interact with the project, learning and applying a scientific method or attending a workshop</p> <p><i>Information:</i> The balance between engagement and research is highlighted as an important issue in ECSA's characteristics of citizen science. For example, if a project only focuses on engagement, can it really be considered citizen science?"</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Science engagement and science education. Citizen science projects can have educational outcomes for participants involved in various phases of the research process. Intended learning outcomes for participants are a favourable aspect in citizen science. However, for a project to be classified as citizen science, educational goals or science engagement/outreach should not be the only focus, to ensure they are aligned with the research goals. Hence, achieving higher awareness of and engagement with scientific processes can be one aim (intentional or unintentional) of citizen science projects – but should not be the main aim.</p>
19 (119)	<p>What engagement approaches does the project use?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gamification • Real-time validation on observation/data submission • Notification of updates to contributed observations • Tips of the day • Personalised recommendations • Feedback on data quality • Active and responsive social-media presence ("responsive" in the sense that questions from participants are responded to) • Storytelling or exchanging of experiences • Invitation to or suggestion of events • Workshops • Measurement campaigns • Active and responsive pilot / case study presence ("responsive" in the sense that questions from participants are responded to) • A forum, or other platform on a website • Awareness raising (ad-hoc demonstrations, meetings and appearances from partners) • Photo contests • Social events not included in previous options • Creation of champions, ambassadors or leaders • Organic conversation 	<p><i>Help:</i> Here are some definitions in case you're not familiar with the terms we've used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gamification is the process of encouraging engagement within the project by turning the process into a game (using point scoring, challenges and competition). - A workshop is a group of people discussing a topic or engaging in activities surrounding the topic. - A measurement campaign or intensive observation period involves collecting a large amount of data in a defined, and usually short, time period. 	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: What engagement strategies does the project have (e.g. gamification)?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None of the above • I don't know 		
20 (120)	<p>Does the project offer any incentives for participation?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial • Merchandise • Vouchers • General equipment, such as bird-boxes • Scientific equipment, such as sensors • Access to media and special events • Volunteering hours (for students or inmates) • Co-authorship • Food • Education, knowledge or skills • Increased sense of community • Socialisation (the activity of mixing socially with others) • A good excuse to avoid lockdown restrictions • The project does not offer incentives for participation • I don't know 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: Incentives to participate in an activity. Projects that incentivise participants can qualify as citizen science, but this is dependent on the context and form of relationship between project leaders and participants. Incentives could take different forms, such as small payments in crowdsourcing activities, or providing bikes to facilitate mobility in a place with high deprivation. However, the type or amount of the incentive should be taken into account before considering its consistency with citizen science. Acceptance of incentives/payments to participants in the citizen science context depends on the culture/country and the social/economic status of participants.</p> <p>Guldberg et al. 2019: engaging in social learning can create immediate value such as the company of like-minded people or doing something exciting.</p> <p>Woods et al. 2020: How has participating in the project enhanced your community?</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Type of incentives offered to encourage different participant groups</p>
21 (121)	<p>Does the project work with other organisations to involve specific target groups or individuals?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: For example, a project about water-quality monitoring might work with an organisation like a river trust to reach volunteers who are likely to be interested in water (the specific target group).</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: "Working with civic society organizations may allow for working with specific target groups and individuals with a genuine interest in the topic."</p>
22 (122)	<p>Does the project have a formal engagement strategy?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: An engagement strategy is a document which outlines the project's approach to engaging participants in the project activities.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: What engagement strategies does the project have (e.g. gamification)? Is the engagement strategy clearly communicated and transparent?</p>
23 (123)	<p>Is the engagement strategy shared with participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Is the engagement strategy clearly communicated and transparent?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
24 (124)	<p>How does the project communicate with participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online meetings • In person • In print • Online social media (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, LinkedIn, Instagram, TikTok) • Blogs • A forum • Newsletter or email update • Project website • Video platforms (for example, YouTube) • None of the above • I don't know 	<p><i>Information:</i> Some projects experiment with rich, multimedia formats such as video. Interestingly, video isn't always the best way to go; many people prefer news in text form. Simply put, video takes too long. The most important thing is to understand the project participants and what they want. You can read more here: https://digiday.com/media/despise-publisher-enthusiasm-video-people-prefer-getting-news-text/</p> <p>[Image: Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2016, https://www.digitalnewsreport.org/]</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Local and lay knowledge-sharing and application. Citizen involvement in producing and interpreting data gathered locally by community members, to raise local awareness and action, is a common model of citizen science. The active participation of professional scientists or researchers, and the sharing of results outside the local community, are not mandatory, as long as the project adheres to established research principles and practices.</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Are the project objectives and results clearly and transparently communicated?</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Peer-reviewed publications, Popular publications and outreach events</p> <p>Bonney et al. 2009: Frequency of media exposure</p> <p>Wiggins et al. 2018: Newsletters (Y/N), Videos (Y/N), Presentations (Y/N), Website (Y/N)</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Channels of data and information flow between different stakeholders, the pattern of information flow ('unidirectional', 'bi-directional' and 'interactive') between different stakeholders</p>
25 (125)	<p>Does the project include any of the following communication activities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hands-on experiences (for example, an interactive exhibit) • Multi-directional communication (for example, a forum where all stakeholders can have a voice) • Innovative means of communication (for example, TikTok) • Collaboration with science-communication professionals • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the communication strategy include hands-on experiences and bi-directional communication?</p> <p>Does the project include innovative means of science communication and popular media (e.g. art)?</p> <p>Does the project seek collaboration with science communication professionals?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
26 (126)	<p>How are the project outcomes shared?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scholarly outputs e.g. peer-review publications, open data sets Grey literature e.g. reports, working papers, policy briefs Popular media e.g. social media, magazine or newspaper articles, TV or radio, newsletters, leaflets Events e.g. conferences, community talks lectures, workshops, fairs, seminars or webinars None of the above I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Grey literature is produced by organisations whose main activity is not publishing (at least in traditional commercial or academic publishing). It can include reports, speeches, policy briefs and working papers.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: See above.</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Are the project objectives and results clearly and transparently communicated?</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Peer-reviewed publications, Popular publications and outreach events</p> <p>Bonney et al. 2009: Frequency of media exposure</p> <p>Wiggins et al. 2018: Newsletters (Y/N), Videos (Y/N), Presentations (Y/N), Website (Y/N)</p>
27 (127)	<p>Does the project have specific communication plans for specific target groups?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No The project has only one target group I don't know 	<p><i>Information:</i> Projects often have different communication plans for specific target groups. For example, projects which work with schools may need to contact teachers before other participants because teachers need to plan lessons in advance whereas the general public can be contacted closer to the start of project activities.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project have specific communication plans for target groups? Does the project have a targeted outreach and communication strategy?</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Considerations/strategies for the design of communication and outreach strategies; consideration for language/cultural barriers, etc.</p>
28 (128)	<p>Does the project create a positive change in how stakeholders communicate with one another?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> A positive change in how stakeholders communicate could include new communication channels, increased frequency of communication, or more diverse methods of communication (such as social media, newsletters, posters and emails).</p>	<p>Woods et al. 2020: How has participating in the project enhanced your community? To what extent has this project strengthened the communication and networks in your community?</p> <p>Fazey et al. 2014: New structure: new networks or structures are set up, communication is improved</p>
29 (129)	<p>As a result of this project, are channels available for participants and other stakeholders to communicate without the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No I don't know 		<p>Woods et al. 2020: See above.</p>
30 (130)	<p>Are there plans for sustaining the collaboration between citizen scientists and other stakeholders (for example, scientists or public authorities) beyond the current project activities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Are there plans for sustaining the collaboration between citizens and scientists?</p> <p>Haywood and Besley 2014: Do new networks, connections, or collaborative efforts result from the project or interactions among project participants or are existing connections strengthened? How are these networks sustained upon completion of the project?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no collaboration between citizens and other stakeholders in the project. • I don't know 		
31 (131)	<p>Which socially-relevant issues are directly addressed by the project? (We'll ask for details about each issue later.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poverty • Hunger and nutrition • Health and wellbeing • Education • Reduced inequalities • Gender equality • Decent work and economic growth • Industry, innovation and infrastructure • Responsible consumption and production • Peace, justice and strong institutions • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the scientific objective show relevance for society and does it address a socially relevant problem?</p> <p>SDGs: Goal 1. End poverty in all its forms everywhere; Goal 2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture; Goal 3. Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages; Goal 4. Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all; Goal 5. Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls; Goal 6. Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all; Goal 8. Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all; Goal 9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation; Goal 10. Reduce inequality within and among countries; Goal 12. Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns; Goal 16. Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels</p>
32 (132)	<p>Does the project relate to human physical health (directly or indirectly)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: Medical sciences and human health. Projects investigating human health (physical or mental) can present different challenges to assess as citizen science due to their varying levels of active engagement, the purpose of knowledge production, data sharing, the level of expertise required to assess medical information, and the involvement of commercial activities. In such cases, the organisational context needs to be considered: the same activity (e.g. a trial of an intervention) can be done by a hospital or a commercial actor, and therefore be assessed differently. While in other domains, sharing personal data is sometimes problematic, in the health domain it is almost a prerequisite to participation.</p>
33 (133)	<p>Does the project aid in the investigation of diseases?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, directly as part of the project activities • Yes, indirectly from the project activities • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG 3.3: By 2030, end the epidemics of AIDS, tuberculosis, malaria and neglected tropical diseases and combat hepatitis, water-borne diseases and other communicable diseases</p> <p>SDG 3.4 By 2030, reduce by one-third premature mortality from non-communicable diseases through prevention and treatment and promote mental health and well-being</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
34 (134)	<p>Does the project aid in the research and development of vaccines and medical interventions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, directly as part of the project activities • Yes, indirectly from the project activities • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG 3.b: Support the research and development of vaccines and medicines for the communicable and non-communicable diseases that primarily affect developing countries, provide access to affordable essential medicines and vaccines, in accordance with the Doha Declaration on the TRIPS Agreement and Public Health, which affirms the right of developing countries to use to the full the provisions in the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights regarding flexibilities to protect public health, and, in particular, provide access to medicines for all</p>
35 (135)	<p>Does the project explicitly investigate the link between pollution and health?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, air pollution • Yes, water pollution • Yes, some other kind of pollution • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG 3.9: "By 2030, substantially reduce the number of deaths and illnesses from hazardous chemicals and air, water and soil pollution and contamination."</p>
36 (136)	<p>Does the project have a positive impact on the physical health of participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG: Goal 3. Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages</p> <p>Chase and Levine 2016: A perceived direct link between a resource and the health and well-being of a community can also foster and influence citizen science programs. For example, a direct reliance on clean air and drinking water may foster a monitoring program for the resource, as well as motivate a pool of volunteers.</p>
37 (137)	<p>Does the project directly research mental health concerns?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Information</i>: More information about how a project could research mental health concerns and contextual examples are available in this paper: "Developing a Citizen Social Science approach to understand urban stress and promote wellbeing in urban communities".</p>	<p>SDG 3.4. See above.</p>
38 (138)	<p>Does the project actively raise motivation amongst participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Motivation is based on the individual's desire to achieve.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project raise motivation and self-esteem amongst participants?</p> <p>Phillips et al. 2018: Our new framework is thus based on both empirical data and contributions from the literature and includes the following learning outcomes: Interest in Science and the Environment; Self-efficacy for Science and the Environment; Motivation for Science and the Environment; Knowledge of the Nature of Science; Skills of Science Inquiry; and Behaviour and Stewardship.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
39 (139)	<p>Does the project increase the self-efficacy of participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Self-efficacy is based on an individual's belief in their own capacity to achieve.</p>	<p>Phillips et al. 2018: See above.</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Attitude towards their own abilities: This is for participants, facilitators, and organisations as a whole - it points to a level of (self-)confidence and acknowledgement of abilities, aspirations, and limitations. Limitations can be technical but may also be attitudinal. This input feature also aims to capture facilitators' and participants' lessons learnt, openness to change, willingness to share thoughts on room for improvement, etc.</p> <p>Fazey et al. 2014: Confidence: increased confidence in participants. Self-efficacy (of patients in speaking to doctors).</p>
40 (140)	<p>Does the project have a positive impact on the mental health of participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Pocock et al. 2019: Improved wellbeing and livelihoods through connection to (and consequent ownership of) nature and sense of belonging</p> <p>SDG 3.4. See above.</p> <p>Chase and Levine 2016: A perceived direct link between a resource and the health and well-being of a community can also foster and influence citizen science programs. For example, a direct reliance on clean air and drinking water may foster a monitoring program for the resource, as well as motivate a pool of volunteers.</p>
41 (141)	<p>Does the project investigate the social or psychological needs of non-human animals?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I'm too old for this question • I don't know 		<p>Peggs 2013: Two central questions are raised: first, should sociology include the study of nonhuman animals and secondly, can sociology advocate for non-human animals? The paper concludes with an affirmative response to both of these questions.</p>
42 (142)	<p>What kind of specific training does the project provide to participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Written instructions • Training video • In-person training • Online training • Training is not required • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDG: 4.4 By 2030, substantially increase the number of youth and adults who have relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship</p> <p>Haywood and Besley 2014: What instruction and training are necessary? When and how will this be provided?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
43 (143)	<p>How does the project contribute to the formal education of participants (for example, by working with schools)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-primary-level education to children • Primary-level education to pupils • Secondary-level education to pupils (middle and high school) • Tertiary education to students (university, college and vocational courses) • Adult education or life-long learning • The project does not contribute to the formal education of participants. • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Did the project contribute to adult education and life-long learning?</p> <p>SDG 4.1: By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes; 4.2: By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care and pre-primary education so that they are ready for primary education; 4.3 By 2030, ensure equal access for all women and men to affordable and quality technical, vocational and tertiary education, including university</p>
44 (144)	<p>What support is provided to educational institutions by the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-person sessions run by the project • Lesson plans • Educational resources (for example, work sheets or classroom activities) • Explicit links to the institution's curriculum • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDG 4.c By 2030, substantially increase the supply of qualified teachers, including through international cooperation for teacher training in developing countries, especially least developed countries and small island developing States</p>
45 (145)	<p>Do participants gain new knowledge from taking part in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Do individuals gain new knowledge, skills and competencies?</p> <p>Bonney et al. 2009: Improved participant understanding of science content</p> <p>Fazey et al. 2014: Increased knowledge, awareness or understanding</p>
46 (146)	<p>Do participants gain new skills from taking part in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: A skill is the ability to perform a task. To help participants learn new skills, the project might provide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT training (such as using a website), • Equipment training (such as, using an app), • Measurement training, • Training for the trainer, • Training about citizen-science methodologies. 	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: See above.</p> <p>Haywood and Besley 2014: Does knowledge about the science process increase or does the acquisition of skills occur? Are participants provided opportunities to expand skill sets that are transferable to other settings and applications? What new skills are developed?</p> <p>Bonney et al. 2009: Improved participant skills for conducting science</p> <p>Phillips et al. 2018: Skills of Science Inquiry</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
			<p>SDG: 4.4 By 2030, substantially increase the number of youth and adults who have relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship</p> <p>Fazey et al. 2014: Skills: new skills learned by participants</p>
47 (147)	<p>Do participants gain new competencies from taking part in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Competencies are behaviours which allow a participant to perform a task well and often require specific skills and knowledge. For example, competencies include working together, creativity and flexibility, the ability to learn, and internet savviness.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: See above.</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: There are specific skills and competencies that a community needs to participate in planning, decision making and governance processes. Longstaff (2005) argued that the capacity to acquire trusted and accurate information, to reflect on that information critically and to solve emerging problems is far more important for community resilience than is a detailed plan that rarely foresees all. Working together, creativity and flexibility, ability to learn, internet savviness.</p>
48 (148)	<p>Is specific equipment or infrastructure required for participants to be able to contribute to project activities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Wehn et al. 2017: Equipment required for participation, Infrastructure required for participation</p>
49 (149)	<p>Are specific knowledge and skills required for individuals to participate in the project activities? For example, do participants need to be trained before they can take part?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Wehn et al. 2017: Knowledge required for participation, Skills required for participation</p>
50 (150)	<p>Are support and training adapted to all relevant participant groups (e.g. participants' age, language)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: "All relevant participant groups" refers to those people who could reasonably be expected to have an interest in participating in the project; we don't expect projects to translate all their resources into Portuguese if the project only runs in Sweden.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Are support and training measures adapted to the different participant groups?</p> <p>Chase and Levine 2016: Ease of training or learning for monitoring</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: The percentage of activities purposefully modified to address issues of social justice and inclusion: e.g. translated methodologies and techniques, linked to the needs of a specific community, etc.</p>
51 (151)	<p>Has consideration been given to enable citizen participants to participate in the project given other demands and responsibilities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: This question refers to any consideration the project has made that allows participants to be involved in the project without a negative impact on their everyday lives. This may include running sessions both inside and outside of working hours (for participants who are involved in the project as part of their jobs and for those who are involved in a voluntary capacity), recording sessions to allow for viewing flexibility</p>	<p>Haywood and Besley 2014: Has adequate consideration been provided to allow citizen participants time and space to participate in the research given other demands and responsibilities?</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: The percentage of activities purposefully delivered in accessible locations: e.g. at community centres. The percentage of activities purposefully modified to address issues of social justice and inclusion: e.g. translated methodologies and techniques, linked to the needs of a specific community, etc. Considerations/strategies of ethical issues and values in the design, development and</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
		or allowing for data collection to occur at any time of day.	implementation of activities: This includes suitable event times and locations (provisions such as day care or meals).
52 (152)	<p>Has the project been designed to give access, where possible, to all participants, including those with "functional diversity" [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Functional_diversity_(disability)]?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Functional diversity is a politically and socially correct term for special needs, disability, impairment and handicap, which began to be used in Spain in scientific writing, at the initiative of those directly affected, in 2005 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Functional_diversity_(disability)].</p> <p>It is unlikely that a project can be made accessible to all potential participants. For example, it may not be possible to adapt projects which rely on participants recording observations to be accessible to individuals with visual impairments.</p>	<p>SDG 10.2: By 2030, empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status</p> <p>Butterfoss 2006: diversity of participants/organizations</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Strategies for addressing access issues from disadvantaged social groups: Number and type of strategies for e.g. the disabled. The percentage of activities purposefully delivered in accessible locations: e.g. at community centres.</p>
53 (153)	<p>Which age groups are the participants in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-10 • 11-20 • 21-40 • 41-60 • 61+ • I don't know 		<p>SDG 10.2: By 2030, empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status.</p> <p>Butterfoss 2006: diversity of participants/organizations.</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: DITOs: Strategies for addressing access issues from disadvantaged social groups: Number and type of strategies for e.g. elderly people.</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Demographic characteristics of the population</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
54 (154)	<p>Does the project explicitly promote diversity and inclusion among all relevant participant groups?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> A diverse group could include people from ethnic minorities, or people who are non-binary.</p>	<p>SDG 10.2: By 2030, empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status.</p> <p>Haywood and Besley 2014: How are citizen participants initially recruited and are diverse constituent groups targeted?</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Strategies for addressing access issues from disadvantaged social groups: Number and type of strategies for e.g. the disabled, illiterate people, migrants, elderly people, single parents, etc. The percentage of activities purposefully delivered in accessible locations: e.g. at community centres. The percentage of activities purposefully modified to address issues of social justice and inclusion: e.g. translated methodologies and techniques, linked to the needs of a specific community, etc. The percentage of participants attending events from disadvantaged groups: This includes inquiring how these participants found out about the event.</p>
55 (155)	<p>Does the project involve a socio-economically diverse pool of participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Participants are from the same socio-economical group • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Socioeconomic status is the social standing or class of an individual or group. It is often measured as a combination of education, income and occupation.</p>	<p>Palmer et al. 2017: Citizen science often struggles to attract a socio-economically diverse pool of participants, and that challenge is clearly vital to ensuring not only the equitable distribution of benefits stemming from participation, but also sound scientific outcomes.</p> <p>Butterfoss 2006: diversity of participants/organizations,</p>
56 (156)	<p>Does the project actively engage participants from disadvantaged or historically marginalised backgrounds?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG 1.4: By 2030, ensure that all men and women, in particular the poor and the vulnerable, have equal rights to economic resources, as well as access to basic services, ownership and control over land and other forms of property, inheritance, natural resources, appropriate new technology and financial services, including microfinance</p> <p>Pocock et al. 2019: Widens participation to all stakeholders (not just elites)</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Strategies for addressing access issues from disadvantaged social groups: Number and type of strategies for e.g. the disabled, illiterate people, migrants, elderly people, single parents, etc. The percentage of participants attending events from disadvantaged groups: This includes inquiring how these participants found out about the event.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
57 (157)	<p>Does the project make sure that minorities and those who usually have less power are among those who are able to influence the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No or not yet • I don't know 	<p><i>Information:</i> Whether the scientific questions to be addressed by a citizen science project come from citizens themselves or civic educators - including scientists, professional researchers, and their institutions - needs to be interrogated.</p> <p>Is it reasonable to expect communities to ask the questions?</p> <p>Is it overambitious to assume that they can?</p> <p>Does suggesting that they cannot indicate a level of institutional and structural racism?</p> <p>Empowering people includes enabling them to drive citizen-science projects. (Ceccaroni et al., 2021)</p>	<p>Ceccaroni et al. 2021: "How can we make sure that those with less power, women, and minorities are among those who are asking the questions? Is the science being conducted by a diverse group of people? Is it being analysed by a diverse group of people, using technology that does not discriminate?"</p> <p>"First, who asks the questions? Whether the scientific questions to be addressed by a citizen science project come from citizens themselves or civic educators (including scientists, professional researchers, and their institutions) needs to be interrogated. Is it reasonable to expect communities to initiate and drive a socio-environmental justice movement? Is it overambitious to assume that they can? Does suggesting that they cannot indicate a level of institutional and structural racism? Empowering people includes enabling them to initiate citizen science projects."</p>
58 (158)	<p>Does the project incorporate traditional or local knowledge?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Traditional knowledge and local knowledge generally refer to knowledge systems embedded in the cultural traditions of regional, indigenous, or local communities. These kinds of knowledge are generally based on accumulations of empirical observation and on interaction with the environment.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project ease the access to traditional and local knowledge resources?</p> <p>Pocock et al. 2019: Widening perspectives through better integration of indigenous knowledge and reflections from participants</p>
59 (159)	<p>Does the project explicitly contribute to gender equality?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG Goal 5. Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: % of women attending events; % of women in Advisory Boards; % of women facilitators & collaborators; % of women initiating/leading citizen initiatives; % of women sharing feedback.</p>
60 (160)	<p>What proportion of participants are cisgender men?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-20% • 21-40% • 41-60% • 61-80% • 81-100% • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Cisgender (sometimes shortened to cis) describes a person whose gender identity matches their sex assigned at birth.</p>	<p>DITOs consortium 2016: % of women attending events; % of women sharing feedback.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
61 (161)	<p>Are there relevant stakeholders which the project was not able to engage?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Wehn et al. 2017: Composition of stakeholders involved in decision making process in focus of the Demo Case.</p> <p>Skarlatidou et al. 2019: Our workshop identified certain stakeholder groups that tended to be neglected in our three case studies. For instance, funders are of the utmost importance, but they are often missing as a stakeholder group in the studied CS initiatives. Funders need to be identified early, approached regularly, and project results disseminated to them to increase future funding. Policy-makers were also found to be often neglected and need to be more actively engaged: Their support is crucial to increase the appreciation of the benefits of CS and evidence-based policymaking.</p>
62 (162)	<p>Does the project include objectives to protect or enhance cultural heritage components?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Chandler et al. 2017: Enhancing natural and socio-cultural capital to create a sustainable environment. Cultural heritage components enhanced.</p> <p>SDG: 11.4 Strengthen efforts to protect and safeguard the world's cultural and natural heritage</p>
63 (163)	<p>Does the project help to strengthen adaptive capacity to respond to natural disasters and other hazards?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG 13.1: Strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters in all countries</p>
64 (164)	<p>Does the project contribute to social innovation?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Social innovation is the process of developing and deploying effective solutions to challenging and often systemic social and environmental issues in support of social progress. These solutions often require the active collaboration of constituents across government, business, and the non-profit world.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project contribute to social innovation?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
65 (165)	<p>Does the project foster resilience (potentially by fostering learning and adaptation which then leads to resilience)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • After five minutes, I still don't understand the question • I don't know 	<p>This is often done by fostering one of the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) the will and intention to maintain social-ecological resilience (2) knowledge about the problem and the desired direction of change (3) proactive behaviour (4) the capacity to change existing patterns of behaviour. 	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project foster resilience and collective capacity for learning and adaptation?</p> <p>Fazey et al. 2007: Four main requirements enable societies to successfully adapt to change: (1) the will and intention to maintain social-ecological resilience, (2) knowledge about current problems and the desired direction of change, (3) proactive behaviour, and (4) the capacity to change existing patterns of behaviour.</p> <p>Haywood and Besley 2014: Does the project enhance the resiliency or adaptive capacity of socio-ecological systems? Are residents better prepared to face future challenges?</p> <p>SDG 1.5: By 2030, build the resilience of the poor and those in vulnerable situations and reduce their exposure and vulnerability to climate-related extreme events and other economic, social and environmental shocks and disasters. SDG 13.1 Strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-related hazards and natural disasters in all countries.</p>
66 (166)	<p>Does the project foster social capital?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 	<p>Social capital is the networks of relationships among people that enable society to function effectively.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project foster social capital?</p> <p>Woods et al. 2020: How has participating in the project enhanced your community? To what extent has this project strengthen the communication and networks in your community?</p>
67 (167)	<p>Does the project lead to an increased level of trust among participants and other stakeholders?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Haywood and Besley 2014: Does engagement in the project influence the level of trust, confidence, or respect among citizen participants and project leaders?</p> <p>Pocock et al. 2019: Greater ownership through involvement at every stage, including motivations for monitoring and action, increased trust, tolerance and attitudes to nature</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Trust and belonging (neighbourhood) Trust and belonging are important indicators of how much people care about their mutual environment. It is linked to the likelihood with which they will participate in decision making if it concerns their neighbourhood. Trust and belonging is measured with the presence of mutual concerns and shared values amongst neighbours and an emotional connection to the neighbourhood or city.</p> <p>Fazey et al. 2014: Shared understanding; consensus on the topic; fishing agreement in place; less intervillage conflict; communication and collaboration is increased; trust has increased between partners</p>

4.3 Impact on the environment

Citizen science has some potential to enable the reaching of some environmental SDGs, both directly and indirectly, and specifically:

- SDG 14 (life below water)
- SDG 15 (life on land)

SDG 14 and SDG 15 are both goals for which several targets specify actions to be taken by 2020, 2025, and 2030, and some of them are thus partly either achieved or delayed already. Nevertheless, some of the targets are more general; and the overall intentions behind these goals are also of interest on their own, seen apart from the specific targets.

SDG 14: Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.

The ten targets for SDG 14 specify goals related to the reduction of marine pollution of all kinds, the sustainable management of marine and coastal ecosystems, ocean acidification, overfishing and unregulated fishing practices, the conservation of 10% of marine and coastal areas, improved regulation and preferential treatment of developing nations and small island developing nations in particular. The means to achieve these goals are to increase scientific knowledge, develop research capacity, and transfer technology. In addition, specific attention is given to giving small-scale artisanal fishers access to marine resources and markets. Finally, international law and regulation of marine resources have to be enhanced.

One potential positive application of citizen science in this context is its use in improved monitoring and surveillance systems for marine and coastal areas and resources, including fish stocks and fishing vessels. Improved insight and control of all marine and coastal activity will enable both nations and the international community to further develop and, not least, enact stricter and more sustainable policies.

SDG 15: Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss.

SDG 15 encompasses terrestrial and inland water systems as well as other land-based ecosystems. The targets specify goals related to conservation, restoration, and sustainable use of such systems, sustainable use of forests and halting deforestation, fighting desertification, and conserving mountain ecosystems. It also calls for urgent and significant action to stop poaching and trafficking of vulnerable animals and flora. Furthermore, SDG 15 emphasises the need for fair and equitable access to the benefits from using genetic resources. This is to be achieved by the increased focus on ecosystem and biodiversity values in national and local planning, the mobilisation of resources to conserve and sustainably use biodiversity and ecosystems and forest management, and enhancing global support to combat unlawful poaching and trafficking.

The potential benefits of citizen science in enabling SDG 15 are once again related to its use in monitoring and generating actionable insight related to the status of ecosystems and biodiversity, thus improving sustainability through scientific conservationism. Increased information allows for taking appropriate action, understanding the trajectories we are on, and enabling transparency and the possibility of sanctions in treaties and partnerships.

The following table presents the input features used in MICS to measure how citizen science enables (or inhibits) the achievement of sustainable environmental development.

Table 4.c Environment-domain input features

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
1 (401)	<p>Does the project take measures to decrease its material footprint?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> A material footprint is the total amount of raw materials (including biomass - such as food for participants, fossil fuels - petrol for cars, metal and non-metal ores - often used in the production of laptops and smartphones) needed to meet the final demands of the project. All projects have a material footprint, and steps such as reducing the amount of printing and sharing equipment between teams can help to reduce the amount of "stuff" the project uses.</p>	<p>SDG 8.4.1; SDG 12.2.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP</p>
2 (402)	<p>Does the project take measures to reduce its polluting emissions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Polluting emissions can be caused by transport or energy use. This can be reduced by using carbon-neutral or net-zero transportation methods and clean energy sources.</p>	<p>SDG 9.4 By 2030, upgrade infrastructure and retrofit industries to make them sustainable, with increased resource-use efficiency and greater adoption of clean and environmentally sound technologies and industrial processes, with all countries taking action in accordance with their respective capabilities. SDG 9.4.1 CO2 emission per unit of value added.</p>
3 (403)	<p>Does the project have a procurement policy that is environmentally sustainable?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> A procurement policy guides decision making and purchasing within a project or operation to ensure that the solutions are in line with the values and ethics of the organisation.</p> <p>The environmental impact of the procurement policy can be improved by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using items of high recycled content or those that can be recycled or reused, • Using services that consider and reduce their environmental impact, • Considering the amount of, and cost of energy used in processes. <p>More information on writing a procurement policy can be found at https://planergy.com/blog/procurement-policy-sample/.</p>	<p>SDG 12.7 Promote public procurement practices that are sustainable and in accordance with national policies and priorities</p>
4 (404)	<p>Does the project explicitly share information on sustainable development or lifestyles?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Information on sustainable development or lifestyles could be shared directly with participants or more widely through the project's social media and other communication channels.</p>	<p>SDG 12.8 "By 2030, ensure that people everywhere have the relevant information and awareness for sustainable development and lifestyles in harmony with nature."</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
5 (405)	<p>Does the project educate participants on environmental challenges?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG 13.3 "Improve education, awareness-raising and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction and early warning."</p> <p>Braun and Dierkes 2019: Environmental knowledge incorporates at least three different subtypes: system, action-related and effectiveness knowledge. To enable a person to act in an environmentally friendly manner, they must primarily understand the basic structural and functional characteristics of an ecosystem (system knowledge). Furthermore, knowledge about solutions for environmental issues (action-related knowledge) and the benefit of sustainable actions (effectiveness knowledge) are deemed crucial for an individual to choose a set of behaviours.</p>
6 (406)	<p>Does the project explicitly contribute to a higher awareness of, or positive attitude towards, the natural environment, on this planet or others?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Ecological impact "Does the project contribute to higher awareness and responsibility for the natural environment?"</p> <p>Braun and Dierkes 2019: Environmental knowledge incorporates at least three different subtypes: system, action-related and effectiveness knowledge. To enable a person to act in an environmentally friendly manner, they must primarily understand the basic structural and functional characteristics of an ecosystem (system knowledge). Furthermore, knowledge about solutions for environmental issues (action-related knowledge) and the benefit of sustainable actions (effectiveness knowledge) are deemed crucial for an individual to choose a set of behaviours.</p> <p>Zwickle and Jones 2018: This chapter introduces a revised Assessment of Sustainability Knowledge (ASK) and the Sustainability Attitudes Scale (SAS), and discusses when and how to use them for applied and theoretical purposes.</p> <p>Pocock et al. 2019: Increased awareness of conservation and the environment by individuals, communities, media, NGOs and governments</p> <p>Milfont and Duckitt 2010: Environmental attitudes (EA), a crucial construct in environmental psychology, are a psychological tendency expressed by evaluating the natural environment with some degree of favour or disfavour. There are hundreds of EA measures available based on different conceptual and theoretical frameworks, and most researchers prefer to generate new measures rather than organize those already available. The present research provides a cumulative and theoretical approach to the measurement of EA, in which the multidimensional and hierarchical nature of EA is considered. Reported are findings from three studies on the development of a psychometrically sound, multidimensional inventory to assess EA cross-culturally, the Environmental Attitudes Inventory (EAI).</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
7 (407)	<p>Does the project lead to an increased stewardship of the natural environment among participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Phillips et al. 2018: Our new framework is thus based on both empirical data and contributions from the literature and includes the following learning outcomes: Interest in Science and the Environment; Self-efficacy for Science and the Environment; Motivation for Science and the Environment; Knowledge of the Nature of Science; Skills of Science Inquiry; and Behaviour and Stewardship.</p>
8 (408)	<p>Does the project collaborate with external companies to enable the adoption of sustainable practices?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG 12.6 Encourage companies, especially large and transnational companies, to adopt sustainable practices and to integrate sustainability information into their reporting cycle</p> <p>Woods et al. 2016: Level of regulation and enforcement of environmental standards for business and industry</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Enabling organizations and businesses to become more sustainable. Partnerships: organizations actively engaged</p>
9 (409)	<p>Do the project activities include pro-environmental actions e.g. litter picking?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: This collaboration may involve working with companies that have made pledges to work towards sustainable practices (clean energy, waste reduction, carbon neutral practices) or that are certified to work to an environmental standard, such as B Corps.</p>	<p>Chandler et al. 2017: Pro-environment actions taken at the research project site</p>
10 (410)	<p>Does the project include objectives to protect or enhance natural resources?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Ecological impact "Does the project include objectives that protect and enhance natural resources?"</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Natural habitats enhanced</p>
11 (411)	<p>Does the project help to identify the location of specific issues related to environmental challenges?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Ways in which a project might help to identify the location of a specific issue include identifying which sections of a river are polluted or which areas of a city have high levels of air pollution.</p>	<p>Moses 2022: The role of citizen science in improving source awareness is less clear. Without a greater emphasis on sources of pollution, scientists or community members using citizen science techniques cannot effectively identify or target interventions</p> <p>Dickinson et al. 2012: Dispersed data collection and the ability to collect observations and connect with people, in places, and at scales that would otherwise not be possible render citizen science increasingly important to environmental research. Today, the internet and geographic-information-system—enabled web applications allow participants to collect large volumes of location-based ecological data and submit them electronically to centralized databases.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
12 (412)	<p>Does the project inform how a natural resource or ecosystem is managed?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Pocock et al. 2019: Improved conservation action leading to better environments including ecosystem function, ecosystem services and resilience</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Informing environmental policies, agendas, management plans and government policies. Contributions to conventions, agendas, policies, and management plans.</p>
13 (413)	<p>Does the project monitor ecosystem services?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment – a four-year United Nations assessment of the condition and trends of the world’s ecosystems - categorizes ecosystem services as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provisioning Services or the provision of food, fresh water, fuel, fibre, and other goods; • Regulating Services such as climate, water, and disease regulation as well as pollination; • Supporting Services such as soil formation and nutrient cycling; and • Cultural Services such as educational, aesthetic, and cultural heritage values as well as recreation and tourism. 	<p>Pocock et al. 2019: See above.</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Enhancing natural and socio-cultural capital to create a sustainable environment. Ecosystem services enhanced.</p>
14 (414)	<p>Which environmental challenges are related to the aims of the project? (We'll ask for details about each issue later.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable agriculture • Freshwater • Affordable and clean energy • Sustainable cities and communities • Air quality • Responsible consumption and production (including food waste and chemical pollution) • Climate action • Marine water • Life on land • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDGs Goal 2. End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture; Goal 6. Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all; Goal 7. Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all; Goal 11. Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable; Goal 12. Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns; Goal 13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts; Goal 14. Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development; Goal 15. Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss;</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
15 (415)	<p>How does the project contribute to sustainable agriculture?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researching sustainable agriculture • Increasing the proportion of agricultural area being managed sustainably • Increasing investment in rural infrastructure, agricultural research and technology development • Increasing agricultural productivity • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDGs 2.a "Increase investment, including through enhanced international cooperation, in rural infrastructure, agricultural research and extension services, technology development and plant and livestock gene banks in order to enhance agricultural productive capacity in developing countries, in particular least developed countries"; 2.4.1 "Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture". 2.3 "By 2030, double the agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers, in particular women, indigenous peoples, family farmers, pastoralists and fishers, including through secure and equal access to land, other productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment"</p>
16 (416)	<p>With regards to freshwater, which of the following does the project monitor?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambient water quality or pollution • Water-related ecosystems and biodiversity • Water-use efficiency • Water stress or water scarcity • Correct treatment of wastewater • River restoration • Physical quality or engineering and land use pressures • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDGs 6.3.2 "Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality"; 6.6 By 2020, protect and restore water-related ecosystems, including mountains, forests, wetlands, rivers, aquifers and lakes; 6.4 By 2030, substantially increase water-use efficiency across all sectors and ensure sustainable withdrawals and supply of freshwater to address water scarcity and substantially reduce the number of people suffering from water scarcity; 6.4.2 "Level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources"; 6.3.1 Proportion of domestic and industrial wastewater flows safely treated; 6.6.1 "Change in the extent of water-related ecosystems over time"; 6.b "Support and strengthen the participation of local communities in improving water and sanitation management"</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Quality of specific natural resources</p>
17 (417)	<p>With regards to freshwater, which of the following does the project have a demonstrable positive impact on?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambient water quality or pollution • Water-related ecosystems and biodiversity • Water-use efficiency • Water stress or water scarcity • Correct treatment of wastewater • River restoration • Physical quality or engineering and land use pressures • Involving local communities in water management • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDGs 6.3.2 "Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality"; 6.6 By 2020, protect and restore water-related ecosystems, including mountains, forests, wetlands, rivers, aquifers and lakes; 6.4 By 2030, substantially increase water-use efficiency across all sectors and ensure sustainable withdrawals and supply of freshwater to address water scarcity and substantially reduce the number of people suffering from water scarcity; 6.4.2 "Level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources"; 6.3.1 Proportion of domestic and industrial wastewater flows safely treated; 6.6.1 "Change in the extent of water-related ecosystems over time"; 6.b "Support and strengthen the participation of local communities in improving water and sanitation management"</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Quality of specific natural resources</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Ecosystem services enhanced</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
18 (418)	<p>How does the project contribute to affordable and clean energy?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researching clean energy • Increasing the share of clean energy in the energy mix • Increasing energy efficiency • None of the above • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Clean energy includes sources like sunlight, wind, rain, tides, waves, and geothermal heat.</p>	<p>SDGs 7.2 "By 2030, increase substantially the share of renewable energy in the global energy mix"; 7.3 By 2030, double the global rate of improvement in energy efficiency; 7.a "By 2030, enhance international cooperation to facilitate access to clean energy research and technology, including renewable energy, energy efficiency and advanced and cleaner fossil-fuel technology, and promote investment in energy infrastructure and clean energy technology"</p>
19 (419)	<p>With regards to sustainable cities and communities, which of the following does the project monitor?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Correct collection and treatment of solid waste • Green/blue public spaces • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDGs 11.3.2 "Proportion of cities with a direct participation structure of civil society in urban planning and management that operate regularly and democratically"; 11.6.1 "Proportion of urban solid waste regularly collected and with adequate final discharge out of total urban solid waste generated, by cities"; 11.7 "By 2030, provide universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible, green and public spaces, in particular for women and children, older persons and persons with disabilities"</p>
20 (420)	<p>With regards to sustainable cities and communities, which of the following does the project have a demonstrable positive impact on?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involving local communities in urban planning and management • Correct collection and treatment of solid waste • Green/blue public spaces • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDGs 11.3.2 "Proportion of cities with a direct participation structure of civil society in urban planning and management that operate regularly and democratically"; 11.6.1 "Proportion of urban solid waste regularly collected and with adequate final discharge out of total urban solid waste generated, by cities"; 11.7 "By 2030, provide universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible, green and public spaces, in particular for women and children, older persons and persons with disabilities"</p>
21 (421)	<p>Does the project monitor ambient air quality or pollution?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG 11.6.2 "Annual mean levels of fine particulate matter (e.g. PM2.5 and PM10) in cities (population weighted)."</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Average concentration of particulate matter (PM2.5) in the air</p>
22 (422)	<p>With regards to air quality, which of the following does the project have a demonstrable positive impact on?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involving local communities in air quality management • Ambient air quality and pollution (including fine particulate matter, e.g. PM2.5 and PM10) • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDG 11.6.2: See above.</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Average concentration of particulate matter (PM2.5) in the air</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
23 (423)	<p>With regards to responsible consumption and production, which of the following does the project monitor?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food waste • Harmful chemicals in the air • Harmful chemicals in the water • Harmful chemicals in the soil • Waste generation and management (including prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse) • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDGs 12.3 "By 2030, halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses"; 12.4 "By 2020, achieve the environmentally sound management of chemicals and all wastes throughout their life cycle, in accordance with agreed international frameworks, and significantly reduce their release to air, water and soil in order to minimize their adverse impacts on human health and the environment"; 12.5 "By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse"</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Average concentration of particulate matter (PM2.5) in the air</p> <p>Woods et al. 2016: Availability and ease of recycling of paper, plastic, hazardous waste, and metal for both households and business/industry</p>
24 (424)	<p>With regards to responsible consumption and production, which of the following does the project have a demonstrable positive impact on?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food waste • Harmful chemicals in the air • Harmful chemicals in the water • Harmful chemicals in the soil • Waste generation and management (including prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse) • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDGs 12.3 "By 2030, halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer levels and reduce food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses"; 12.4 "By 2020, achieve the environmentally sound management of chemicals and all wastes throughout their life cycle, in accordance with agreed international frameworks, and significantly reduce their release to air, water and soil in order to minimize their adverse impacts on human health and the environment"; 12.5 "By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse"</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Average concentration of particulate matter (PM2.5) in the air</p>
25 (425)	<p>With regards to marine water, which of the following does the project monitor?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine nutrient pollution • Marine plastic pollution • Ocean acidification • Marine protected areas • Overfishing • Marine technology • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDGs 14.1 "By 2025, prevent and significantly reduce marine pollution of all kinds, in particular from land-based activities, including marine debris and nutrient pollution"; 14.3 "Minimize and address the impacts of ocean acidification, including through enhanced scientific cooperation at all levels"; 14.5 "By 2020, conserve at least 10 per cent of coastal and marine areas, consistent with national and international law and based on the best available scientific information"; 14.a "Increase scientific knowledge, develop research capacity and transfer marine technology, taking into account the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission Criteria and Guidelines on the Transfer of Marine Technology, in order to improve ocean health and to enhance the contribution of marine biodiversity to the development of developing countries, in particular small island developing States and least developed countries" 14.4 "By 2020, effectively regulate harvesting and end overfishing, illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing and destructive fishing practices and implement science-based management plans, in order to restore fish stocks in the shortest time feasible, at least to levels that can produce maximum sustainable yield as determined by their biological characteristics."</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
26 (426)	<p>With regards to marine water, which of the following does the project have a demonstrable positive impact on?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine nutrient pollution • Marine plastic pollution • Ocean acidification • Marine protected areas • Overfishing • Marine technology • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDGs: See above.</p>
27 (427)	<p>With regards to life on land, which of the following does the project monitor?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable management of forests • Desertification or land degradation • Mountain ecosystems • Other terrestrial ecosystems • Biodiversity • Species extinction • Invasive alien species • Wildlife poaching or trafficking • Animal behaviour • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDGs 15.1 "By 2020, ensure the conservation, restoration and sustainable use of terrestrial and inland freshwater ecosystems and their services, in particular forests, wetlands, mountains and drylands, in line with obligations under international agreements"; 15.2 "By 2020, promote the implementation of sustainable management of all types of forests, halt deforestation, restore degraded forests and substantially increase afforestation and reforestation globally"; 15.3 "By 2030, combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil, including land affected by desertification, drought and floods, and strive to achieve a land degradation-neutral world 15.4 By 2030, ensure the conservation of mountain ecosystems, including their biodiversity, in order to enhance their capacity to provide benefits that are essential for sustainable development"; 15.5 "Take urgent and significant action to reduce the degradation of natural habitats, halt the loss of biodiversity and, by 2020, protect and prevent the extinction of threatened species"; 15.7 "Take urgent action to end poaching and trafficking of protected species of flora and fauna and address both demand and supply of illegal wildlife products"; 15.8 "By 2020, introduce measures to prevent the introduction and significantly reduce the impact of invasive alien species on land and water ecosystems and control or eradicate the priority species" 15.c Enhance global support for efforts to combat poaching and trafficking of protected species, including by increasing the capacity of local communities to pursue sustainable livelihood opportunities</p> <p>Pocock et al. 2019: See above.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
28 (428)	<p>With regards to life on land, which of the following does the project have a demonstrable positive impact on?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable management of forests • Desertification or land degradation • Mountain ecosystems • Other terrestrial ecosystems • Biodiversity • Species extinction • Invasive alien species • Wildlife poaching or trafficking • None of the above • I don't know 		<p>SDGs 15.1 "By 2020, ensure the conservation, restoration and sustainable use of terrestrial and inland freshwater ecosystems and their services, in particular forests, wetlands, mountains and drylands, in line with obligations under international agreements"; 15.2 "By 2020, promote the implementation of sustainable management of all types of forests, halt deforestation, restore degraded forests and substantially increase afforestation and reforestation globally"; 15.3 "By 2030, combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil, including land affected by desertification, drought and floods, and strive to achieve a land degradation-neutral world 15.4</p> <p>By 2030, ensure the conservation of mountain ecosystems, including their biodiversity, in order to enhance their capacity to provide benefits that are essential for sustainable development"; 15.5 "Take urgent and significant action to reduce the degradation of natural habitats, halt the loss of biodiversity and, by 2020, protect and prevent the extinction of threatened species"; 15.7 "Take urgent action to end poaching and trafficking of protected species of flora and fauna and address both demand and supply of illegal wildlife products"; 15.8 "By 2020, introduce measures to prevent the introduction and significantly reduce the impact of invasive alien species on land and water ecosystems and control or eradicate the priority species"</p> <p>Pocock et al. 2019: See above.</p>
29 (429)	<p>Does the project help to classify local breeds or species at risk of extinction?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG 2.5.2 Proportion of local breeds classified as being at risk of extinction</p>
30 (430)	<p>Does the project contribute to secure plant and animal genetic resources in either medium- or long-term conservation facilities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG 2.5.1 "Number of plant and animal genetic resources for food and agriculture secured in either medium or long-term conservation facilities."</p>

4.4 Impact on governance

The goal detailed in this section is the following:

- SDG 17 (partnerships for the goals)

The standard three dimensions of sustainability (economy, society, and environment) arguably underplay the importance of the governance domain. Even if the three dimensions are very established, MICS breaks the convention, considering that governance is vital for reaching all and any of the SDGs. While SDG 16 (which is categorised as a social goal) and SDG 17 go some way towards describing the kinds of governance activity required to enable the reaching of the SDGs, they still leave much of the governance territory underexplored, for example, at the level of project governance.

SDG 17: Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalise the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development.

Citizen science often plays a role in monitoring systems, which are part of the governance domain, in which case it might be said to improve both the chances of partnerships being formed around that monitoring effort and the chances of any partnership being successful. This is, however, more related to the creation and implementation of effective monitoring systems in general and not necessarily dependent on citizen science to a significant degree.

MICS's reason for arguing that citizen science can have a significant impact on governance can be seen more clearly if the targets of SDG 17 are considered. They relate to, for example, domestic mobilisation of resources for sustainable development, mobilisation of resources (finance) in general, follow-through by developed countries on their development assistance, and coordination of policies. Of particular importance are the need to assist least developed countries, to enhance science sharing and cooperation across regional, North-South and South-South boundaries, and crucially:

Promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally-sound technologies to developing countries on favourable terms, including on concessional and preferential terms, as mutually agreed (Target 17.7).

The latter target strikes at the core of citizen science's suitable nature as a sustainable development tool.

Citizen science can thus be a subject matter and a key topic when partnerships are sought and formed, and when policy and regulations are developed and harmonised globally. Citizen science and the associated technologies and infrastructure are one of the focus areas for technology transfer and diffusion if the SDGs are to be reached. This will not occur through the use of citizen science by a small number of influential organisations or projects in selected countries or continents. Citizen science will have a positive impact only when citizen-science capacity is built domestically, with a particular focus on the least developed countries, and when access to citizen science, including its development, tailoring, and deployment, is both fair and equitable.

Citizen science holds great promise if the current obstacles to its use in the Global South are removed. This can, however, only happen through the active and resource-demanding efforts of developed countries, and this is what SDG 17 is all about.

The input features related to governance are presented in the following table and constitute the basis for examining the overall impact of citizen science on this domain.

Table 4.d Governance-domain input features

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
1 (201)	<p>How is the project managed?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project is run by a single organisation • The project is run by a group of organisations but led by a single organisation • The project is run by a group of organisations that lead equally • The project is run by citizens • An Artificial Intelligence is running the project • Some other management structure • I don't know 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: Individual project, community-led project and researcher-led project. Citizen science projects can be led by researchers or scientists, or can be led collaboratively by a community to address a particular issue. Projects can also be run by an individual, who will carry out the whole project alone. All are potentially consistent with citizen science, and the decision on each project can be made by examining its context and practices.</p>
2 (202)	<p>What type of organisation leads the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public bodies (including governments and municipalities) • Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), charities, and community-based organisations • Research-performing organisations (including universities) • Some other kind of organisation • I don't know 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: Research-performing organisations, public bodies and institutions, non-governmental organisations. Citizen science initiatives can be supported and run by different types of organisations. While commercial activities need special attention, activities that are run by public bodies (e.g. environmental monitoring) and non-governmental organisations (e.g. health charities) could be part of citizen science, and it is not mandatory to include professional scientists or research-performing organisations.</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: PI affiliation: University, NGO, University and NGO, Government agency.</p>
3 (203)	<p>What types of organisations are partners in running the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public bodies (including governments and municipalities) • Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), charities, and community-based organisations • Research-performing organisations (including universities) • Some other kind of organisation • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Organisations which are partners in running the project will likely have made a formal commitment to running the project (for example, signing a consortium agreement) and may have received funding if the project was funded by a grant.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Research-performing organisations, public bodies and institutions, non-governmental organisations. Citizen science initiatives can be supported and run by different types of organisations. While commercial activities need special attention, activities that are run by public bodies (e.g. environmental monitoring) and non-governmental organisations (e.g. health charities) could be part of citizen science, and it is not mandatory to include professional scientists or research-performing organisations.</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Partnerships: organizations actively engaged</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
4 (204)	<p>What types of organisations are involved with the project (but don't help to manage the project)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public bodies (including governments and municipalities) • Non-governmental organisations (NGOs), charities, and community-based organisations • Research-performing organisations (including universities) • Some other kind of organisation • No other organisations are involved with the project • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> There are many ways organisations could be involved with a citizen science project without directly helping to manage the project. For example, representatives from the organisation could attend project events or the organisation may have expressed an interest in using the results of the project.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Research-performing organisations, public bodies and institutions, non-governmental organisations. Citizen science initiatives can be supported and run by different types of organisations. While commercial activities need special attention, activities that are run by public bodies (e.g. environmental monitoring) and non-governmental organisations (e.g. health charities) could be part of citizen science, and it is not mandatory to include professional scientists or research-performing organisations.</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Composition of stakeholders involved in decision-making process in the focus of the initiative</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Partnerships: organizations actively engaged</p>
5 (205)	<p>Does the project have explicit links with public authorities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> There are many ways in which a project could have explicit links with public authorities. For example, having them as partners of the consortium managing the project, as part of the advisory board, or as regular attendants of project events.</p>	<p>Ferri et al. 2020: Citizen observatories (COs) are a particular form of citizen science in so far as they constitute the means not just for new knowledge creation but also for its application, which is why they are typically set up with linkages to specific policy domains (Wehn et al., 2019). COs must, therefore, include a public authority (e.g. a local, regional or national body) to enable two-way communication between citizens and the authorities to create a new source of high-quality, authoritative data for decision-making and for the benefit of society.</p>
6 (206)	<p>Does the project explicitly foster new relationships among different stakeholders (not including those between citizens and scientists; so, for example, between public bodies and commercial organisations)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Scientific impact: New knowledge resources "Does the project foster new collaborations amongst societal actors and groups?"</p> <p>Haywood and Besley, 2014: Do new networks, connections, or collaborative efforts result from the project or interactions among project participants or are existing connections strengthened?</p>
7 (207)	<p>Does the project collaborate with other initiatives to enhance mutual learning?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Collaboration and synergies "Does the project collaborate with other initiatives at national or international level to enhance mutual learning and adaptation?"</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
8 (208)	<p>Which resources does the project directly share with other initiatives?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data • Learnings • Participants • Instruments (for example, measuring kits) • Methodologies • Resources on the theory and practice of citizen science • Communication channels • Other resources • The project does not share resources with other initiatives • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Scientific impact: New fields of research and research structures "Did any cross-fertilization of projects take place?"</p>
9 (209)	<p>Among which of the following dimensions does the project create institutional change (within the organisations associated with the project)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open access/data: for example, development of an organisational Data Management Plan • Ethics: for example, creation of an ethics board, or employment of a quality assurance officer • Gender equality: for example, development of an organisational Gender Equality Plan • Public engagement • Science education • Responsible research and innovation: for example, development of organisational practices that enhance social responsibility, inclusiveness or sustainability of research and innovation processes and products • The project does not create institutional change among these dimensions • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> This question refers to the "institutional changes" a project contributes to, which EU-funded projects are required to consider.</p> <p>The institutional change is usually measured along the following six dimensions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open access/data 2. Ethics 3. Gender equality 4. Public engagement 5. Science education 6. Responsible research and innovation <p>This question asks not just what dimensions the project works on, but whether the project has led to a change in the organisations associated with the project.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Scientific impact: New fields of research and research structures "Did the project contribute to any institutional or structural changes?"</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Capacity building initiatives at the organisational level [for public engagement]: How do facilitators prepare for their science activities (what training, sources, guidance do they use); how are they supported (infrastructurally (on and off-line), in terms of content and resources, etc.); what learning plans are in place (e.g. scientific procedures, philosophical orientations, technical issues, learning methodologies, etc.).</p>
10 (210)	<p>Are the outputs generated by the project open access?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes; all outputs • Yes: some outputs • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Outputs are any direct result of the project's activities. They include data collected, and technology developed (and the data collected by that technology) during the project.</p>	<p>SDG 16.10 "Ensure public access to information and protect fundamental freedoms, in accordance with national legislation and international agreements."</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project have open interfaces to connect to other systems and platforms?; Is the generated data shared publicly and if so, under which conditions?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
11 (211)	<p>How can the outputs generated by the project be used by external parties?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outputs can be shared • Outputs can be edited or combined with other material to produce a new work • Outputs can be used for commercial purposes • Outputs can be used without attribution to the author • I don't know. 		<p>SDG 16.10: See above.</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: See above.</p>
12 (212)	<p>Does the project have a data management plan?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: A data management plan describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project have a data management plan, IPR strategy and ethical guidelines?</p>
13 (213)	<p>The following four questions focus on the 'FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship'. They focus on the data generated by the project, rather than on other outputs.</p> <p>Are the data generated by the project findable?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: To be findable, data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier and are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.</p> <p><i>Information</i>: The FAIR Guiding Principles aim to encourage good data management with the end goal of increasing the ease of finding and sharing data, particularly in the case of machine automated data retrieval. It is based on four principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability), which are fully defined in the following questions, and apply to data, algorithms, tools and workflows. It is important that datasets can be easily found, accessed (while protecting privacy where applicable) and reused in future projects to aid research and development. The guidelines can be applied to different degrees to suit the characteristics of the data.</p> <p>More information about the FAIR guidelines can be found in this paper: "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship".</p>	<p>Wilkinson et al. 2016: [the FAIR guiding principles]</p> <p>ECSA Characteristics: Data ownership and use. Citizen science is commonly perceived and placed within the open science domain, such as by complying with open data-sharing, open access publications, and full transparency of data ownership. There may, however, be cases in which data use is limited to certain stakeholder groups, the outcomes are not made public, or the publications generated are not open access, particularly with regards to privacy concerns. It is preferable for participants to own the data they generate, and they should be made fully aware of why, when and how it is used by others.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
14 (214)	<p>Are the data generated by the project accessible?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> To be accessible, data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol. The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.</p>	<p>Wilkinson et al. 2016: [the FAIR guiding principles]</p> <p>ECSA Characteristics: Data ownership and use. Citizen science is commonly perceived and placed within the open science domain, such as by complying with open data-sharing, open access publications, and full transparency of data ownership. There may, however, be cases in which data use is limited to certain stakeholder groups, the outcomes are not made public, or the publications generated are not open access, particularly with regards to privacy concerns. It is preferable for participants to own the data they generate, and they should be made fully aware of why, when and how it is used by others.</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the data adhere to common standards?</p>
15 (215)	<p>Are the data generated by the project interoperable?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> To be interoperable, data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. An example would be a resource that is available in a standardised format, clearly labelled, and with relationships between categories shown.</p>	<p>Wilkinson et al. 2016: [the FAIR guiding principles]</p> <p>ECSA Characteristics: Data ownership and use. Citizen science is commonly perceived and placed within the open science domain, such as by complying with open data-sharing, open access publications, and full transparency of data ownership. There may, however, be cases in which data use is limited to certain stakeholder groups, the outcomes are not made public, or the publications generated are not open access, particularly with regards to privacy concerns. It is preferable for participants to own the data they generate, and they should be made fully aware of why, when and how it is used by others.</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the data adhere to common standards?</p>
16 (216)	<p>Are the data generated by the project reusable?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> To be reusable, data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license and meet domain-relevant community standards.</p>	<p>Wilkinson et al. 2016: [the FAIR guiding principles]</p> <p>ECSA Characteristics: Data ownership and use. Citizen science is commonly perceived and placed within the open science domain, such as by complying with open data-sharing, open access publications, and full transparency of data ownership. There may, however, be cases in which data use is limited to certain stakeholder groups, the outcomes are not made public, or the publications generated are not open access, particularly with regards to privacy concerns. It is preferable for participants to own the data they generate, and they should be made fully aware of why, when and how it is used by others.</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the data adhere to common standards?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
17 (217)	<p>Whilst the FAIR Guiding Principles are highly specific in their definition, there are other ways to consider the project's data. For example...</p> <p>Are data access rights clear and transparent?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Making data access rights clear and transparent doesn't necessarily mean that all data has to be fully open access. However, it does mean that it should be obvious what data is accessible to who.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Are data ownership and access rights clear and transparent?</p>
18 (218)	<p>Do other stakeholders have more access to project data than participants (for example, access to raw data)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Wehn et al. 2017: Access restrictions to the data for different stakeholder groups</p>
19 (219)	<p>Are participants informed about where the data collected by the project are stored?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Data and Systems: Ethics, data protection, IPR "Is the data handling process transparent? E.g. do citizens know what the data is used for, where the data is stored and shared?"</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Access restrictions to the data for different stakeholder groups</p>
20 (220)	<p>Are participants informed about how the data collected and analysed by the project are used?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Data and Systems: Ethics, data protection, IPR "Is the data handling process transparent? E.g. do citizens know what the data is used for, where the data is stored and shared?"</p>
21 (221)	<p>Are participants informed about whether the data collected by the project are shared?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Data and Systems: Ethics, data protection, IPR "Is the data handling process transparent? E.g. do citizens know what the data is used for, where the data is stored and shared?"</p>
22 (222)	<p>Does the project explicitly state which procedures it follows to ensure all data are collected and processed lawfully?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • The project doesn't need to ensure the data are collected lawfully • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> "All data" here refers to any data collected by the project, not just personal data about participants.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: "This statement is also linked to the 'Ethics' statement above, and attention should be paid to local ethics practices and guidance on personal and medical data."</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project have a data management plan, IPR strategy and ethical guidelines?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
23 (223)	<p>Does the project involve the collection of personal data of the participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, at least sometimes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Personal data is any information that relates to an identified, or identifiable, living individual.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Sharing personal and medical data. In the medical and the social sciences, the boundaries of citizen science and data-collection practices can be challenging. Sharing personal and medical data can be part of citizen science, but this depends on the framing and intention of the project, and on a consideration of whether those taking part are subjects of research or participants who are shaping and carrying out different stages of the project. The inclusion of practices that are in line with the <i>ten principles</i> can assist in establishing this.</p>
24 (224)	<p>Do participants have to explicitly give consent (for example, signing a consent form) to take part in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: The aim here is to re-emphasise the need for ethical practices, and with a linkage to the previous statements in this section. The need for communication of ethical standards “clearly and openly” is noted as explicit consent from participants.</p>
25 (225)	<p>Does the project have a code of ethics?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project have a data management plan, IPR strategy and ethical guidelines?</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Considerations/strategies of ethical issues and values in the design, development and implementation of activities:</p>
26 (226)	<p>Is the code of ethics made available to participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Bowser et al. 2017: Some research suggests that incomplete or poorly articulated data policies prevent volunteers from understanding how information is collected and shared. Volunteers become aware of privacy concerns in a number of ways. Ideally, information on key facets of participation— particularly the types of data collected, and relevant information flows—is posted to a project’s website. But data policies are often opaque, or insufficiently documented.</p> <p>Bowser and Wiggins 2015: To effectively support agency, all policies should be hosted on clearly labelled pages and explained at in-person recruitment and training events.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
27 (227)	<p>Does the project include opportunities for project leaders and participants to discuss the ethical and political dimensions of the science involved?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Haywood and Besley 2014: Table 1: Science in Society Bell et al., 2009; Biegelbauer and Hansen, 2011; Blackstock et al., 2007; Bonney et al., 2009a; McCallie et al., 2009 "Degree to which participants are able to situate science concepts, theories, phenomena, and skills within broader social processes (includes analysis of the ethics and political aspects of science)" / "For Citizen Scientists: Are participants asked to consider the "big picture" implications of the research project and encouraged to discuss the political and ethical dimensions of the project or potential impacts that might emerge from the research?" / "For Professional Scientists/Staff: Are project leaders exposed to new ways of thinking about science in society? Are they willing to engage in conversation or debate about the ethical and political dimensions of the research project?"</p> <p>Lucero et al. 2018: Our partnership reflects on issues of power and privilege within our partnership [7-point scale: completely disagree - completely agree]</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Considerations/strategies of ethical issues and values in the design, development and implementation of activities: This includes issues/topic discussed (are there multiple interpretations/perspectives, are these contentious (and how is it moderated), are there resolutions/follow-ups?).</p>
28 (228)	<p>Does the project have explicit health and safety procedures in place?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Not applicable • I don't know 		<p>SDG 8.8 Protect labour rights and promote safe and secure working environments for all workers, including migrant workers, in particular women migrants, and those in precarious employment</p>
29 (229)	<p>Does the project have a risk management plan?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Risk in the context of project management rather than risk to the participants.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project have an appropriate risk management plan?</p>
30 (230)	<p>Have the organisations involved in the project increased their commitment to or investment in citizen science as a result of being involved in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, they have made a formal commitment • Yes, but not as a formal commitment • No • I don't know 		<p>Wehn et al. 2017: How much has your organization invested in CO-related activities in [year]?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
31 (231)	<p>Does the project lead to an increase in the commitment of organizations to public participation in decision making?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, they have made a formal commitment • Yes, but not as a formal commitment • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG: 16.7 Ensure responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making at all levels</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Commitments by institutions and organisations to public engagement: These may be embedded in organisational' structure (e.g. mission statements and goals or the types of projects/programmes they hold or plan). This input feature also includes the type as well as the number of commitments and its source (e.g. linked to funding commitments, political environment, social pressures, etc.).</p>
32 (232)	<p>Does the project help organisations to increase their capacity for public participation in decision making?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: For example, the project could provide training or resources to help give organisations concrete suggestions of how to include members of the public in their decision-making processes.</p>	<p>SDG 16.7 Ensure responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making at all levels</p>
33 (233)	<p>Are participants more actively involved in the political process as a result of taking part in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Haywood and Besley 2014: Do participants and project leaders exhibit changes in behaviours towards community action, political processes, or advocacy?</p> <p>Woods et al. 2020: Have you had any interactions with policy makers? e.g. visits from policy makers, writing a letter to your local council. Have you identified local policy problems the sensor data can help solve?</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project stimulate political participation?</p>
34 (234)	<p>Have the project's results or findings supported authorities in enforcing existing regulations, laws, or policies?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • Not yet • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Authorities could include Environmental Protection Agencies, Ministries for Health and the Environment, or other sectorial authorities that have the task to oversee compliance with existing laws. More resources on the topic can be found at https://sensingforjustice.webnode.it/.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: "Links to decision-making. Citizen science projects may include an intervention into the current state of affairs, such as local decision making. This might happen in activities that fall under banners such as participatory action research, community science, or addressing environmental injustice."</p> <p>Haywood and Besley, 2014: How successful is the project at influencing relevant policies or management practices? Are project results utilized for these purposes and if so, in what ways?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
35 (244)	<p>Have the results or findings of your citizen-science project been used as evidence in court (for example, for demonstrating environmental harm)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • Not yet • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Results and findings could include: raw data, visual and audio materials, analyses, maps built by the project and also testimonies of the citizen scientists engaged in the project.</p> <p>For an example of a case where citizen science evidence was used in court to demonstrate environmental harm, see https://cstrack.eu/format/reports/the-formosa-case-a-step-forward-on-the-acceptance-of-citizen-collected-evidence-in-environmental-litigation/.</p>	<p>Suman and Schade 2021: In June 2019, a landmark court decision (San Antonio Bay Estuarine Waterkeeper, et al. v. Formosa Plastics Corporation, et al., hereafter referred to as the Formosa ruling) was issued in Texas, where a judge found a petrochemical company liable for violating the United States Clean Water Act. The case—initiated by a civic group—was mostly built on citizen-collected evidence involving volunteer observations of plastic pellets, powder and flakes in the water over a considerable time span. The contamination could not be proven through existing data held by competent authorities because the company never filed any record of pollution (Formosa ruling, XI.A, p. 17).¹ In contrast to the majority of environmental pollution cases to date, the monitoring and data collection for this case was conducted by local residents who gathered a wealth of evidence of plastic pollution in water. Through a traditional case law and text analysis of the Formosa ruling, complemented by the analysis of surrounding communications, we explore why and how citizen-collected evidence was admitted and influenced the judge's ruling.</p>
36 (235)	<p>Which policy frameworks does the project consider?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisational frameworks • Local frameworks • Regional frameworks • National frameworks • Global frameworks • The project does not consider any policy frameworks • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> A policy framework is a document that sets out a set of procedures or goals which is used guide to guide the creation or ongoing maintenance of an organisation's policies. Explanations of the different scales of policy frameworks are outlined below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisational frameworks occur within an organisation such as Goldman Sachs Environmental Policy Framework; • Local frameworks occur within a county/municipality; • Regional frameworks influence policy over multiple counties/municipalities; • National frameworks such as the U.K. Environment Agency framework are significant for a country; • Global frameworks have influence throughout the world, such as the UNEP environmental, social and sustainability framework. 	<p>Wehn et al. 2017: National or sub-national policy related to the environmental problem in focus</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
37 (236)	<p>Does the project explicitly inform any governmental policy process?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, at the local level • Yes, at the regional level • Yes, at the national level • Yes, at the international level • No • I don't know 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: "Links to decision-making. Citizen science projects may include an intervention into the current state of affairs, such as local decision making. This might happen in activities that fall under banners such as participatory action research, community science, or addressing environmental injustice."</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Political participation "Does the project have any impact on political decisions?"</p> <p>Haywood and Besley, 2014: See above.</p> <p>Woods et al. 2016: Efforts by local government to reduce its negative impact on the environment (e.g., mandated use of low-emissions vehicles on government business, low-emissions or electric vehicles used for public transportation and garbage pickup)</p>
38 (237)	<p>Does the project have any explicit impact on external organisational policy?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: For example, Outfall Safari, a project monitoring urban water quality, has caused a change in the policies of Thames Water, the local water company.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: See above.</p> <p>Haywood and Besley, 2014: See above.</p> <p>Wiggins et al. 2018: Existence of decisions based on project data and findings (e.g., for policy or management)</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Informing environmental policies, agendas, management plans and government policies. Contributions to conventions, agendas, policies, and management plans</p>
39 (238)	<p>Is the project team aware of what the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: In 2015, the UN met and decided on the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) with a total of 169 targets. The SDGs aim to end poverty and hunger, encourage peace, protect the planet and foster partnership. Projects may be related to the SDGs by investigating a specific indicator for an SDG and reporting on this or by considering the SDGs in the planning stage.</p> <p>More information about the aims of the SDGs can be found at https://sdgs.un.org/ and a full list of the SDGs at https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/indicators/indicators-list/.</p>	<p>Fritz et al. 2019: Here we argue that data produced through 'citizen science', which is the involvement of citizens in scientific research or knowledge production, can complement and ultimately improve the SDG reporting process.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
		And now you've read this help text, you can tick yes to answer the question.	
40 (239)	<p>Is the project at all related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		Fritz et al. 2019 : See above.
41 (240)	<p>Which of the following Sustainable Development Goals is the project related to?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No Poverty 2. Zero Hunger 3. Good Health and Well-being 4. Quality Education 5. Gender Equality 6. Clean Water and Sanitation 7. Affordable and Clean Energy 8. Decent Work and Economic Growth 9. Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure 10. Reducing Inequality 11. Sustainable Cities and Communities 12. Responsible Consumption and Production 13. Climate Action 14. Life Below Water 15. Life On Land 16. Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions 17. Partnerships for the Goals 		Fritz et al. 2019 : See above.
42 (241)	<p>Does the project involve data which match a specific indicator of a Sustainable Development Goal?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		Fritz et al. 2019 : See above.
43 (243)	<p>Does the project contribute data to the official reporting for a Sustainable Development Goal indicator?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		SDG 17.18.1 "Proportion of sustainable development indicators produced at the national level with full disaggregation when relevant to the target, in accordance with the Fundamental Principles of Official Statistics."

4.5 Impact on science and technology

Citizen science enables various beneficial innovations and scientific advances.

The goal detailed in this section is the following:

- SDG 9 (industry, innovation, and infrastructure)

SDG 9 is a compound goal that citizen science potentially impacts heavily.

SDG 9: Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialisation and foster innovation.

Of the eight targets under SDG 9, the following two relate most to science and technology:

- 9.5: Enhance scientific research, upgrade the technological capabilities of industrial sectors in all countries, in particular developing countries, including, by 2030, encouraging innovation and substantially increasing the number of research and development workers per 1 million people and public and private research and development spending.
- 9.b: Support domestic technology development, research, and innovation in developing countries, including by ensuring a conducive policy environment for, inter alia, industrial diversification, and value addition to commodities.

One of the most heralded benefits of citizen science is its use in science and technology, especially in the public and NGO sectors. Citizen science has to be considered with its linkages to the sociotechnical systems in which it is deployed. Emphasis should be given to local development and the ownership of data. Aspects such as local benefits, data extraction by project coordinators, and structures related to data gathering and sharing should be considered.

The reason to focus on data to empower citizens is that the generation of and access to extensive datasets is what has driven recent progress in citizen science. Citizen-science innovation requires both infrastructure and universal, fair, and equal access to data to secure benefits for the citizens. However, even without this, citizen science might form the basis of new scientific discoveries and innovations that will positively influence all people and SDGs in the long run.

While equality and access to technology are essential, one might here, as with economic growth, also argue that science and technology are subject to cascades of benefits, or trickle-down innovation. Even if some people get the benefits first, some might argue that this will lead to a situation where these benefits gradually become available to all. While this might be problematic for SDGs such as 10, which concerns inequality, it might indeed lead to benefits related to, for example, SDG 6 and clean water and sanitation.

Scientific progress and technology are susceptible to citizen-science impacts, but the ripple effect from citizen-science—related impacts on SDG 9 on all other domains is arguably one of the most crucial contributions of citizen science. As mentioned in a previous section, this relates to the distinction between direct and indirect impacts, and shows that it is not possible to separate the impacts on different domains. The five domains are mainly used for the presentation of input features and results to the user of the platform, but all input features of all domains are processed together without distinction by the algorithm calculating the impact scores, so that these indirect impacts can be taken into account, and impacts are not counted twice. The input features related to science and technology are presented in the following table and constitute the basis for examining the overall impact of citizen science on this domain.

Table 4.e Science-and-technology—domain input features

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
1 (501)	<p>Which disciplines are the focus of the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen science (If you don't select this one, you are in trouble) • Agricultural and veterinary sciences (including forestry sciences, fisheries sciences, and land and farm management) • Art theory and criticism • Biological sciences (including ecology, zoology, genetics, and biodiversity) • Chemical sciences (including medicinal and biomolecular chemistry) • Earth sciences (including geology, atmospheric sciences, and oceanography) • Engineering (including food sciences, environmental engineering, and biomedical engineering) • Environmental sciences (including ecological applications, environmental management, and soil sciences) • Information and computing sciences (including artificial intelligence and image processing, distributed computing, and computer software) • Language, communication and culture (including linguistics, and literary studies) • Law and legal studies • Mathematical sciences and statistics • Medical and health sciences (including neurosciences, public health and health services, nutrition and dietetics, and human movement and sports science) • Philosophy and religious studies (including applied ethics, and history and philosophy of specific fields) • Physical sciences (including astronomical and space sciences, atomic, molecular, nuclear, particle and plasma physics, and quantum physics) • Psychology and cognitive sciences • Studies in human society (including human geography, history, archaeology, policy and administration, sociology, and education) • Technology (including communications technologies, and computer hardware) • None of the above • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> The list of disciplines used in this question is from the PPSR core citizen-science ontology.</p> <p>A discipline is an area which is studied in the project. The project may not be interested in the discipline of IT solely because an app or website is used or may not be investigating education simply because some learning is involved in the project for participants (these examples would not disqualify the project from investigating the mentioned disciplines but they are not enough alone to suggest that the project is interested in those areas).</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Science and research. Citizen science practices cross-disciplinary boundaries: some belong to fields widely acknowledged as scientific research, while others fall under the general term 'research', especially in the arts and humanities. Citizen science can describe many of these activities, especially when they comply with the <i>ten principles</i>. We use 'scientific research' to refer to research in the sciences, the social sciences, the humanities and the arts.</p> <p>Gresle et al. 2019: Transdisciplinary</p> <p>Pocock et al. 2019: Enhanced data collection, including coverage, resolution (spatial, temporal and taxonomic), accuracy and interdisciplinarity</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
2 (502)	<p>Does the project explicitly promote interdisciplinary ways of working?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: See above.</p> <p>Gresle et al. 2019: Transdisciplinary</p> <p>Pocock et al. 2019: Enhanced data collection, including coverage, resolution (spatial, temporal and taxonomic), accuracy and interdisciplinarity</p>
3 (503)	<p>Is the project's citizen science basic or applied?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic • Applied • Both • Too difficult to distinguish • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Basic science is research aimed at understanding fundamental problems. Examples of this include understanding how cells work, or biodiversity monitoring projects where participants collect data on which species are present.</p> <p>Applied science, such as in the medical field or in the game Quantum Moves where citizen scientists optimise solutions to quantum problems, is the application of basic scientific knowledge to solve practical problems.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: What counts as scientific research? In common with research practice in general, citizen science can address a topic that is basic or applied, inductive or deductive, local or global. In specific contexts, it is appropriate to identify a subset of activities (explicitly include environmental monitoring, or focus on hypothesis-driven research). To ensure rigour, the research should aim to follow protocols and practices in line with the disciplines within which the research is framed.</p>
4 (504)	<p>Is the purpose of the project's research to put existing theories to the test (deductive), or is it about gathering information and developing knowledge from this information (inductive)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inductive • Deductive • Both • Too difficult to distinguish • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Inductive reasoning is described as a method where one's experiences and observations are synthesised to come up with a general truth. Many dictionaries define inductive reasoning as deriving general principles from specific observations: "bottom-up logic". Deductive reasoning, or "top-down logic", is the process of reasoning from one or more hypotheses to reach a logical conclusion.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: See above.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
5 (505)	<p>Do participants take part in systematic or convenience data-collection?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic data-collection • Convenience data-collection • Both • Data collection is not a significant element of the project • I do not know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Convenience data-collection or sampling - also known as grab sampling, accidental sampling, or opportunistic sampling - is a type of non-probability sampling that involves the sample being drawn from that part of the population that is close to hand. This type of sampling is the most common in citizen science (for example, data collected by participants travelling to any green space to do a biodiversity study or water testing).</p> <p>Systematic sampling is a type of probability sampling where the sample is selected, at regular intervals, from a randomised list of the whole population (for example, data collected by participants going to a specific local green space to do a biodiversity study or water testing).</p> <p>An example of both may be a project where the locations sampled are based on convenience, but in each location the sampling frequency and location are systematic (for example, if a citizen-scientist chose a green space because it was close to their house, but for the biodiversity study, the green space was divided into sections and the sections sampled were chosen randomly in a systematic way).</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Opportunistic vs systematic data collection. Different scientific research projects can use and benefit from datasets with a wide variety of characteristics. For some analyses, a systematic and rigorously created dataset is necessary, while in others opportunistic or partial information is fit for purpose. Citizen science can contribute to both. The specific context, research aims and disciplinary practices of the project will determine where the activities fall on the spectrum of opportunistic to systematic data collection.</p>
6 (506)	<p>Does the project formally build on existing citizen-science expertise in the specific field of research?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • No, because this is the first citizen-science project in the specific field of research • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project build on existing citizen science expertise in the specific field of research?</p>
7 (507)	<p>Is new knowledge developed regarding how best to incorporate citizens into research design?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and formally documented • Yes, but not formally documented • No • I don't know 		<p>Haywood and Besley, 2014: Is new knowledge developed regarding how best to incorporate citizens into research design?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
8 (508)	<p>Does the project have or adopt a code of research or a research integrity policy available to participants? (See, for example, [https://ukrio.org/publications/code-of-practice-for-research/])</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>ECSA Characteristics: Ethics. The aims and intentions of citizen science projects and the research they involve should be communicated clearly and openly to participants and other stakeholders. If involvement is consensual and fully understood by participants, it may be considered citizen science. Special attention needs to be paid to transparency in community- or self-initiated projects that operate outside organisational ethical practices. In any case, all actors must adhere to a code of research integrity and quality issues when they participate in a research project.</p>
9 (509)	<p>Does the project have a formal dissemination strategy?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No - but it does have an informal dissemination strategy • No - the project does not have a dissemination strategy • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Unsure how dissemination differs from communication?</p> <p>- Communication means taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.</p> <p>- Dissemination is the public disclosure of the results of the project in any medium. It is a process of promotion and awareness-raising that makes research results known to various stakeholder groups in a targeted way, to enable them to use the results in their own work.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project demonstrate an appropriate dissemination strategy?</p>
10 (510)	<p>How many publications, indexed by Google Scholar, resulted from the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project has not produced any publications • Less than 3 • 3-30 • More than 30 • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> You can check the number of publications here: https://scholar.google.com/</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Data and knowledge generation. Citizen science, scientific, academic, and policy-oriented research can include different forms of data and knowledge generation, including novel data generation, creation of new analyses, or production of new knowledge in written and other forms. The knowledge produced in such projects should aspire to disciplinary standards, such as appropriate data quality and quality assurance, the peer review of project publications and materials, or policy-relevant evidence that is fit for decision-making.</p> <p>Wiggins et al. 2018: Number of published peer-reviewed scientific papers that report on the project or apply its data</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Peer-reviewed publications</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
11 (511)	<p>How many open-access publications, indexed by Google Scholar, resulted from the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project has not produced any open-access publications • Less than 3 • 3-30 • More than 30 • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> You can check the number of open access publications here: https://scholar.google.com/</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: See above.</p> <p>Wiggins et al. 2018: See above.</p>
12 (512)	<p>How many citations have the publications produced by the project received, in total (according to Google scholar)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 3 • 3-30 • 31-300 • More than 300 • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> You can check the number of citations here: https://scholar.google.com/</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: See above.</p> <p>Wiggins et al. 2018: See above.</p> <p>Bonney et al. 2009: # of papers published, # of citations</p>
13 (513)	<p>What is the highest impact-factor (or impact-index) of the publications produced by the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 2 • 2-5 • More than 5 • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Just Google: "[journal name]" impact factor</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: See above.</p> <p>Wiggins et al. 2018: See above.</p>
14 (514)	<p>How is the involvement of participants formally recognised in publications?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual authorship • Group pseudonym as (co-)author • Individuals acknowledged by name • Group of participants collectively acknowledged • Participants are not formally recognised in publications • I don't know 	<p><i>Information:</i> When the project does produce publications, you may wish to use a group pseudonym, such as "on behalf of the consortium", as Rambaut et al. did:</p> <p>https://virological.org/t/preliminary-genomic-characterisation-of-an-emergent-sars-cov-2-lineage-in-the-uk-defined-by-a-novel-set-of-spike-mutations/563</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Are citizen scientists participating in publications or is their engagement recognised?</p> <p>Cox et al. 2015: Total number of papers where the list of authors contains at least one citizen scientist author. The coauthorship of academic papers is a means by which well-functioning citizen science platforms can formally recognise the participation of volunteers and incentivise more valuable contributions.</p>
15 (515)	<p>Has the project supported students' dissertations or theses?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • It's in progress • No • I don't know 		<p>Wiggins et al. 2018: Number of theses and dissertations using data from or reporting on the project</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
16 (516)	<p>How many stakeholders have shown an active interest in the results of the project? (for example, downloaded results from the project website)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 3 • 3-30 • 31-300 • 301-3000 • More than 3000 • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> A stakeholder is anyone with interest in the project and may have been involved in the project or only be interested in the data or technology produced by the project. External stakeholders may include policy makers or businesses in the area the project affects.</p>	<p>Wiggins et al. 2018: Number of curated exports of data and related documentation, usually as a downloadable file</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Number of stakeholders who actively review / show interest in research results that have an impact on social justice, e.g. advisory board members, collaborators, external researchers, community leaders.</p>
17 (517)	<p>Does the project provide data visualisations such as graphs, maps and animations?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Wiggins et al. 2018: Existence of documentation describing data structure, formats, and contents</p>
18 (518)	<p>Are the project data used in models or forecasting?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Wiggins et al. 2018: Existence of models based on project data that simulate or predict complex phenomena</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
19 (519)	<p>What processes are defined in the project to guarantee high data-quality?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validated methodology - Carefully designed data collection methodology which is easy to carry out at a high level of accuracy. High-quality equipment - Equipment that has been rigorously tested to ensure that it provides high data-quality Training - Sufficient training provided to allow participants to collect data which has been tested to ensure participants reach the required skill level Data profiling - Initially assessing the data to understand their current state, often including value distributions Data standardization - Ensuring that data conform to standards Data monitoring - Keeping track of data quality over time and reporting variations in the quality of data Peer-to-peer validation - More-expert participants validating observations by less-expert participants Expert validation – Professionals validating observations by participants Automated strategies: Matching or linking - A way to compare data so that similar but slightly different records can be aligned Automated strategies: Artificial intelligence - For example, improving image or audio classification by using computer vision or computer hearing None of the above I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Matching may use "fuzzy logic" to find duplicates in the data; it can for example recognise that "Sasha Wood" and "Sasha Woods" may be the same individual.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Data quality. Citizen science raises questions about data quality, which can be addressed in a range of ways, such as well-developed protocols, good design of the task to fit the purpose, and good participant support. Similar to research activities generally, data quality is a key aspect that warrants attention throughout the entire process of knowledge production.</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: What processes are defined to guarantee high data quality?</p> <p>Haywood and Besley, 2014: Are efforts made to ensure that the quality standards of all participants are upheld?</p>
20 (520)	<p>Are project data available through APIs?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> An application programming interface (API) is a connection between computers or between computer programs. It is a type of software interface, offering a service to other pieces of software.</p>	<p>Wiggins et al. 2018: API: Y/N</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
21 (521)	<p>What technology does the project use a pre-existing version of?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apps • Sensors • Artificial intelligence • Platforms (a range of services available on the Internet including marketplaces, search engines and social media) • Digital solutions (digitalising old methodologies, processes or technology: e.g. Trello is a project management solution; Slack is a communication solution) • Websites • The project does not use technology • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: "Wider innovation potential: Does the project foster the use of new technologies? Does the project contribute to the development of new technologies?"</p>
22 (539)	<p>What technology does the project develop?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apps • Sensors • Artificial intelligence • Platforms (a range of services available on the Internet including marketplaces, search engines and social media) • Digital solutions (digitalising old methodologies, processes or technology: e.g. Trello is a project management solution; Slack is a communication solution) • Websites • The project does not develop technology • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Development can include new versions of existing technology.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: "Wider innovation potential: Does the project foster the use of new technologies? Does the project contribute to the development of new technologies?"</p>
23 (522)	<p>Does the project explicitly develop, transfer or disseminate information about environmentally-sound technologies?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Environmentally sound technologies are techniques and technologies capable of reducing environmental damage through processes and materials that generate fewer potentially damaging substances, recover such substances from emissions prior to discharge, or utilize and recycle production residues.</p>	<p>SDG 17.7 Promote the development, transfer, dissemination and diffusion of environmentally sound technologies to developing countries on favourable terms, including on concessional and preferential terms, as mutually agreed</p>
24 (523)	<p>Does the project use mobile phones as a primary tool (for example, using an app to collect observations)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG 5.b.1 Proportion of individuals who own a mobile telephone, by sex</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Equipment required for participation, Infrastructure required for participation</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
25 (524)	<p>Is participation possible without a phone connected to the internet?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes; participation is possible without a phone or a computer connected to the internet. • Yes; participation is possible without a phone, but a computer connected to the internet is necessary. • No; it's nearly impossible • I don't know 		<p>Wehn et al. 2017: Equipment required for participation, Infrastructure required for participation</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Considerations/strategies of ethical issues and values in the design, development and implementation of activities: This includes a tally of existing and development of strategies for the use of technologies/methodologies (are these affordable/accessible to the participating population)</p>
26 (525)	<p>Does the project provide technical support to participants?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Technical support provides help regarding specific problems with a product or service, rather than providing training or other support services</p>	<p>SDG 4.4: By 2030, substantially increase the number of youth and adults who have relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Type of material support provided for participants (e.g. manuals, instructions, training, sensor devices, etc.). Digital divide: With the digital age, another source of (in)equity has emerged. As internet savviness has become important to sustain oneself, the gap between people that do know their way around the computer and internet and those who do not has become another societal divider.</p>
27 (526)	<p>Does the project use enabling technology, in particular information and communications technology, to promote the empowerment of women?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: One way in which a project could use technology to promote the empowerment of women is by using social media to reach a wider audience. This may allow women to overcome structural barriers which would usually prevent them from being able to take part in projects. You can read examples in this blog.</p>	<p>SDG 5.b: Enhance the use of enabling technology, in particular information and communications technology, to promote the empowerment of women</p> <p>DITOs Consortium 2016: # & type of events discussing gender dimension in science & technology; % of women sharing feedback</p>
28 (527)	<p>Does the project enhance international cooperation on science, technology or innovation?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>SDG 17.6: Enhance North-South, South-South and triangular regional and international cooperation on and access to science, technology and innovation and enhance knowledge sharing on mutually agreed terms, including through improved coordination among existing mechanisms, in particular at the United Nations level, and through a global technology facilitation mechanism</p> <p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project collaborate with other initiatives at the (inter-) national level to enhance mutual learning?</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: How many international clients does your organization have in the CO business?</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
29 (528)	<p>Does the project provide participants with easy and explicit access to pertinent research findings or important literature used to inform the project (i.e. not produced by the project itself) before participants begin their research activities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Haywood and Besley, 2014: Are citizen participants able to access pertinent research findings, salient literature, or project information used to inform the project before research begins?</p>
30 (529)	<p>Are participants exposed to steps in the scientific process in a systematic manner?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, mostly • Yes, partially • No, it has not been considered • No, it would not be appropriate for this project • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> There are many ways in which participants could be exposed to steps in the scientific process in a systematic manner. For example, they may be presented with the problem before they are presented with the method or they could be exposed to the results before they are given the conclusion.</p>	<p>Haywood and Besley, 2014: Are participants exposed to steps in the scientific process in a systematic manner and are they allowed to practice research skills in an integrated fashion?</p>
31 (530)	<p>Are participants explicitly encouraged to reflect on or discuss current values, perspectives, opinions and attitudes relating to science concepts?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 		<p>Haywood and Besley, 2014: Are participants encouraged to reflect on and discuss current VPOA [Values, Perspectives, Opinions, and Attitudes] relating to general science concepts and the research project?</p> <p>Smajgl et al. 2015: The learning-focused ChaRL framework measured and facilitated changes in existing beliefs, by tracing the fate of new knowledge introduced by a specific research process and capturing attendant changes in value and belief orientations.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
531	<p>Does participation in the project increase participants' scientific literacy?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Scientific literacy is the knowledge and understanding of scientific concepts and processes required for personal decision-making, participation in civic and cultural affairs, and economic productivity.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project contribute to a better understanding of science?</p> <p>Haywood and Besley, 2014: Are participants able to interact with novel concepts, theories, and phenomena to expand their understanding of science and relate knowledge to their personal lives?</p> <p>Bonney et al. 2009: Improved participant understanding of science content. Enhanced participant understanding of the science process.</p> <p>Phillips et al. 2018: Our new framework is thus based on both empirical data and contributions from the literature and includes the following learning outcomes: Interest in Science and the Environment; Self-efficacy for Science and the Environment; Motivation for Science and the Environment; Knowledge of the Nature of Science; Skills of Science Inquiry; and Behavior and Stewardship.</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Understanding of science: We base this directly on EC (2015) classical indicators for public understanding of science "knowledge of science in terms of textbook facts, methodological processes and awareness of and beliefs about institutional functioning" and it applied to both facilitators and participants. However, they also note that "knowledge is not a driver of positive attitudes but a cognitive component of public perceptions".</p>
532	<p>Does the project positively influence the attitudes of participants regarding science?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the project influence the values and attitudes of participants regarding science?</p> <p>Bonney et al. 2009: Better participant attitudes toward science</p> <p>Phillips et al. 2018: See above.</p> <p>DITOs consortium 2016: Attitude towards science: includes the perception of science in broader terms (e.g. social gains from science and technology - medicine, environmental protection, etc.), and relevance of science to daily lives.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
533	<p>Does the project increase the interest of participants in the topic of the research?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Phillips et al. 2018: See above.</p> <p>Chase and Levine 2016: Social and cultural characteristics of a resource - resource perceived as charismatic or ecologically significant. Because citizen science programs draw upon the public for natural resource monitoring, social and cultural characteristics of the resource are an important consideration in program approaches and outcomes. These characteristics reflect the diverse ways that communities and individuals interact with the resource, causing the resource to become socially or culturally significant.</p>
534	<p>Are participants explicitly exposed to various careers in science through the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Example careers in science include: academic careers such as lecturers; laboratory careers such as researchers or lab managers; data analysts, such as bioinformaticians; or science communicators, including editors.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: In the case of younger students, do they consider a scientific career?</p> <p>Haywood and Besley, 2014: Are participants exposed to various careers in science and able to analyze the contributions of those careers to society?</p>
535	<p>Are participants more likely to consider a scientific career having participated in the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, and it has been measured • Yes, but it has not been measured • No • I don't know 		<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: See above.</p> <p>Bonney et al. 2009: Increased participant interest in science as a career</p>
536	<p>Does the project link participants to experts (often researchers)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: Links between participants and experts may occur to validate data, provide data analysis, or discuss the conclusions arising from the results.</p>	<p>Kieslinger et al. 2017: Does the validation of citizen science data match with the scientific question and the expertise in the project? Does the project link to experts from other disciplines?</p>
537	<p>Are participants able to challenge the project's methodologies?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, at any time during the project, and this could result in methodologies changing • Yes, but only during a pilot / testing phase, and this could result in methodologies changing • Yes, but this could not result in methodologies changing • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help</i>: A methodology is a system of methods used in a particular area of study. This could include interviewing participants, sending out surveys or how data is analysed.</p> <p>Methodologies may not be changed in a project because, for example, data need to be compared with existing datasets, for continuity of research, or because some SDG indicator is determining the parameters to measure, even if they don't necessarily make sense in a particular location.</p>	<p>Lucero et al. 2018: Power relations: How much do you agree or disagree that community members...[7 point scale: completely disagree - completely agree]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - have increased participation in the research process - can voice their opinions about research in front of researchers

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
538	<p>Are professionals involved in organising the project (coordinators or researchers, for example) challenged to consider novel connections between their own careers and research, and the context of participating citizens?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Project coordinators and researchers involved in citizen science often have to consider the context of participating citizens. This may challenge them to reconsider their own career or research for example if parameters which they thought were important aren't of interest to participants or if participants are passionate about an issue which they hadn't considered before.</p>	<p>Haywood and Besley, 2014: Are project leaders challenged to consider novel connections between their own careers and research and those of citizen participants?</p> <p>Gresle et al. 2019: community alignment (alignment of project goals to the community demands and efficacy of engagement techniques) and responsiveness to community alignment.</p>

4.6 General descriptors

Not all the input features used in MICS are related to the impact of citizen science on some specific domain. To get to grips with both the short-term and long-term comprehensive impacts of citizen science, it is necessary to consider general descriptors of citizen-science projects. These descriptors help define the context of the project in question. The citizen-science projects examined by MICS are regarded as part of the socioeconomic system and not considered in isolation. Therefore the platform includes questions on institutions, structures, funding and governance systems. These elements are all mutually dependent; each of the parts impacts the other factors, and they all enable, restrict, and shape the development and use of citizen science. And citizen science, in turn, affects the different parts of the system.

The input features related to the general description of a project are presented in the following table and constitute the basis for examining the overall context of the impact of citizen science.

Table 4.f General input features

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
1 (001)	<p>What forms of knowledge does the project as a whole create?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New data (quantitative or qualitative) • New analyses (including existing approaches applied to new data) • New methodologies (e.g. for data collection, participant engagement, education) • New concepts or theories • None of the above • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> New concepts or theories: for example, in MICS we are working on a new way to theorise impact assessment which is different to the "theory of change".</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Data and knowledge generation. Citizen science, scientific, academic, and policy-oriented research can include different forms of data and knowledge generation, including novel data generation, creation of new analyses, or production of new knowledge in written and other forms. The knowledge produced in such projects should aspire to disciplinary standards, such as appropriate data quality and quality assurance, the peer review of project publications and materials, or policy-relevant evidence that is fit for decision-making.</p>
2 (004)	<p>What is the expected duration of the project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 1 year • 1-2 years • 3-4 years • 5 years or more • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Duration refers to all stages of the project life cycle, not just the data collection phase.</p>	<p>Cox et al. 2015: For many measures of project outcomes, we report rates of activity over time as opposed to raw numbers; both in terms of the active project duration (the length of time that the project has actively accepted new classifications) and project age (the length of time between the start of the project and October 2014, which may include periods of inactivity). These are used as appropriate depending on whether the particular performance measure can only occur whilst the project is active (e.g. classification activity) or after the project has finished accepting new classifications (e.g. publications).</p>
3 (005)	<p>Are participants currently able to contribute to the project's citizen-science activities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Projects use many words to describe the people who take part in their activities: citizen scientists, volunteers, stakeholders, amateurs, community members, human sensors.</p> <p>In MICS we just use the word participants.</p>	<p>Cox et al. 2015: For many measures of project outcomes, we report rates of activity over time as opposed to raw numbers; both in terms of the active project duration (the length of time that the project has actively accepted new classifications) and project age (the length of time between the start of the project and October 2014, which may include periods of inactivity). These are used as appropriate depending on whether the particular performance measure can only occur whilst the project is active (e.g. classification activity) or after the project has finished accepting new classifications (e.g. publications).</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
4 (008)	<p>How many observations have been collected so far?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • 30,001-300,000 • More than 300,000 • I have no idea about how many observations have been collected • I don't really know what observations are • Observations are not a significant element of the project and quantifying them is not important 	<p><i>Help:</i> What counts as an observation? That's up to the project to decide. Some projects count every item of data they collect. Some projects count each dataset uploaded if, for example, a single sample taken includes several data points. Some projects count the number of classifications made because their activities involve data analysis rather than data collection. Just choose whatever makes the most sense in the context of the project.</p>	<p>Wiggins et al. 2018: Data Specimens/samples (#) Number of material data points in the form of physical specimens or samples</p> <p>Bonney et al. 2009: Size and quality of citizen science databases</p>
5 (009)	<p>How many observations are collected in a typical recent year of active project? (If the project has been running for less than a year, you can estimate the number).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • 30,001-300,000 • More than 300,000 • Too difficult to estimate 	<p><i>Information:</i> To put the project's data collection in perspective, just think that eBird collected 700 000 000 observations and iNaturalist 40 000 000. But that doesn't mean that you have less than 1% of the impact of these projects. Context is important and that's why we need to ask so many questions.</p>	<p>Wiggins et al. 2018: Data Specimens/samples (#) Number of material data points in the form of physical specimens or samples</p> <p>Bonney et al. 2009: Size and quality of citizen science databases</p>
6 (010)	<p>What is the scope of the citizen science project? (The project, for example, studies plastic pollution worldwide.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National • Multinational • Global • Galactic • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Global projects can have participants anywhere in the world; multinational projects have participants in a limited number of countries across the world.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: What counts as scientific research? In common with research practice in general, citizen science can address a topic that is basic or applied, inductive or deductive, local or global. In specific contexts, it is appropriate to identify a subset of activities (explicitly include environmental monitoring, or focus on hypothesis-driven research). To ensure rigour, the research should aim to follow protocols and practices in line with the disciplines within which the research is framed.</p> <p>Chase and Levine 2016: Geographic scale</p> <p>Wehn et al. 2017: Geographic scope of the issue in focus</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
7 (013)	<p>How many participants have contributed to the project's citizen science activities so far?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-30 • 31-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • More than 30,000 • Too difficult to estimate • Participants are not a significant element of the project and quantifying them is not important 	<p><i>Help:</i> Citizen science activities can be broader than just data collection, and may include, for example, training other participants or sharing project outputs.</p>	<p>ECSA Characteristics: Small scale vs large scale. Citizen science projects can include a single person carrying out a research project and publicly sharing their knowledge on a non-traditional platform (e.g. a blog) while adhering to scientific standards (e.g. peer review). It can also consist of a small group of participants, or be open to large-scale participation in various phases of the research process. Projects may aim to achieve large-scale participation, or to contribute significantly to knowledge through personal effort, depending on the context and the discipline. Depending on the aim of the project, all scales could be considered citizen science.</p> <p>Cox et al. 2015: $\text{Project Appeal Number of volunteers} / (\text{Project active period})^2$; Total number of volunteers who have contributed to the project divided by project active-period squared.</p> <p>Chandler et al. 2017: Number of participants; Continuous; Number of participants / project per year; The number of people participating in the project each year.</p>
8 (014)	<p>How many participants contribute to citizen science activities in a typical year of active project? (If the project has been running for less than a year, you can estimate the number).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-30 • 31-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • More than 30,000 • Too difficult to estimate 	<p><i>Information:</i> Many citizen science projects have a "long tail" of participation, where a small minority of citizen scientists make the majority of contributions to the project (Wald, Longo, and Dobell, 2016). If the same is true in this project, 10% of the participants would collect x% of observations whilst y% of observations would be collected by the remaining 90% of participants.</p> <p>Wald, Longo, and Dobell, 2016 reference: https://conbio.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/cobi.12627</p>	<p>Chandler et al. 2017: See above.</p>
9 (015)	<p>How many people have been directly engaged by the project (including participants who have contributed to the citizen science activities)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • 30,001-300,000 • More than 300,000 • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> People can be engaged with a project in ways other than taking part in citizen science activities. For example, they might attend a project event or subscribe to the project newsletter.</p>	<p>Jackson et al. 2016: Active, less active, and passive participants: A number of prior studies divided participants into active members who contribute the majority of work, less active participants, and passive members who take advantage of the benefits offered without contributing themselves to community activities.</p>

#	Question text and answer options	Help and information	Source of question and original wording
10 (018)	<p>What is the total external funding received by the project? (in €, £ GBP, or \$ USD)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • 30,001-300,000 • 300,001-3,000,000 • More than 3,000,000 • The project did not receive external funding • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> External funding is money that comes from outside the organisation(s) managing the project.</p> <p>In this question, we use €, £ GBP, or \$ USD interchangeably because the answers are given as orders of magnitude which make the difference in the exchange rate between the three currencies largely irrelevant. Here's a currency converter in case it's helpful: https://www1.oanda.com/currency/converter/</p>	<p>Wehn et al. 2017: How many revenue streams does your organisation have for CO-related value propositions?</p> <p>Bonney et al. 2009: Numbers and sizes of grants received for citizen science research</p>
11 (021)	<p>What is the total financial investment in the project including internal funding? (in €, £ GBP, or \$ USD)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0-300 • 301-3000 • 3001-30,000 • 30,001-300,000 • 300,001-3,000,000 • More than 3,000,000 • The project did not use internal funding • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Total financial investment is money that comes both externally and internally from the organisation(s) managing the project</p> <p>In this question, we use €, £ GBP, or \$ USD interchangeably because the answers are given as orders of magnitude which make the difference in the exchange rate between the three currencies largely irrelevant. Here's a currency converter in case it's helpful: https://www1.oanda.com/currency/converter/</p>	<p>Wehn et al. 2017: In total, what is your organization's budget (income and own investment) in these CO-related research projects?</p>
12 (022)	<p>Is the project focused on one or more of the following five domains?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Society • Governance • Economy • Science and technology • Environment • None of the above • I don't know 	<p><i>Help:</i> Society: individuals as well as collective (societal) values, understanding, actions and well-being (including relationships)</p> <p>Governance: the processes and institutions through which decisions are made, both informal and formal</p> <p>Economy: the production and exchange of goods and services among economic agents</p> <p>Science and technology: the scientific process (method) as well as research more broadly; the scientific system, scientific paradigms and resulting technological artefacts and standards</p> <p>Environment: the bio-chemical-physical environment</p>	<p>Wehn et al. 2020: While the three domains of sustainable development (environment, society and economy) are well-known and accepted, the context of citizen science warrants the focus on the two additional domains (science and technology, and governance). The science and technology domain is considered by MICS due to the inherent nature of citizen science's alignment with/use of the scientific process and resulting (potential) implications for the scientific system, scientific paradigms and technological artefacts. A separate governance domain is considered owing to the links of citizen-science processes and results in monitoring, (environmental) management and (public) decision-making processes.</p>

4.7 AI

A comprehensive assessment of the impact of citizen science requires considering hundreds of input features (see section 3.1). And the analysis of hundreds of input features requires sophisticated techniques. MICS rethinks impact assessment in citizen science from the bottom up and puts technology and data at the service of people. In MICS, data produced by the users of the platform belong to the users. MICS believes data should be considered a public good. AI, particularly machine-learning algorithms, now helps make decisions on many issues, including impact assessment. But important decisions are often happening in the dark. Programs are often unaccountable. To arrive at their choices, machine-learning algorithms automatically build complex models based on some data sets used as input for learning, so that even the people using them may not be able to explain why or how a conclusion is reached. They are a black box.

Some software owners often claim that increasing transparency could risk revealing their intellectual property. This is not the case in MICS, where all software is open source. But being open-source is not the most critical feature for many. It might not be necessary at all. If a project has a low positive impact, the project participants do not necessarily care so much about how the algorithm works. They want to know why the impact is low and have some guidance on how to improve. So, the project implemented Alquimics, a new impact-assessment feature using machine learning and a rule-based engine in MICS's open-source web application. And Alquimics includes personalised recommendations on how to improve impact. Alquimics is a significant step forward in transparency and accountability on the intersection between citizen science and AI.

However, transparency in the impact-assessment process is only one side of the coin of accountability. It gives some idea about why a decision has been made in a particular way, but it does not mean the decision is justified or legitimate. That justification and legitimisation is provided by the methodology presented in section 2. One problem, sometimes, is a lack of transparency around what data are being used to train impact-assessment algorithms in the first place. In many cases, algorithms are building assumptions about citizens and their activities based on variables they are unaware of. Organisations should be required to demonstrate that the data points they use to measure impact or make other decisions are relevant and lead to accurate predictions.

Under GDPR, the European data protection regulations implemented in 2018, everyone in the European Union has the right to access and amend any data an organisation holds about them. We also have the right to be forgotten. In MICS, the same applies to project data. As well as access to project data, project coordinators can ask for and correct any assumptions MICS has made about their projects based on whatever content has been collected. This is the logical counterpart to the right to be forgotten. Project participants also have a right on if and how their project is seen.

As mentioned earlier, Alquimics is the algorithm behind the MICS platform. It has been created through part handcrafting (a labour-intensive technique for programming that involves writing explicit rules and templates) and part machine learning (a type of AI that learns to perform a task by analysing patterns in data). From the start, the team has faced a defining question: Which parts of the platform's brain should be handcrafted and which should employ machine learning? Handcrafting is the more traditional approach, in which scientists painstakingly write extensive sets of rules to guide AI's understanding and assessments. Statistically-driven machine-learning systems, by contrast, have the computer teach itself to assess impact by learning from data. Machine learning is a superior method for tackling so-called classification problems, in which neural networks find unifying patterns in noisy data. But machine learning has a long way to go when it comes to translating input features

characterising citizen-science projects into impact assessment. And the team, like the tech world at large, struggled to find the best balance between the two approaches.

To help Alquimics automatically generate impact assessments, the team had only nine complete sets of instances of about 200 input features at its disposal. So the MICS team wrote extensive assessment-guiding rules. The team created five "impact domains": environment, economy, governance, science, and society. The MICS system has been engineered to know the five domains' core elements. And the team divided the platform's brain into a committee of smaller rule-based algorithms, each with a speciality of its own.

In addition, a machine-learning approach (a neural network) has been developed. It is especially tough for a machine-learning system to assess impact, because there usually is not a verifiably correct way to evaluate impact. Neural networks work best when there is a clear goal, like winning at the game of Go, that the system can find the optimal strategy to reach through trial and error on a massive scale. Impact assessment has no well-defined goal. In the rule-based system, the MICS team started guessing how much to weigh each input feature. With the help of the evaluation by the neural network, weights will be adjusted so that the two sides of the algorithm (rule-based and machine-learning—based) will stay aligned, in a middle-of-the-road approach to mixing rules-based programming and machine learning into the system.

In summary, the edge of the MICS platform with respect to existing systems is the most extensive (to date) set of input features used (features **and values**), and an interface and an interaction that people will (we hope) enjoy. The system not only asks questions about input features but provides interesting, conversational feedback, so the users can learn more about their projects and how to improve them to achieve a more substantial impact.

4.8 Citizen science and AI ethics

Any analysis of the impacts of citizen science using AI is connected to the discipline of AI ethics, which is, as the name implies, concerned with the study of the ethical implications of AI (Coeckelbergh, 2020; Bostrom and Yudkowsky, 2018). Citizen science is, after all, intrinsically related to deeply ethical questions. And AI ethics provides a fertile ground for examining how AI impacts citizen-science assessments. Some issues that have garnered much attention from the AI ethics community are related to how AI impacts privacy (Sætra, 2019, 2020; Solove, 2000). Furthermore, a key focus area is the nature of bias in AI systems (Buolamwini and Gebru, 2018; Noble, 2018). One fundamental notion related to the ethics of AI is that technology (including AI) impacts the distribution and exertion of power (Culpepper and Thelen, 2020; Gillespie, 2010; Sattarov, 2019). As AI is part of larger sociotechnical systems, the issues related to the data (mainly access to, ownership, and use) are central for understanding some of AI's essential citizen-science-related impacts.

It is then essential to ensure that AI algorithms in citizen science are created and applied with a robust ethical code of conduct, and MICS will remain vigilant in avoiding causing harm to people or places. Already the CARE (collective benefit, authority to control, responsibility, ethics) and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles for data give important social considerations for ethical data governance (Carroll et al., 2021). Existing frameworks, such as the CARE principles, could be drawn upon to identify needs for mitigating issues that may arise as AI is more readily integrated into MICS, as a project aiming to explore science relating to people, to biodiversity, and to broader environmental challenges.

4.9 Indicators and recommendations

Specific sets of input features on the same theme are combined into indicators. Impact scores for indicators - out of 42 - are calculated based on a set of rules which implement these combinations. A higher score means the project is carrying out more positive changes related to the theme of the indicator and is, therefore, more likely to have a higher positive impact in this area.

Each indicator is calculated by summing the weights of the answer options selected, and recommendations are provided depending on the weighting (see following tables). Details about each indicator, including their formula and recommendation score threshold, are included below.

4.9.1 Economy indicators

4.9.1.1 Economic productivity

Definition: Economic productivity measures output per unit of input, such as labour, capital, or any other resource.

Why we use it: Economic productivity relates to **SDG 8.2 “Diversify, innovate and upgrade for economic productivity”**: Achieve higher levels of economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading and innovation, including through a focus on high-value added and labour-intensive sectors.

Table 7 Indicator formula for "Economic productivity"

Question number	Question text	Answers	Weights
Economy 16	Does the project explicitly improve economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading or innovation?	Yes; the project doubled the GDP of a country	420*
		Yes; but it wasn't as successful as that!	42
		No	0
		I don't know	21

* This is a humorous note. The MICS team will work to include lighter elements into the platform without compromising its scientific rigour. So, this is an initial experiment in this sense.

Table 8 Recommendation score thresholds for "Economic productivity"

Recommendations	Lower score	Higher score
Well done! Can you give us a loan to improve MICS further?	420	420
It is great that the project has produced outputs that contribute to the economy through industry, commerce, innovation or technological development. If you haven't already, it might be worth considering any legal implications through a dedicated IPR plan	42	42
We know that economic productivity isn't a priority for most citizen-science projects. If you are interested in improving the economic productivity of the project, it might help to fully appraise any potential developments and advances made through the creation of a dedicated IPR plan . This will help reveal any economic potential that might have been overlooked, and support its exploitation.	0	21

4.9.1.2 Financial sustainability

Definition: Financial sustainability is the assessment that a project will have sufficient funds to meet all its resource and financial obligations when the initial funding ends.

Why we use it: Citizen science is frequently hailed as an inexpensive alternative to traditional science. [Palmer et al.](#) note, “with its relatively low cost centred on non-recurring investments, citizen science is inherently more scalable than traditional tools”. But financial sustainability is more than simply using

inexpensive equipment; it is also about planning to exploit outputs, for example - which is why this indicator is a little broader than Palmer’s original definition.

Table 9 Indicator formula for “Financial sustainability”

Question number	Question text	Answers	Weights
Economy 15	Does the project have explicit plans to sustain its activities after the current funding received has ended?	Yes	11
		No	0
		I don't know.	5
Economy 12	Does the project have an explicit exploitation plan?	Yes	10
		No	0
		I don't know.	5
Economy 24	Does the project require recurring investments in technology (for example, software licences or app/platform maintenance) that affect its long-term sustainability?	Yes	0
		No	11
		I don't know.	5
Economy 25	What is the estimated, approximate cost per observation (in £, € or \$) (observations as defined by the project)?	Observations are not a significant element of the project and quantifying their cost is not important.	10
		Less than 2 (Just for comparison, this is the income per day of one seventh of the world population.)	10
		2-8 (Just for comparison, this is the income per day of three sevenths of the world population.)	6
		9-32 (Just for curiosity, this is the income per day of two sevenths of the world population.)	4
		More than 32 (Just for curiosity, this is the income per day of one seventh of the world population.)	2
		I don't know	5

Table 10 Recommendation score thresholds for “Financial sustainability”

Recommendations	Lower score	Higher score
If the project wants to improve its financial sustainability, it could consider creating an exploitation plan . To reduce recurring investments in technology and the cost per observation, the project could consider using open-source software and tools.	0	9
Well done! The project has a high score due to forward thinking in creating an exploitation plan, planning sustainability activities to prolong the project's influence and fully appraising any recurring costs and maintenance.	33	42
You are on the right path! It is clear that the project has considered its financial sustainability into the future. However, there could be more to do. If one does not already exist, an exploitation plan could help sustain project outputs, whilst considering open-source software and tools could reduce costs.	10	32

4.9.2 Society indicators

4.9.2.1 Activeness

Definition: Activeness is the level of cognitive engagement, where “active” indicates that the participant requires full cognitive attention during participation, and “passive” suggests there is no engagement beyond setup.

Why we use it: Activeness is included in the [ECSA characteristics of citizen science](#) and explained in the explanatory notes of that document: “Participants need to be aware of the contribution and participate actively and intentionally, as this is necessary for cases where the information that participants produced is not directly used by the project, but only as a secondary use of data (e.g.

reusing images that people share on a social networking site). We recommend transparency about roles and expectations [...]. it is highly recommended to be open and transparent about choices that were made about the roles of participants. The project owner has responsibility for communicating that the participants are contributing to research.”

Activeness is further discussed in the associated peer-reviewed publication, “[Contours of citizen science: a vignette study](#)”.

Table 11 Indicator formula for “Activeness”

Question number	Question text	Answers	Weights
Society 4	How much responsibility is offered to the participants? (with options depending on interests, availability and knowledge).	Not much	0
		Something in the middle	8
		A lot	16
		I don't know	4
Society 8	Are the participants satisfied with the process of participation in the project?	Yes, and it has been measured	12
		Yes, but it has not been measured	10
		No	0
		I don't know	4
Society 12	Are participants aware they are contributing to a research project?	Yes	14
		No	0
		I don't know	4

Table 12 Recommendation score thresholds for “Activeness”

Recommendations	Lower score	Higher score
The activeness of participants within a project is an important aspect of citizen science. Efforts should be made to make participants aware they are contributing to a research project through clear communication channels, and to offer them the opportunity to be responsible for their activities. If the project has not measured participants' degree of satisfaction in the process, it might want to consider to consider investigating this further using this paper as a starting point.	0	12
The activeness of participants within a project is an important aspect of citizen science. Activeness depends on participants being aware that they are contributing to a project, having a lot of responsibility in the project, and being satisfied with the process of participation. This project should ensure that all aspects of activeness have been considered.	13	33
The activeness of participants within a project is an important aspect of citizen science, and this project has made great efforts to ensure participants are aware they are contributing to a research project, have responsibility in the project, and are satisfied with the process of participation. Great job!	34	42

4.9.2.2 Involvement

Definition: Involvement is the degree of participation in different stages of a process.

Why we use it: Involvement is included in the [ECSA characteristics of citizen science](#): “Research involving citizen science can take many forms, and the roles of the participants can include, for example: identifying a research question, collecting or analysing data to support or refute a hypothesis; monitoring environmental or health conditions for management or policy outcomes; and creation of generic data within a domain to support a wide range of research questions.”

Involvement is further discussed in the associated peer-reviewed publication, “[Contours of citizen science: a vignette study](#)”, as well as Kieslinger’s paper “ [The Challenge of Evaluation: An Open Framework for Evaluating Citizen Science Activities](#)”.

Table 13 Indicator formula for "Involvement"

Question number	Question text	Answers	Weights
Society 1	In which phases of the project do participants play a role?	Background research	2
		Identifying a research question	2
		Grant proposal writing	2
		Project initiation	1
		Definition of project activities	1
		Design and development of technology and equipment for the project	1
		Collecting data	1
		Analysing data	1
		Monitoring in ways other than collecting data	1
		Passive participation (for example, contributing computer resources or social media information which is harvested by the project)	0
		Recruiting or engaging other participants	1
		Training other participants	1
		Sharing of outputs (including publications and arranging project events)	1
		Assessment of project impacts	1
		Acting on the results of the project	1
Closure or handover of the project	1		
I don't know	0		
Society 2	Are participants offered multiple project activities which they can take part in?	Yes	13
		No; participants only have one activity they can take part in	0
		I don't know	4
Society 3	Are participants offered different levels of involvement in each project activity depending on their interest, availability and knowledge?	Yes	13
		No	0
		I don't know	4

Table 14 Recommendation score thresholds for "Involvement"

Recommendations	Lower score	Higher score
Participants can contribute to many more phases of a project than collecting or analysing data. Think about other phases of the project participants could be involved with in the future, such as sharing the outputs or assessing impact. Remember that different participants will have different interests, knowledge and availability, so try to offer them different levels of involvement and multiple project activities to take part in.	0	10
The degree of involvement of participants in a project is an important aspect of citizen science, and includes involving participants in multiple stages of the project, offering them multiple activities to take part in, and offering different levels of involvement depending on individual interests and availability. This project could consider whether there are more stages of the project that participants could be involved in for example by considering co-design or co-evaluation .	11	29
The degree of involvement of participants in a project is an important aspect of citizen science, and this project goes to great lengths to ensure that participants are involved in multiple stages of the project. It is positive that participants are offered multiple project activities to take part in, and that they are offered different levels of involvement depending on their individual interests and availability. Good work!	30	42

4.9.3 Environment

4.9.3.1 Environmental footprint

Definition: The environmental (or ecological) footprint measures how fast we consume resources and generate waste compared to how fast nature can absorb our waste and generate resources.

Why we use it: Environmental footprint relates to **SDG 9.4 “Upgrade all industries and infrastructures for sustainability”**: By 2030, upgrade infrastructure and retrofit industries to make them sustainable, with increased resource-use efficiency and greater adoption of clean and environmentally sound technologies and industrial processes, with all countries taking action in accordance with their respective capabilities.

It also relates to **SDG 12.2 “Sustainable management and use of natural resources”**, and **SDG 12.7 “Promote sustainable public procurement practices”**.

Moreover, even if a citizen-science project does not aim to explicitly impact the environment positively, there are still ways in which the environmental footprint can be addressed; thus, this indicator is relevant to all citizen-science projects.

Table 15 Indicator formula for “Environmental footprint”

Question number	Question text	Answers	Weights
Environment 1	Does the project take measures to decrease its material footprint?	Yes	11
		No	0
		I don't know.	2
Environment 2	Does the project take measures to reduce its polluting emissions?	Yes	11
		No	0
		I don't know.	2
Environment 3	Does the project have a procurement policy that is sustainable?	Yes	10
		No	0
		I don't know.	2
Environment 9	Do the project activities include pro-environmental actions e.g. litter picking?	Yes	10
		No	0
		I don't know.	2

Table 16 Recommendation score thresholds for “Environmental footprint”

Recommendations	Lower score	Higher score
The project could do more to decrease its material footprint (see about.mics.tools/material-footprint), take measures to reduce its polluting emissions (see about.mics.tools/polluting-emissions), or use a sustainable procurement policy (see UCL's as an example).	0	9
This indicator considers the project's material footprint, polluting emissions, procurement policy, and pro-environmental actions for participants (such as litter picking). The project's score for this indicator shows that the project has considered some of these elements but to get a higher score the project needs to take measures to improve its environmental footprint in all these areas.	10	34
The project has taken actions to improve its environmental footprint by decreasing its material footprint, reducing its polluting emissions, using a sustainable procurement policy, and including pro-environmental actions for participants (such as litter picking). Congratulations!	35	42

4.9.3.2 Environmental awareness

Definition: Environmental awareness can be broadly defined as the attitude regarding the environmental consequences of human behaviour ([Ham et al., 2016](#)).

Why we use it: Environmental awareness relates to **SDG 12.8 “Promote universal understanding of sustainable lifestyles”** and **SDG 13.3 “Build knowledge and capacity to meet climate change”**.

Table 17 Indicator formula for “Environmental awareness”

Question number	Question text	Answers	Weights
Environment 4		Yes	7
		No	0

	Does the project explicitly disseminate information on sustainable development or lifestyles?	I don't know.	2
Environment 5	Does the project educate participants on environmental challenges?	Yes	7
		No	0
		I don't know.	2
Environment 6	Does the project explicitly contribute to a higher awareness of, or positive attitude towards, the natural environment, on this planet or others?	Yes, and it has been measured	21
		Yes, but it has not been measured	14
		No	0
		I don't know.	7
Environment 7	Does the project lead to an increased stewardship of the natural environment among participants?	Yes, and it has been measured	7
		Yes, but it has not been measured	5
		No	0
		I don't know.	2

Table 18 Recommendation score thresholds for “Environmental awareness”

Recommendations	Lower score	Higher score
Being environmentally aware means understanding how our behaviour impacts the environment and committing to making changes to our activities. The project could do more to educate participants on environmental challenges and contribute to participants' awareness of the natural environment, by explicitly disseminating information on sustainable lifestyles.	0	6
The project clearly promotes environmental awareness, by educating participants on environmental challenges, or by contributing to participants' awareness of the natural environment through dissemination activities. Want to be able to measure participants' higher awareness, or increased stewardship? You might want to consider this paper .	7	37
Congratulations! This project goes to great lengths not only to promote environmental awareness and educate participants on environmental challenges, but also to measure improvements in participants' environmental attitudes, behaviour and knowledge.	38	42

4.9.4 Governance

4.9.4.1 Policy

Definition: Policy is a deliberate system of guidelines to guide decisions and achieve rational outcomes. A policy is a statement of intent and is implemented as a procedure or protocol.

Why we use it: Policy is addressed in the [ECSA characteristics of citizen science](#), where it is covered under “Links to decision-making”: “Citizen science projects may include an intervention into the current state of affairs, such as local decision making. This might happen in activities that fall under banners such as participatory action research, community science, or addressing environmental injustice.”

In the explanatory notes of that document, it is also noted that “Citizen science can be used in cases where the participants are concerned with an issue and want to actively change the situation, be it concern over public health, medical support to a group of patients, or addressing a pollution issue.”

Table 19 Indicator formula for “Policy”

Question number	Question text	Answers	Weights
Governance 34	Does the project's data or findings lead to the enforcement of existing regulations or policies?	Yes	8
		No	0
		I don't know	4
Governance 35		Organisational frameworks	1

	Which policy frameworks does the project consider?	Local frameworks	1
		Regional frameworks	1
		National frameworks	1
		Global frameworks	1
		The project does not consider any policy frameworks	0
		I don't know	0
Governance 36	Does the project explicitly inform any governmental policy process?	Yes, at the local level	4
		Yes, at the regional level	6
		Yes, at the national level	8
		Yes, at the international level	10
		No	0
		I don't know	1
Governance 37	Does the project have any explicit impact on external organisational policy?	Yes	8
		No	0
		I don't know	4

Table 20 Recommendation score thresholds for "Policy"

Recommendations	Lower score	Higher score
<p>It looks like policy influence might not be a priority for the project. Of course, not every project can affect policy and some projects have a large impact on governance without ever interacting with official policy. If you're interested in the idea of citizen science as a form of socio-technical governance you can read more in this paper</p> <p>If the project is interested in influencing policy, it could find inspiration from example projects in this report. It might not be a viable option if the project has already started, but citizen-science projects most often have success influencing policy when specific policies are considered in the design of the project and policy makers are engaged from the start of the project.</p>	0	7
<p>The project's score for this indicator suggests it has started to have some impact on policy already. Well done! A common barrier to policy influence for citizen science is <i>concerns about the data</i>. The project could therefore consider addressing concerns surrounding the quality of citizen-science data and aligning the project with the data standards of the policy makers.</p>	8	19
<p>The project might not look like it has the highest score for policy influence, but the answers given suggest it is actually among the more successful citizen-science projects in terms of policy. The most commonly considered impact on policy is citizen-science data as a source of information for decision makers. But citizen science can also directly impact policy as an object of research policy or as a policy instrument. Policy influence can also include affecting organisational policy not just governmental policy. It might be helpful to consider how the project is influencing policy currently and whether any of the other forms of policy influence could also be achieved in the project. The project might find further inspiration from example projects in this report.</p>	20	31
<p>The project is among the most successful on this platform at influencing policy. Congratulations! To get a score this high, the project must already have a lot of experience interacting with policy. But if the project wants to achieve the top scores for this indicator, it will have to consider and explicitly inform governmental policy at all scales (local, regional, national and global). Additionally, the project needs to be confident it has had an impact on external organisational policy and contributed to the enforcement of existing regulations or policies. It's a lot to ask, so don't be worried if the project is happy as it is; it has already achieved a lot!</p>	32	37
<p>The project is among the most successful on this platform at influencing policy. Congratulations! This suggests the project is quite exceptional in its interactions with policy makers. Maybe consider how you could share your experience with other projects so they can get inspiration and have similar success with policy influence.</p>	38	42

4.9.4.2 Sustainable development goals

Definition: The SDGs are a collection of 17 interlinked global goals designed to be a blueprint for achieving a better and more sustainable future for all [<https://sdgs.un.org/>]. The SDGs were set up in

2015 by the United Nations General Assembly (UN-GA) and are intended to be achieved by 2030. They are included in a UN-GA Resolution called the *2030 Agenda* (or *Agenda 2030*). The SDGs were developed in the Post-2015 Development Agenda as the future global development framework to succeed the Millennium Development Goals, which ended in 2015.

Why we use it: Aside from the SDGs becoming the latest buzzword in citizen science (see [Fritz et al., 2019](#), for example) and MICS’s commitment to considering the SDGs in our project Grant Agreement, the United Nations’ 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development is an ambitious plan for “people, planet and prosperity”, aimed at achieving a sustainable future for all; what’s not to like about it?!

Table 21 Indicator formula for “SDGs”

Question number	Question text	Answers	Weights
Governance 38	Is the project team aware of what the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are? Is the project team aware of what the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are?	Yes	2
		No	0
		I don't know	1
Governance 39	Is the project at all related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)?	Yes	4
		No	0
		I don't know	2
Governance 40	Which of the following Sustainable Development Goals is the project related to?	(1) No Poverty	2
		(2) Zero Hunger	2
		(3) Good Health and Well-being	2
		(4) Quality Education	2
		(5) Gender Equality	2
		(6) Clean Water and Sanitation	2
		(7) Affordable and Clean Energy	2
		(8) Decent Work and Economic Growth	2
		(9) Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	2
		(10) Reducing Inequality	2
		(11) Sustainable Cities and Communities	2
		(12) Responsible Consumption and Production	2
		(13) Climate Action	2
		(14) Life Below Water	2
		(15) Life On Land	2
		(16) Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions	2
		(17) Partnerships for the Goals	2
Governance 41	Does the project include data which match a specific indicator of a Sustainable Development Goal?	Yes	12
		No	0
		I don't know	6
Governance 43	Does the project contribute data to the official reporting for a Sustainable Development Goal indicator?	Yes	18
		No	0
		I don't know	6

Table 22 Recommendation score thresholds for “SDGs”

Recommendations	Lower score	Higher score
The Sustainable Development Goals are a collection of 17 interlinked global goals designed to be a "blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all". However, citizen science has a much broader remit, so it is ok that your project does not directly consider them. You can find more information on SDGs here , to see if there are any possible links between their aims and your project.	0	2
The project must be very closely aligned to the SDGs, either contributing data to the official reporting of the SDGs or with targets related to the majority of the goals. This makes this project one of the most impactful citizen-science projects with regards to the SDGs.	36	42

The project is related to an improbably high number of SDGs. So improbably high, in fact, that it has broken our scoring system for this indicator. Excellent work!	43	100
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4.9.5 Science and technology

4.9.5.1 Scientific productivity

Definition: Scientific productivity refers to the productivity of scientists in their research performance. In other words, the term concerns how much output scientists produce within a specific period, or compared to the inputs utilized for the research.

Why we use it: Scientific productivity is included in the [ECSA characteristics of citizen science](#) under the heading of “data and knowledge generation”: “Citizen science, scientific, academic, and policy-oriented research can include different forms of data and knowledge generation, including novel data generation, creation of new analyses, or production of new knowledge in written and other forms. The knowledge produced in such projects should aspire to disciplinary standards, such as appropriate data quality and quality assurance, the peer review of project publications and materials, or policy-relevant evidence that is fit for decision-making.”

[Kieslinger et al.](#) also note the importance of citizen scientists participating in publications, or having their engagement recognised.

Table 23 Indicator formula for “Scientific productivity”

Question number	Question text	Answers	Weights
Science 10	How many publications, indexed by Google Scholar, resulted from the project?	The project has not produced any publications	0
		Less than 3	5
		3-30	8
		More than 30	9
		I don't know	1
Science 12	How many citations have the publications produced by the project received, in total (according to Google scholar)?	Less than 3	3
		3-30	5
		31-300	8
		More than 300	9
		I don't know	1
Science 13	What is the highest impact-factor (or impact-index) of the publications produced by the project? (Just Google: “[journal name]” impact factor	Less than 2	5
		2-5	7
		More than 5	9
		I don't know	1
Science 15	Has the project supported students' dissertations or theses?	Yes	5
		It's in progress.	4
		No	0
		I don't know.	2
Science 26	How are the project outcomes shared?	Scholarly outputs, e.g. peer-review publications, open data sets	4
		Grey literature, e.g. reports, working papers, policy briefs	2
		Popular media, e.g. social media, magazine or newspaper articles, TV or radio, newsletters, leaflets	1
		Events, e.g. conferences, community talks, lectures, workshops, fairs, seminars or webinars	3

Table 24 Recommendation score thresholds for "Scientific productivity"

Recommendations	Lower score	Higher score
It is essential to share the outputs of a citizen-science project - through events, media and publications - otherwise learnings will not extend beyond the sphere of the project. Not every citizen-science project has an academic focus on publications. Nevertheless, by publishing the results of the project in peer-reviewed journals, the project could improve its scientific impact. Try to publish in high-impact-factor journals so the publications will be cited more. Perhaps the project could even support students' dissertations or theses in the future.	0	6
Congratulations - in a world of "publish or perish", this project has high scientific productivity. With many publications in high-impact-factor journals, the project's research has been well cited, indicating outcomes have been widely shared.	30	42

4.9.5.2 Interdisciplinary science

Definition: Interdisciplinary science is the collaborative process of integrating knowledge/expertise from trained individuals of two or more disciplines.

Why we use it: There is evidence that interdisciplinarity is statistically significantly and positively associated with research impact ([Okamura, 2019](#)).

Table 25 Indicator formula for "Interdisciplinary science"

Question number	Question text	Answers	Weights
Science 1	Which disciplines are the focus of the project's research?	Citizen science (If you don't select this one, you are in trouble)	1
		Agricultural and veterinary sciences (including forestry sciences, fisheries sciences, and land and farm management)	1
		Art theory and criticism	1
		Biological sciences (including ecology, zoology, genetics, and biodiversity)	1
		Chemical sciences (including medicinal and biomolecular chemistry)	1
		Earth sciences (including geology, atmospheric sciences, and oceanography)	1
		Engineering (including food sciences, environmental engineering, and biomedical engineering)	1
		Environmental sciences (including ecological applications, environmental management, and soil sciences)	1
		Information and computing sciences (including artificial intelligence and image processing, distributed computing, and computer software)	1
		Language, communication and culture (including linguistics, and literary studies)	1
		Law and legal studies	1
		Mathematical sciences and statistics	1
		Medical and health sciences (including neurosciences, public health and health services, nutrition and dietetics, and human movement and sports science)	1
		Philosophy and religious studies (including applied ethics, and history and philosophy of specific fields)	1
		Physical sciences (including astronomical and space sciences, atomic, molecular, nuclear, particle and plasma physics, and quantum physics)	1
		Psychology and cognitive sciences	1
Studies in human society (including human geography, history, archaeology, policy and administration, sociology, and education)	1		

		Technology (including communications technologies, and computer hardware)	1
		I don't know	0
Science 2	Does the project explicitly promote interdisciplinary ways of working?	Yes	30
		No	0
		I don't know	15

Table 26 Recommendation score thresholds for "Interdisciplinary science"

Recommendations	Lower score	Higher score
By working across multiple disciplines, this project is making efforts to promote interdisciplinary ways of working. There is evidence that interdisciplinarity is statistically significantly and positively associated with research impact (Okamura, 2019), mainly through the engagement of a wider audience. Keep up the good work!	20	42
Explicitly promoting interdisciplinary ways of working could increase the impact of the project. There is evidence that interdisciplinarity is statistically significantly and positively associated with research impact (Okamura, 2019), mainly through the engagement of a wider audience.	0	19

4.10 Limitations

There is an inevitable level of uncertainty at each stage of data collection and analysis in the impact assessment process of the MICS platform. The purpose of this section is to explain how this uncertainty has been managed and what limitations still remain. These uncertainties are presented in the spirit of responsible quantification, allowing interpretation of the outputs of the MICS platform with an appropriate level of context, including an awareness of assumptions, framing, consequences and unknowns (Saltelli et al., 2020).

First, considering the assumptions and unknowns in the platform, it is important to acknowledge that these uncertainties are cumulative such that uncertainties at the data collection phase (users answering questions on the platform) are carried through subsequent data analysis and also contribute a proportion of uncertainty to the outputs of the platform (primarily the impact report). There are three main areas of the platform where assumptions and unknowns accumulate, which are detailed below.

4.10.1 Quality of the data input

Assumption that users are able to "correctly" answer the questions. The MICS platform offers projects the chance to carry out an unsupervised self-assessment of the impact of their project. As such, there is no guarantee that, as users are answering the questions, they are interpreting the questions as they are intended to, or that they will select the answer options which most accurately reflect their project. This includes a number of assumptions: that users will be able to understand the meaning of every question; that every question will have a relevant answer option for every citizen-science project; that users will know enough about all aspects of the project they are representing; and that users will choose to accurately answer the questions rather than adapting their answers in an attempt to improve their impact scores. To some extent, these assumptions are addressed by the careful testing of the question wording and the help text which is provided to try and reduce the chance that users can misinterpret a question. Nevertheless, as a self-administered tool, a level of uncertainty is inevitable, and the platform relies on users to answer the questions in good faith and interpret the outputs in the context of this uncertainty.

Unknowns arising from incomplete responses from users. With a total of over 200 input features, it is likely that not every user of the MICS platform will provide an answer to every question. Not only will some questions be left blank, all questions have answer options which introduce a level of ambiguity, such as “I don’t know” or “Yes, but it has not been measured”. The proportion of questions which are unanswered or which users select an ambiguous answer for will have a knock-on effect on the confidence with which conclusions can be drawn from their answers about the impact of their project. This is at least partially acknowledged by the “impact assessment progress” percentage, which is displayed at the top of both the project page and the impact report.

4.10.2 Machine learning scores

The uncertainty of the effectiveness of the neural network used in Alquimics can actually be easily quantified and is currently operating at over 96% accuracy whilst assessing the training set (see Figure 5).

```
Command Window
Loading data...

Initialising neural-network parameters...

Starting neural network...

Calculating cost function with regularisation (to avoid overfitting)...

Cost function corresponding to initialisation parameters: 6.413712

Evaluating sigmoid gradient...

Sigmoid gradient at [-1 -0.5 0 0.5 1]: 0.196612 0.235004 0.250000 0.235004 0.196612

Training neural network...

Iteration    10 | Cost: 2.921882e+00
Training-set accuracy per domain: 96.524076
Training-set accuracy per domain: 97.047786
Training-set accuracy per domain: 97.348181
Training-set accuracy per domain: 98.153519
Training-set accuracy per domain: 97.585976
>> |
```

Figure 5. Accuracy of Alquimics whilst assessing the training set

However, in addition to this and the uncertainties around the quality of the data input discussed above, there are a number of other limitations:

Assumption that the scores used to train and test the machine learning algorithm are accurate. The training and testing sets for the machine learning algorithm were collected via self-assessment exercises in interviews with project coordinators, whose responses were then moderated by the interviewers to ensure the projects were assessed consistently. There is, therefore, an underpinning assumption that project coordinators (and the MICS team interviewers) are able to quantify the impact of their projects across five separate domains. The scores produced by the machine-learning algorithm are therefore best considered as an approximation of how other project coordinators might judge a project rather than an objective measure of its impact

Assumption that the training set and testing set data for the machine learning algorithm are representative. Regardless of the quality of the data collected to train and test the machine learning algorithm, the process is reliant on the projects selected being representative of citizen-science

projects as a whole. In practice, this is probably not possible given the diversity of the citizen-science field, even if efforts have been made to recruit projects representing a mixture of disciplines, sizes, ages and forms of citizen science. The algorithm will therefore be biased towards certain types of projects and might not be able to assess the impact of every citizen science project with the same level of accuracy.

Unknown differences between the training and testing projects and new projects added to the platform. Given the difficulty in finding a mixture of projects to act as a representative sample for the training and testing sets, there is a risk that the projects used for training and testing are significantly different from new projects added to the platform. This might lead to erroneous impact results. This is normal at this early stage of the platform life whilst the number of projects used to train the machine-learning algorithm is still relatively low, but, hopefully, this uncertainty will reduce with time as the algorithm continues to be trained.

4.10.3 Rule-based scores

It should, in theory, be easier to understand the uncertainty arising from the calculation of the rule-based scores in the MICS impact report because the logic underpinning the algorithms can be described and understood compared to the “black box” of the machine learning algorithm. In addition to the limitations in the data input described above, the largest assumption or unknown arising from the rule-based scores is the extent to which the weights assigned to each question answer reflect the “real-world” impact they supposedly represent in that indicator. Whilst the rule-based scores are simple enough that there is a high level of certainty that an answer to a particular question indicates the project is having an impact in a particular area, it is not clear that this impact can be easily quantified without further information. The numbers in the rule-based scores, whilst still useful indications of impact, probably should not be considered linear quantifications of real-world change.

4.10.4 Complexity, framing and consequences

As an attempt to advance the state of the art with regard to citizen-science impact assessment, the MICS platform has an inevitable level of complexity. This is particularly true of the machine-learning scores, which involve so many input features that the logic used to combine the answers to over 200 questions into a set of five numbers is not (easily) explainable or understandable. In this sense, the rule-based scores provide a good counterbalance by combining only a small selection of questions with a known logic. Nevertheless, a limitation in the quantifications of impact provided by the MICS platform arises from the high level of complexity inherent in the approach.

Whilst the majority of the uncertainties above cannot be easily quantified, in all likelihood they cumulatively represent a very high margin of error in the quantification provided in the MICS impact report. It is, therefore, essential that the framing of the MICS platform helps to guide users into interpreting the outputs of the MICS platform about their project in the appropriate context. This is particularly true given the potential consequences of (mis)interpretation of a project’s impact report. For example, the scores from the platform could inspire a project coordinator to make changes to the way a project is run in a way which actually decreases the project’s impact, or a funder might assign funding to a project based on the score it received from MICS even if it was actually ineffectual in terms of the desired real-world changes. To some extent, the framing of the outputs of the MICS platform acknowledges that the generalised approach adopted on the platform means that not everything will be relevant to every project. For example, the recommendations in the impact report are purposefully framed as suggestions and sources of inspiration rather than strict instructions, given that activities that were successful in one project would not necessarily be feasible or suit the context of another project. However, more can still be done to improve the way that limitations are

acknowledged throughout the MICS platform and especially in the impact reports. Future development of the platform could include more prominent explanations of uncertainty on the impact report, including error bars or other indicators of the limitations discussed above.

5 Applying the impact-assessment approach

5.1 [about.mics.tools](#)

The MICS platform [[mics.tools](#)] also has a companion website [[about.mics.tools](#)], which provides resources and guidance to complement the impact assessment tools on the MICS platform. The [[about.mics.tools](#)] website has three main aims:

- to provide help for users of the MICS platform and details of the platform content;
- to make the methodological work undertaken in the project accessible to users in the form of impact assessment guidance;
- to archive information about the MICS project, allowing the MICS brand to be primarily associated with the platform.

Content from key project deliverables and other outputs has been reformatted and is now presented in a more accessible form on [[about.mics.tools](#)]. The menu structure of the website has also been carefully designed to help users to navigate the large volumes of information available to them and to help them find the resources which are of most use to them. This philosophy is also applied to the structure of each of the pages on the website, which often have links to related pages, either signposted in the main text on the page or in a side banner. In this way, [[about.mics.tools](#)] represents the practical application of the knowledge generated and methodological development in the MICS project, described in section 2 of this deliverable.

[[about.mics.tools](#)] will be updated and maintained by Earthwatch alongside the main MICS platform.

5.1.1 Site structure

The menu structure of [[about.mics.tools](#)] is split into two halves. Firstly, there is the main menu which contains the home page and all the pages which are accessible from the drop-down menus on the header bar. These are the pages that users will be able to freely navigate. The other half of the menu structure is the hidden menu which contains all the pages which are published on the website but are only accessible by clicking on a direct link to the page or entering the page URL. The purpose of using the hidden menu is to stop the drop-down menus on the header bar from becoming too long and difficult for users to navigate. A description of each of the pages is given below.

Main menu:

- **Home page:** this is the first page that most users will see on [[about.mics.tools](#)] (see Figure 6). The page gives an overview of all the content on the website and explains the menu structure so that users can navigate to what they are most interested in. There is a brightly coloured banner at the bottom of the page, which currently (July 2022) draws attention to the “user stories” page. The text in the banner can easily be updated to make announcements to users as needed in the future.
 - **Impact assessment guidance:** there are no sub-menu items for the impact assessment guidance page because there are too many sub-pages which would be difficult to navigate on a drop-down menu. Instead, the impact assessment guidance page contains a decision tree which gives users a guided navigation of the resources

available. The decision tree is worded as statements about what the user would like to achieve, helping users to pick the page which will be of the most use to them. The pages linked to on this page are all on the hidden menu.

- **MICS platform:** clicking on this menu item links to [mics.tools] and gives users the possibility to navigate back to the MICS platform from any page of [about.mics.tools]. It also acts as a heading for the sub-menu items, which all relate to the MICS platform.
 - **How-to guide:** The how-to guide for the MICS platform was initially prepared as a document for Deliverable D5.5 *Multimedia resources and policy briefs presenting general and region-specific recommendations*, the content from which has since been reformatted and uploaded as a page on [about.mics.tools]. The how-to guide will be periodically reviewed and updated to reflect any changes to [mics.tools] or to address feedback from users.
 - **Questions:** The full list of questions, answer options, help and information text, question sources, and original wording in the source are presented in this page (in the same table format as in section 4 of this deliverable). The purpose of the page is to give users easy access to the questions in case they want to read the full list without entering the [mics.tools] interface or use the questions for any other purpose.
 - **Indicators:** The indicators and recommendations are presented in full on this page (in the same format as in section 4 of this deliverable). The page is linked to directly from the impact report generated by the MICS platform and gives users a more detailed explanation of how the rule-based scores are calculated and the recommendations chosen for their project.
 - **Alquimics:** This page gives an explanation of the algorithms used in the [mics.tools] impact report. The text will be updated to reflect any changes as the algorithms continue to be trained and tested.
 - **Where to find help (WTF):** This page is the equivalent of a *frequently asked questions* (FAQ) page and will be updated as users ask further questions when using the platform. The purpose of the page is to reduce the time required to maintain the MICS platform, as users will be able to check responses to common questions before contacting the MICS team directly.
 - **User stories:** this page will collect testimonials and use-cases of the MICS platform. These user stories will be a useful tool in encouraging other users to register for the platform and to apply the impact report in their project(s). Currently (July 2022), there is one user story on the page from the H2020 project [MONOCLE](#) who used the MICS platform impact report when writing a deliverable evaluating the project's impact. This user story is described in section 5.5 of this deliverable.

Welcome to MICS

Where you'll find everything you need to know about Measuring the Impact of Citizen Science.

If you only have 90 seconds to spare, watch our video.

If you have a little longer, read the information below.

Impact assessment guidance

The MICS guidance provides insights into the various impacts of citizen science and why it is important to measure them, how citizen-science initiatives can be co-designed for impact, and how to measure their impacts. Here you'll be guided through available resources such as tools, scientific papers, training materials, and networks, and helped to improve impact assessment.

MICS platform

The MICS platform provides an easy-to-use tool as an entry into the world of impact assessment. The platform uses a set of questions with pre-defined answers which users can pick from, and provides links to helpful resources as well as recommendations to help increase the impact of the projects.

Under this tab you will also be able to find all the support you might need to use the MICS platform. Our how-to guide takes you step-by-step through the process of registering on the platform, creating a project page and taking the impact assessment. "Where to find help" answers any niggling questions you may have about how best to tackle this impact assessment. Just want to know the 200 questions the platform asks? No problem, we've listed them for you on the Questions page.

Wondering how you might use the MICS platform?

Click [here](#) to read how the H2020 project MONOCLE used the MICS impact report when writing their impact deliverable.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824711.

Information

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- The team
- Partners
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Figure 6 Home page of [about.mics.tools]

Hidden menu:

- **Impact assessment guidance:** as previously explained, the impact assessment guidance page contains a decision tree which helps users to navigate between a series of pages which present the methodologies developed in the MICS project (see Figure 7).
 - **Learn about the impacts of citizen science:** this page gives a light introduction to the concept of impact assessment, in particular in the context of citizen science projects. It is intended for users who are unfamiliar with the topic.
 - **Co-design citizen science:** this page summarises the Ground Truth 2.0 co-design method light developed as part of the MICS project (published in Deliverable D4.6 *Guidance for co-design of citizen science activities in the MICS case-study sites*) and applied in three of the MICS case studies. The method is outlined in this page so that it can be used by other projects.
 - **Measure the impacts of citizen science:** this page provides another set of branches for users to choose from, offering four different impact assessment methods.
 - **MICS platform:** this page summarises the MICS platform in the context of this decision tree so that users can compare it to the other impact assessment methods on offer.
 - **MICS impact indicator explorer:** this page summarises the indicators collected as part of the MICS impact assessment framework (and described in [Deliverable D2.7: Finalised version of the conceptual framework](#)). Each indicator has its own page on [about.mics.tools], which gives the full details of the indicator, including the data collection methods, feasibility of data collection, and source of the indicator. There are also five sub-pages, one for each of the MICS domains, which help users to navigate between indicators in each domain:
 - 5 pages for the MICS domains
 - 83 pages for each indicator in the MICS impact assessment framework
 - **MICS impact journeys:** this page presents the approach to co-evaluation which was developed during the MICS project. It provides an alternative style of impact assessment to the others developed in MICS, focusing more on the specific goals and aims of the project and its participants rather than on completing a generalised and overarching assessment.
 - **Impact stories:** this page presents an impact reporting approach produced by the WeObserve Impact Community of Practice. Although it was not developed as part of the MICS project, it provides an alternative approach to impact reporting which relies less on measurement or quantification and helps guide projects in how to communicate the impacts they know they have had.
 - **About the guidance:** this page describes how the guidance on [about.mics.tools] was produced and can be accessed from a link at the bottom of the impact assessment guidance page.

MICS Online Guidance

The MICS Online Guidance is designed to guide citizen science practitioners and academics through impact assessment in the context of citizen science. Start using the MICS Online Guidance by selecting the topic that you are interested in:

I want to...

...learn about the impacts of citizen science & why it is important to measure them

...co-design citizen science for impact

...measure the impacts of citizen science projects

...by using the standardised approach on the MICS Platform

...by focusing on specific indicators using the MICS Impact Indicator Explorer

...by co-evaluating via the MICS Impact journeys approach

...by creating impact stories

You can find out more about the MICS Online Guidance on the about page.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824711.

Information

Citizen science
Nature-based solutions
Data protection and privacy policy
Contact

About the MICS project

The MICS project
The team
Partners
Deliverables
Resources

Newsletter

Email address

SUBMIT

Enter your email address above to receive updates on the MICS project. Please see our privacy policy for more information.

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Figure 7 Impact assessment guidance page on [about.mics.tools].

- **Project page:** the project page can be accessed from the footer of [about.mics.tools] and is intended to act as an archive space for information about the MICS project (as opposed to the MICS platform). These pages should not need updating beyond the end of the MICS project.
 - **Team:** This page contains profiles of all the staff that have worked on the MICS project from each of the partner organisations.
 - **Partners:** This page provides links to the websites of all the MICS partner organisations and other collaborators.
 - **Advisory board:** This page contains profiles of all the advisory board members of the MICS project
 - **Workplan:** This page summarises the main work packages in the MICS project (not including the project management and ethics work packages).
 - **Deliverables:** This page contains titles and links to all of the deliverables produced by the MICS project. All MICS deliverables will also be made available in the [MICS community on Zenodo](#).
 - **Case studies:** The MICS project worked with citizen science projects in five case studies. The citizen science and impact assessment activities carried out in each of the case studies are described on a dedicated page for each project.
 - Marzenego river
 - Creek Rakos
 - Carasuhat wetlands
 - Outfall Safari
 - Riverfly
 - **Resources:** This page contains resources produced by or about the project, including the project logos, fact sheet and other media files.
 - **Newsletters:** This page contains an archived list of all the MICS newsletters with links to copies of each one.
 - **Project impact:** This page presents a summary of the (expected) impacts of the MICS project and may be updated to reflect the continued impacts of the MICS project.
- **Miscellaneous pages:** the following pages are linked in the footer of [about.mics.tools] and explain key terminology or concepts used in the MICS project or provide information such as the data protection and privacy policy and contact details for the MICS project team.
 - Interoperability
 - Citizen science
 - Nature-based solutions
 - Data protection
 - Contact

5.2 Comprehensive evaluation report

In Deliverable 4.5, a description and evaluation have been provided of the findings on the impact of citizen science in the case study sites. The MICS impact assessment approach was applied to the five MICS case study sites across Europe, each of which has differing levels of citizen-science engagement, approaches to environmental management, needs, contexts, approaches to *nature-based solutions* (NBSs), and levels of citizen-science application. The case studies are:

- (i) Outfall Safari (UK): aims to use citizen science to detect and record pollution from surface water outfalls to gather evidence and report on pollution incidents.

- (ii) Riverfly monitoring (UK): aims to monitor key macroinvertebrate species (riverflies) that are indicators of river water quality.
- (iii) Marzenego River NBS project (Italy): aims to establish a monitoring program to gauge the effectiveness of NBS implemented within the Marzenego River catchment.
- (iv) The Creek Rákos citizen-science project (Hungary): aims to use citizen science as a means of establishing the baseline condition of the creek to identify suitable sites for restoration and promote public support for NBS.
- (v) The Carasuhát Wetland NBS project (Romania): aims to establish a monitoring programme to gauge the effectiveness of wetland NBS implemented in the Danube Delta.

The MICS case studies represent different types and stages of water-related NBS implementation, with some activities in the early planning phase, some underway and others already implemented. D4.5 provided a description and evaluation of the process of applying the MICS impact assessment described in MICS deliverables D2.2, D2.3, and D2.7 to the case studies.

The MICS case studies include two existing contributory citizen-science projects (UK) and three new projects (Italy, Hungary and Romania) that applied the Ground Truth 2.0 co-design light methodology to guide the set-up of citizen-science activities with local communities. Implementation of the co-design process in the ‘new project’ case studies increased the active involvement of citizens in the design and set-up of activities.

Following the completion of Deliverable 4.5, several updates were made to the *MICS case studies’ impact monitoring journeys (IMJs) and impact monitoring strategies (IMS)*. These updates specifically relate to changes in the Outfall Safari, Marzenego and Carasuhát case studies and are outlined in Appendix B.

5.3 NBS science-briefs

MICS has produced a series of policy briefs, delivered as **D5.4 “Nature-based solutions science briefs”** in 2020. Deliverable 5.4 outlined the context for the creation of these NBS policy briefs. These policy briefs are aimed at decision makers to encourage the uptake and application of NBSs and contain critical recommendations for their implementation.

The content and recommendations of the briefs were derived from a review of the literature and the results of a survey disseminated to practitioners of NBSs. The purpose of this survey was to gather evidence regarding the perceptions of NBS practitioners on working within the policy framework for implementing NBSs, as well as different factors affecting the uptake and lack thereof of NBSs in practice, and recommendations for how these could be overcome.

In July 2022, after consultations with key stakeholders engaged with the delivery of NBSs, these have been updated, and, although the updates are minor, the two-page brief focused on Central and Eastern Europe has now been separated into a two-page brief on Central Europe and a two-page brief on Eastern Europe, allowing to highlight the Carasuhát Wetland project. The updated briefs are included in Appendix C.

5.4 Launch communication-plan

To ensure that the MICS platform is disseminated as far as possible and to maximise its potential in informing and furthering the area of citizen-science impact assessment, a comprehensive launch communication-plan has been developed. Before the launch of the MICS platform, a series of communications will take place:

- A message will be sent out to the MICS consortium to alert them to the launch date and to allow them to promote the platform across their networks.
- The final MICS newsletter will include informative videos (detailed in D5.5) and links to the platform and online guidance.
- Across MICS social media platforms, we will post a countdown to the launch to build up interest amongst the citizen science community, an example tweet from the MICS project account (@MICSproject).

- A blog post will be sent to ECSA, CSA, ACSA and SwafS mailing lists (for example):

Draft blog post: The MICS project has developed a collection of methods and tools to help citizen-science projects measure and achieve their impacts.

The project included several case studies which brought together community groups and local authorities to co-design new citizen-science initiatives around nature-based solutions. In Italy, school children and other locals monitored the effects of wetlands on the water quality of the Marzenego River – even developing their own method for measuring levels of bacteria! In Romania, citizen scientists investigated the effects of Danube wetland restoration on water quality and bank stability; whilst the project in Hungary surveyed water quality and biodiversity to promote the restoration of Creek Rákos (you may have seen us on the local news).

*In the UK, MICS worked with two established citizen-science projects - Outfall Safari and Riverfly - to evaluate their impacts. In fact, MICS has developed an open-access platform to help **all** citizen-science projects assess their impacts and reach their full potential.*

With the platform's help, users can assess whether a project has had an impact on several domains: society, the environment, the economy, governance, and science and technology. The MICS platform can analyse a project at any stage of development and can be used to inform ongoing activities to improve impact.

The impact-assessment process on the MICS platform includes over 200 questions, each with a pre-defined set of answers that users can choose from. These questions capture input features and are based on current impact-assessment methods and other frameworks such as the ECSA characteristics of citizen science. Each project's answers are analysed by a series of artificial-intelligence algorithms, which generate impact scores. The platform also provides projects with recommendations on improving impact across several domains and an assessment of their impact on the UN's Sustainable Development Goals.

The MICS platform is complemented by the MICS Online Guidance, which provides insights into the various impacts of citizen science and why it is important to measure them, how citizen science initiatives can be co-designed for impact, and how to measure their impacts. The MICS Online Guidance guides users through available resources such as tools, scientific papers, training materials and networks; also designed to help improve impact assessment.

Indeed, by improving a project's impact through increasing democratic engagement and promoting a scientific mentality, citizen science can contribute to achieving the SDGs and promoting a sustainable future for all.

Be part of the process – register on the platform today!

- A resource page for the EU.Citizen-Science platform will be published, highlighting the application of the platform.
- And a press release will be published by Earthwatch Europe:

Draft press release: NEW ONLINE PLATFORM LAUNCHED TO IMPROVE CITIZEN SCIENCE

A collaborative EU project, Measuring Impact of Citizen Science (MICS), has launched a new online tool designed to help improve citizen-science projects.

The MICS project has developed methods, guidelines and tools to help organisations measure and achieve their impacts through citizen-science programmes. Citizen science – work undertaken by citizen communities to advance science, and encourage scientific engagement – is a powerful tool and Earthwatch hope that the MICS platform can be widely used to improve citizen-science project outcomes.

The launch of the new platform follows four years of development by the MICS project partners: IHE Delft, AAWA, Geonardo, GeoEcoMar and the RRC, coordinated by Earthwatch Europe, an Oxford-based environmental organisation. The MICS platform helps users to assess a project's impact on several areas: society, the environment, the economy, governance, and science and technology. The platform can analyse a project at any stage of development and can be used to inform ongoing activities to improve impact.

The impact-assessment process on the MICS platform includes over 200 questions, each with a pre-defined set of answers that users can choose from. These questions capture input features and are

based on current impact-assessment methods and other frameworks such as the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) characteristics of citizen science. Each project's answers are analysed by an artificial-intelligence algorithm, which generates impact scores. The platform also provides projects with recommendations on improving impact and an assessment of their impact on the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The MICS platform is complemented by comprehensive online guidance, which provides insights into the various impacts of citizen science and why it is important to measure them, how citizen-science initiatives can be co-designed for impact, and how to measure their impacts. The users are guided through available resources such as tools, scientific papers, training materials, and networks, and are helped to improve impact assessment.

Luigi Ceccaroni, the coordinator of the MICS project, says:

"This tool will help ensure that participatory projects are as effective as possible and that individuals, groups and communities involved can have a positive impact on the environments around them. In the UK, MICS worked with two established citizen-science projects - Outfall Safari and Riverfly - to evaluate their impacts. We want other citizen-science projects to use the platform to assess and hopefully improve their own impact."

Earthwatch champions the use of citizen science for positive environmental impact and to address environmental crises. Citizen science is a key feature of most of Earthwatch's environmental research projects, including Tiny Forest tree planting and Freshwater Watch river pollution monitoring.

Organisations and projects looking to make use of the MICS platform should follow this link: [\[mics.tools\]](#)

5.5 Using MICS

The following is an example of how the outputs of the MICS platform – the impact report and recommendations – have been used by an H2020 project, MONOCLE (Multiscale Observation Networks for Optical monitoring of Coastal waters, Lakes and Estuaries), for impact reporting in their deliverable "Evaluation of project impact":

MICS analysis of project impact in the Citizen Science Sector

To comparatively assess the impact of the citizen-science element of MONOCLE, we utilised the MICS (Measuring Impact of Citizen Science) standardised impact assessment tool.

The impact-assessment process on the MICS platform includes over 200 questions, each with a pre-defined set of answers that users choose from. These questions capture input features and are based on current impact-assessment methods and other frameworks, such as the ECSA characteristics of citizen science. The specific answers from each project are analysed through a series of *artificial intelligence* (AI) algorithms, which result in impact scores across five domains – science and technology, society, governance, environment and economy – all of which are scored out of a maximum of 42 points.

At the time of submission, the algorithms are still in a "learning" phase of development, with the machine-learning scores attributed to the project subject to change based on further data input. However, the rule-based scores are calculated based on a set of rules which combine specific sets of input features on the same theme into a single indicator and are therefore already useful to consider.

MONOCLE scored highest in the science and **Technology** domain, with a score of 31 for scientific productivity – a measure of how much output scientists produce within a certain time period, or compared to the inputs that are utilized for the research – and a score of 36 for interdisciplinary science: the collaborative process of integrating knowledge/expertise from trained individuals of two or more disciplines. This collaborative process has been shown to be statistically significantly and positively associated with research impact. These scores reflect the collaborative nature of the work conducted in WP2 and WP3 (development of sensors and integration into platforms such as citizen science), and the outputs of the project in terms of technology and solutions.

MONOCLE also produced respectable scores in the **Environment** domain, with scores of 26 and 22 for environmental awareness and environmental footprint, respectively. These scores reflect the status of the project as ready (and tested) to engage with citizen science projects rather than achieve societal impact. Across other domains there is mixed feedback. In **Economy**, while economic productivity (output per unit of input) did not score highly, financial sustainability - the assessment that a project will have sufficient means to sustain its outputs - did (31), reflecting the exploitation efforts of WP8. In **Governance**, an understanding of, and reporting around, the SDGs scored well (26); however, **Policy** was much lower (7). This score would be improved upon publication and uptake of the drafted white paper in the short term, and it is worth noting that the assessment on the MICS platform can be updated at any time to reflect the evolution of the project, even beyond the end of the project.

In **Society**, MONOCLE scored well (26) in *activeness*, the level of cognitive engagement of participants, but less well in *involvement*, the degree of participation in different stages of a project. This is a fair criticism of the ongoing citizen science element of MONOCLE: whilst participants had to fully cognitively engage with the activities, there were limited phases of the project in which they played a role – namely data collection, and with the sole purpose of testing new technology. These scores are not surprising considering the scope of MONOCLE is not to do citizen science, but to develop support for it, and so including citizen scientists in other phases of the project would not have been appropriate in this instance.

In summary, MONOCLE had a positive impact in aspects of all impact domains, with a particularly positive impact on science and technology as a whole, as well as financial sustainability and participant activeness within the economy and society domains, respectively.

6 Conclusion and sustainability

This deliverable wanted to be the reference document for the MICS project. It includes a comprehensive description of the platform that the project developed to measure the impact of citizen science and links to all other project outputs. It includes, **for the first time, a detailed description of all the metrics used to measure impact in citizen science**, which are represented by those 200 sets of questions and answers which are called here, in a not particularly attractive way, *input features*.

When starting to read this document, people might have expected a description of how citizen science can positively impact several domains, namely the ones chosen by MICS: **society, governance, the economy, the environment, and science**. We hope the readers were not too disappointed to find out that this document, and the MICS project, take a neutral stance on the impact of citizen science, which can be positive, negative, or insignificant. Also, given the complexity of measuring it, the uncertainty associated with any measure of impact is always very high. There are several reasons for MICS's focus choice, which are briefly reiterated here.

First, it is only too easy to gather several success stories and argue that citizen science has the potential to enable the reaching of a positive impact on any domain or the SDGs. It can be accurate but is not the whole story. Citizen science has much positive potential but is also associated with a significant amount of hype, typical of young disciplines. There is consequently a real possibility that such sunshine stories about how citizen science will contribute to solving some of our problems will lead the non-technical general public to lose sight of the actual scope of the challenges humanity faces, especially in the Global South. And this is because, as argued in this document and as the MICS platform can show, some of the positive potential of citizen science is real but relatively minor. On the other hand, even if a negative impact of citizen science is possible, this is usually not significant. Notably, the *future* impact of citizen science depends on the policy choices decision makers make when they fund (or not) citizen science. And these choices depend on the *current* impact of citizen science, which, until now, was largely unquantified. MICS tried to fill this gap precisely providing a platform for quantified impact assessment in the emergent area of citizen science.

Second, if the focus is exclusively on the demonstrated positive potential of citizen science, the chance will be missed to discuss the magnitude of these potential positive impacts of citizen science. This discussion can happen through rising general awareness or policy action derived from using the MICS platform. It is also worthwhile to point out that the MICS platform's quantification of impact and recommendations might, in fact, be used to increase positive impacts once projects become aware of the, possibly insignificant, magnitude of their current impact. Even those who disagree with the MICS assessment of the current impact of citizen science have little to lose from supporting a development in which that assessment is used to provide recommendations and guidance to ensure citizen-science projects are designed, developed and managed to maximise positive impact.

MICS often referred to impact in relation to the SDGs. The SDGs are intended to *transform the world* for the better and sustainably. While it is helpful to examine how citizen science can contribute to the reaching (or monitoring) of the SDGs, this document has also shown the potential for using the SDGs to evaluate the social, environmental, and economic consequences of citizen science. This makes the SDGs a valuable complement to the traditional impact-assessment frameworks, as the SDGs explicitly and without compromise drive home the message that sustainable development is not just about isolated use cases in the Global North. The message is about how our activities, including citizen-science activities, contribute to either reducing or exacerbating the differences between individuals, groups, and nations. MICS has shown that all aspects of citizen science - the infrastructure it uses, who designs and deploys it, who owns the data, who has access to them, who can use it, what it is used for, and, of course, its impact - have to be understood and addressed to ensure that citizen science offers a meaningful contribution to society, governance, the economy, the environment, science, technology, and the SDGs.

6.1 Sustainability of MICS outputs and learnings

Digital technologies, and the associated services, are ever-evolving, and so are the activities that utilise them. To ensure the sustainability of the MICS platform and its resources, their custodians (the MICS partners) need likewise to be ever-evolving and aware of new systems and technologies for the platform to remain relevant. In addition, technologies can constantly be improved to address the evolving needs related to the inevitable progression of the citizen-science and impact-assessment disciplines. The MICS project team, and Earthwatch in particular as coordinator, are committed to constantly appraising and iteratively improving the MICS platform and outputs beyond the project timeline. Beyond the timeframe of the EC-funded period, the open-source nature of the technologies used for the MICS platform ensures that Earthwatch can perform development tasks on the software code of the platform until at least 2030 to ensure that it remains relevant and usable.

Furthermore, the platform code, and guidance on its development and use, have been made openly available on GitHub. This means that, beyond the original MICS project team, anyone can download a copy of the platform and create their bespoke developments and functionality to fit their specific needs. Through this process, the MICS outputs and learnings can continue to inform and influence the citizen-science and impact-assessment disciplines, directly through the actions of the MICS consortium and indirectly through the efforts of others modifying the approach.

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Appendix A - MICS deliverables (and descriptions)

7.1 WP1 – Coordination, project management, and communication

D1.1. Project scoreboard and progress indicators

This deliverable includes a set of key performance indicators to facilitate the project follow-up, encompassing all MICS areas. These indicators refer to the assessment of project performance, progress and risks. These indicators are summarized in a scoreboard (or scorecard) as a way to monitor project progress. This model is a way of monitoring the project's progress monthly.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3476728>

D1.2 Project management handbook

This document provides an overview of the management and procedures that will ensure efficient execution of the project and thus contribute to the production of high-quality project results.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3878688>

D1.3 Project factsheet

Two-page document under booklet format with a brief MICS project presentation in English containing formal references (scientific and administrative contact information, short name, logo, EC funding, participants list, coordinator contact data) and project main goals, key issues, technical approach and expected achievements and impacts.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3981066>

7.2 WP2 – Methods for measuring citizen science impact

D2.1 Report about identified research results ready for review

This report introduces identified reference projects and results for review to support the development of methods for measuring citizen-science impact. The projects provide an insight into the use of citizen science in a wide range of contexts and explore impact-related concepts, methods, tools, implementation frameworks of citizen science, nature-based solutions and river restoration concepts from which indicators can be derived to evaluate the operationalisation of citizen-science concepts in the pilot.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3520467>

D2.2. Report detailing impact-assessment methods adapted to citizen science

The MICS project develops approaches and tools to evaluate citizen-science impacts. These approaches and tools can help to plan and implement projects in ways that lead to more robust outcomes. This report reviews impact-assessment methods and selects relevant methods to capture the impacts of citizen science in distinct domains.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6542309>

D2.3 Impact-assessment methods adapted to citizen science

The draft citizen-science impact assessment framework, which constitutes the structure within which novel and appropriate impact assessment methods will be provided for citizen science projects.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6542325>

D2.4 MICS corpus of knowledge

The MICS project develops approaches and tools to evaluate citizen-science impacts. These approaches and tools can help to plan and implement projects in ways that lead to more robust results. This report describes the structure and process of building the MICS corpus of knowledge (or knowledge base), which forms part of the MICS methodological and technical efforts to capture, analyse and consolidate insights on the impacts of citizen science.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6542348>

D2.5 A multilingual ontology

The multilingual ontology builds on the metadata scheme introduced in Deliverable 3.3 “The MICS Repository”, (see below) and is presented as an associated module describing a project’s impact. It is related to SDG domains, and the ontology’s vocabulary will be based, where possible, on EuroVoc, the EU’s multilingual thesaurus [<http://eurovoc.europa.eu/drupal/>]. This effort to make the ontology multilingual is to ensure the ontology is accessible across the MICS case-study sites and further afield.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3727240>

D2.6 Relevant themes assigned to curators

In the MICS project, curators (reviewers) have been assigned to oversee the results according to specific SDGs. These curators can also act as moderators in discussions on social media. Curators include experts from the MICS partners and the supporter community outside the consortium. Incentives are provided for them in WP5.

D2.7 Finalised version of the conceptual framework – Initial submission

This report presents the draft MICS conceptual framework, which constitutes the overarching structure within which novel and appropriate impact assessment methods will be provided for citizen science projects, including the MICS case studies, and which will inform the MICS online platform.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6542355>

D2.8 Citizen-science model for impact-evaluation research

This report describes the model workflow and rationale for citizen science in impact evaluation. This document presents a detailed, technical description of the MICS platform and interfaces.

7.3 WP3 – Toolboxes for methods application, information visualisation, and delivery

D3.1 Report on the technical requirements

This document sets general, best-practice principles for developing the MICS platform, analyses tools and projects’ results that can be adapted and adopted for developing the MICS platform, and contains initial functional requirements for the development of the MICS platform.

D3.2 Toolbox for Citizen Science Research: Accompanying Documentation Report

This report presents the 2020 status of the development of the MICS platform for measuring impact and the development of input features.

D3.3 The MICS repository

The MICS repository is a storage facility for the data and documents collected, produced and managed by the project, featuring a metadata scheme for common and interoperable data documentation and processing.

D3.4 Participatory adaptive, personalized information-delivery web platform, period – 1 prototype (P1P)

The MICS platform prototype for period 1 presents the first incarnation of the MICS system and its user interfaces. It is intended to be a demonstration of the technology required to produce a stable platform, and a first consideration of some of the usability issues and potential design solutions. It will form the basis for an iterative design process running up to D3.5 (the period-2 prototype), which will more fully involve the assessment methodologies derived in WP2, and respond to the validation activities of WP4.

D3.5 Participatory adaptive, personalized information-delivery web platform, period – 2 prototype (P2P)

The MICS platform prototype for period 2 presents the initial, live version of the MICS system and its user interfaces that are made available to the public. It is intended to be a demonstration of the technology involved, the impact assessment process and the output and guidance supplied through the MICS assessment tools. It involves and operationalises the assessment methodologies and support derived in WP2, and shows the responses to the validation activities of WP4.

7.4 WP4 – Test site development and tool validation

D4.1 Report on pilot testing in the Western Europe Region (UK)

Deliverable 4.1 provides a description of the citizen-science activities and case studies in the UK that the MICS impact assessment will be tested in 2021. Across the UK, citizen science plays an important long-term role in data collection and monitoring before, during and after NBS implementation. Citizen-science activities are widespread across the UK and are an accepted method of engagement, stakeholder collaboration, data collection and monitoring.

The MICS tools will be applied to:

1. Outfall Safari citizen science initiative, which aims to detect and record pollution from surface water outfalls to gather evidence and report on pollution incidents;
2. Riverfly Anglers Monitoring Initiative, which aims to monitor key macroinvertebrate species (riverflies) that are indicators of river water quality; and,
3. Work of the Farming Wildlife Advisory Group, which encourages farmers and volunteers to detect and manage water-quality—related problems.

D4.2 Report on pilot testing in the Southern Europe Region (IT)

Deliverable 4.2 provides a description of the site and set up of citizen science activities in the Italian case study where the MICS impact assessment will be applied. The Italian case study focuses on the Marzenego River and its tributaries which flow into the Venice Lagoon. The nature-based solutions (NBS) along the Marzenego River have involved restoring two wetlands (Oasi Lycaena and Oasi di Noale) and a new NBS project aims to enlarge the Noale Oasis to increase flood water retention and improve biodiversity. These NBS are the focus of the citizen scientist monitoring activities in the case study. Co-design workshops have identified that the following citizen science monitoring activities will take place: water quality monitoring, bacteriological analysis, riparian vegetation monitoring, and aquatic vegetation monitoring.

D4.3 Report on pilot testing in the Central and Eastern Europe Region (HU)

Deliverable 4.3 introduces the MICS citizen science case study at Creek Rákos, Hungary. The deliverable outlines the potential nature-based solutions which could be implemented at the creek and the co-design process used to develop the citizen-science activities. The citizen-science activities that have taken place so far are described, with an outlook on their continuation and the ongoing impact of COVID-19 on these activities

D4.4 Report on pilot testing in the Central and Eastern Europe Region (RO)

Deliverable 4.4 explores the set-up of hands-on citizen science activities for monitoring the water and environmental quality associated with the restoration of Carasuhat Wetland, on the Danube Delta in Romania. This deliverable describes the context of the nature-based solution and co-design of citizen science activities in the MICS Romanian case study.

D4.5 Comprehensive Evaluation Report

Deliverable D4.5 provides a description and evaluation of the findings on the impact of citizen science in the case study sites. The MICS impact assessment approach was applied to the five MICS case study sites across Europe, each of which has differing levels of citizen science engagement and approaches to environmental management. The case studies are:

1. Outfall Safari (UK): aims to use citizen science to detect and record pollution from surface water outfalls to gather evidence and report on pollution incidents;
2. Riverfly Monitoring (UK): aims to monitor key macroinvertebrate species (riverflies) that are indicators of river water quality;
3. Marzenego River NBS Project (Italy): aims to establish a monitoring program to gauge the effectiveness of NBS implemented within the Marzenego River catchment;
4. The Creek Rákos Citizen Science project (Hungary): aims to use citizen science as a means of establishing the baseline condition of the Creek to identify suitable sites for restoration and promote public support for NBS; and,
5. The Carasuhat Wetland NBS Project (Romania): aims to establish a monitoring programme to gauge the effectiveness of wetland NBS implemented in the Danube Delta.

D4.6 Guidance for co-design of citizen science activities in the MICS case-study sites

This report provides detailed guidance for co-designing and enhancing hands-on citizen-science activities in the MICS case-study sites, using a light version of the Ground Truth 2.0 co-design methodology. It is structured as a compendium, providing instructions for the co-design process as well as dedicated structures to capture the results of the activities.

7.5 WP5 – Dissemination and outreach

D5.1 Strategic plan for the exploitation and dissemination of the results (PEDR)

A clear strategy for the widespread dissemination of the project outcomes and deliverables; and the design of an exploitation strategy ensuring the long-term, post-grant sustainability and replicability of the outcomes and the expansion of the end-user base of the MICS platform. Detailed communication plan and materials, including logos, templates for presentations, and presentations about the project for the use of the partners.

D5.2 Open, peer-reviewed report on NBS science

The deliverable addresses major knowledge gaps in strengthening NBSs by the inclusion of citizen science.

D5.3 Recommendations about the assessment of the impact of citizen science

This report presents a Science Brief of recommendations produced by WP2 - 'Methods for citizen science impacts' on how to assess the impacts of citizen science such that they can be disseminated to a wide audience.

D5.4 Nature-Based Solution Science Briefs

Deliverable 5.4 outlines the context for the creation of four NBS policy briefs. These policy briefs are aimed at decision makers to encourage the uptake and application of NBS and contain key recommendations for their implementation.

The content and recommendations of the briefs were derived from a review of the literature and the results of a survey disseminated to practitioners of NBS. The purpose of this survey was to gather evidence regarding the perceptions of NBS practitioners on working within the policy framework for implementing NBS, as well as different factors affecting the uptake and lack thereof of NBS in practice, and recommendations for how these could be overcome.

D5.5 Multimedia resources and policy briefs presenting general and region-specific recommendations

Eight multimedia resources (with subtitles in the relevant languages) and policy briefs presenting general and region-specific recommendations related to measuring the impact of citizen science.

D5.6 The impact of citizen science on society, governance, the economy, the environment and science

The MICS project [mics.tools] has developed a state-of-the-art tool for assessing citizen science's impact. The free-to-use, open-access platform is available to anyone looking to improve their impact assessment. MICS uses 200 variables to determine the impact of a citizen-science project in five areas: society, the environment, the economy, governance, and science and technology. Five case studies explore how citizen scientists work together to monitor nature-based solutions and protect the environment. AI technology has been developed to help analyse the 200 variables.

D5.7 Project website

A website has been developed as a web-based platform for external communication and dissemination. This includes providing public access to project research and activities, reports and presentations, as well as published electronic newsletters.

D5.8 Report on quarterly newsletters, social media posts and updates

This report describes the updated communication strategy of MICS one year into the project. The strategy is made of two parts: (1) a regular, quarterly newsletter which informs about news, events and recent publications; (2) posts and updates on various social-media channels aimed at reaching out to a wider public and getting them interested in the project and its results.

D5.9 Update to plan for the exploitation and dissemination of the results (PEDR)

An updated strategy for the widespread dissemination of the project outcomes and deliverables; and the design of an exploitation strategy ensuring the long-term, post-grant sustainability and replicability of the outcomes and the expansion of the end-user base of the MICS platform.

7.6 WP6 – Ethics requirements

D6.1 H – Requirement No. 1

This document describes the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants, and the informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participation of humans. Templates of the informed consent forms and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) will be kept on file, as well as copies of opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans.

D6.2 POPD – Requirement No. 2

This deliverable confirms that a data protection policy for the project will be kept on file. An evaluation of the ethical risks related to the data processing activities of the project is also presented, including an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under art.35 General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. Detailed information on the informed consent procedures in regard to data processing will be kept on file.

Appendix B - Update to Deliverable 4.5

This appendix can be accessed at [<https://zenodo.org/record/6944694>].

Developing metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts on the environment and society

EC Horizon-2020 Grant Agreement number 824711

Call: H2020-SwafS-2018-2020 (Science with and for Society)

Topic: SwafS-15-2018-2019

Type of action: RIA

UPDATE to Deliverable 4.5 - Comprehensive Evaluation Report

Delivery Year: 2021

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824711.

Living Nature: Adopting Nature-Based Solutions for Safeguarding Freshwater in Central Europe

What are nature-based solutions?

Nature-based solutions (NBS) are defined by the IUCN as “actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems, that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits”.

- NBS are increasingly seen as a **crucial part of the green recovery programme** because they can address the climate, biodiversity, economic inequality and human health crises in a more integrated and therefore cost-effective way;
- **Water is a key strategic resource in Europe**; by managing our land and water differently, using NBS we can better address all of these challenges;
- European countries have made progress towards addressing the loss of aquatic biodiversity, poor water quality and water security, but more work is needed;
- NBS can help us tackle these issues and achieve more sustainable and cost-effective management of freshwater environments;
- NBS are based on inclusive, transparent and empowering governance processes involving local citizens in design, reflecting their needs and aspirations leading to long-term ownership and care for the environment.

Case Study - NBS for Urban Regeneration and Flood Management

Rákos Creek, Budapest, Hungary

The heavily modified urban rivers in Budapest suffer from pollution, loss of biodiversity and lack of space for recreation.

Changing attitudes to the environment have led to the desire to create a ‘green corridor’ along Rákos Creek by improving connectivity with its wetlands and groundwater, by increasing water retention in the urban areas, and constructing a cycle way.

Role of decision makers

More work is required to mainstream NBS and policy actors at different levels have a role to play. This includes:

- Increasing ambition, setting targets and deadlines;
- Identifying water related issues and the NBS that can address them;
- Encourage large-scale projects to tackle multiple issues through incentives.

77% of NBS practitioners do not believe NBS are adequately supported in policy

The benefits include:

- Reduced flood risk;
- Rejuvenation of the urban landscape, providing recreation space;
- Improved water quality.

Local involvement through citizen science activities has increased support and awareness for the project; reconnecting people with their environment and providing cost-effective collection of information about the condition of the Creek.

Practitioners perceive commitment to **long term funding** as an important enabler of NBS uptake

Why we should use nature-based solutions

NBS can help address some of the most urgent water-related challenges:

- **Surface water quality:** Urban rain gardens, wetlands and connected floodplains intercept run-off before it enters the river, reducing nutrient and sediment loads. These solutions can be much cheaper than conventional water treatment.
- **Natural flood management:** Restored meanders, reconnected floodplains and woody material can slow, store and reduce peak flows, preventing downstream flood risk and damage.
- **Water availability:** River and floodplain restoration promote water retention in soils and encourage groundwater recharge, supporting summer flows in rivers and reducing the severity of drought.
- **Habitat restoration and biodiversity:** All NBS provide more space for wildlife by creating, restoring or maintaining existing habitats, reconnecting people with nature.
- NBS are cross cutting, often providing benefits across multiple challenges, including storing carbon and improving landscape aesthetics and recreational amenity.

More resources are required for NBS implementation and operation

Nature-based solutions for people

Local communities can and should be involved in all stages of designing and implementing NBS from early consultation to collaborative and co-design work and implementation, because this will:

- Increase their knowledge, awareness and involvement;
- Engage with a diverse range of people & interests; provide local employment;
- Empower local citizens and involve them in the democratic process;
- Encourage more diverse partnerships, increased ambition and funding possibilities;
- Encourage ownership and early reporting of problems.

Citizen-science work can help encourage active involvement. From our survey, **79%** of practitioners said that the benefits of co-creating citizen science projects include:

- Shared ownership with the community;
- Regular long-term monitoring and inspection;
- Stronger local voice and champions;
- Reconnects people with nature, improving their health and well-being.

Key recommendations

- 1 Integrate NBS within existing policies so that they become mainstream;
- 2 Restore ecosystem functionality and to achieve climate resilience;
- 3 Co-design and implement NBS with local communities;
- 4 Ensure NBS are informed by science and use available evidence of effectiveness.

Project information

Project Coordinator: Earthwatch Website: mics.tools Scientific Coordinator: Luigi Ceccaroni loeccaroni@earthwatch.org.uk Contact Person: Kalrin Nolland knolland@earthwatch.org.uk

DURATION: 1 JANUARY 2019 - 31 DECEMBER 2021 | TOTAL COST: 1,944,428.00 € (100% EUROPEAN-COMMISSION FUNDING)

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Case Study - NBS for Wetland Restoration

Carasuhat Wetland, Danube Delta, Romania

The Danube Delta is Europe's largest wetland habitat.

However, large areas of the wetland have been drained for agriculture and urban development threatening this unique habitat and inhibiting its ability to deliver ecosystem services, such as stormwater storage and filtration of nutrients and pollutants.

Areas of the wetland are being resorted to tackle this problem. This has involved breaching dykes and reconnecting former agriculture land to the Danube to re-establish hydrological conditions suitable for the development of key natural habitats.

- Reduced risk of flooding;
- Water purification and pollutant and nutrient retention;
- Increased public access;
- Hotspot of biodiversity in the region;
- Engagement in design and continuing involvement.

Local involvement through citizen science activities has increased support and awareness for the project.

Role of decision makers

More work is required to mainstream NBS and policy actors at different levels have a role to play. This includes:

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